

YRI_JH_NISSI_uwaterloo_transcripts_MarkedUP__for__clarities_by_XAVIER- _noubissi_NOUNDOU _____	2
YRI_JH_NISSI_uwaterloo_transcripts_Original_from_The_STUDENT_CENT- RE_nancy _____	4
YRI_CV_ENGLISH _____	6

University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
 Canada
 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Jeffrey M. Caelli
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: **Noumbissi Noundou, Xavier**
 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

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 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Winter 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: **04/30/2015**

Milestones

Program: **Engineering Doctoral**
PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: **Completed**
 Date Completed: **12/20/2011**
 Grade: **CR**

End of Graduate Official Transcript

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Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caell
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 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: Noubissi Noundou, Xavier
Student ID: 20284586
Ontario Education Nbr: 445938806

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

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Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

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<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

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<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: 04/30/2015

Milestones

Program: Engineering Doctoral
 PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: Completed
 Date Completed: 12/20/2011
 Grade: CR

End of Graduate Official Transcript

- "Datou, KEMAJOU" Cameroonian gendarmerie colonel indic PAULETTE AZEFA tried to ASSASSINATE myself, openly, in front of at least 7 people, on Yaounde street, on January 09th, 2024.
- Kemajou spouses talk to people walking across roads that they shalln't perform christian cross-signs since these interrupts sorcery they are doing on people walking on roads (June 3rd, 2024).
- Secret (hidden) orders of any type SHALL be out of civilian society.
- Cameroonian SHALL DEACTIVATE any kind of army soldiers estate, as SWITZERLAND has done in the past.
- Its not a good idea to judge people based on suspicious behavior, and not, real proven or not lived really facts.
- ROSE sangoun, a BIRTH GIVER of mine, SHALLNT ANYMORE be causing so much trouble into my life because she entertains a rostricrucian affair with Prof. Dr. rer. pol. JEAN-CLAUDE SHANDA-TONME; AND with 'DORIS betebugang Gweh', 'tchoutchui-teutchou-noumeni-ingrde-ingrid-Chandriandri', 'Hugues Ntomani Tiako'; 'Dr. Henriette Pola', and her spouse "Dr. Laurent tchandeu".
- People such as KEMAJOU, who acts as a colonel gendarmerie of Cameroon army ARE ALWAYS TRYING to overcome criminal laws of Geneva.
- I don't want to be living with people who has as profession the killing of other people.
- Rose sangoun sister, (Justice) DOROTHEE SHANDA NDJATIE, HAS TRIED to kill me by police force illegally in February 2021, as I have a file on judge HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA at DOUALA-ndokoti JUSTICE Palace ! • LAQUINTINE'S Psychiatrist EYOUN CHRISTIAN, MD, was involved together with 8 other persons at night around 11 : 30PM so to hijack my privately owned property in Douala-CITE-DES-PALMIERS. • JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMAI from same tribal tribe as ACCUSED Psychiatrist main offender (sawa-douala) ! • IT SEEMS "Dr christian eyoum, MD" the corrupted CPDM psychiatrist wanted myself to be sodomized by "BERTRAND" who broke the seal of my gate in steel.
- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like "Peter Alan Burh" 'Emmanuel-baleba-faux-pasteur' 'Brigitte-ekindi' 'magne-narcisse-qc-satan' 'robert-billy-joe-bob-tabet-depse-pd' 'NDZIE' 'PRC-présidence de la république du Cameroun' 'CHAPELLE DE LA GLOIRE DE CHRIST - marc denis djeng djeng - alias pasteur marc' 'jp-kamgain' 'psy-acteur-Ebongue (ing. pétrolier)' 'EMMANUEL-idoit; hors-mis agent-immobilier-soumbil (6 90 60 75 63)' 'santaire;SAPEUR-POMPIER-de-malheur-anti-gang;civil;indic-gendarme-policier-uniforme-medic' 'NORBERT tchatat' 'Bitoungi (douanes)' 'David Moniaux' 'Aurélie Yagno Kamdoun' 'DR. FOSSO-séd' 'Soot-canadian' 'sarah-landy-canadian-citizen' 'tchangoue-labforge.ca' 'carine-alias-edith - LELÉ - NJOUGE - TCHANA' 'Julien-mboutou; santé publique' 'Dan Wasula doua' - so called pastor baptist church 'KAMGA adamo - demon' 'Cameroon-chief-of-state; CAMEROUN:' 'SANDRINE yimbu' 'CHENGWA 'DJOMO-Sawa-gilles-ézechiel' 'didi-ruben' 'mama-fouda' 'INES ngakou' 'Serge Achille Popoussi NONO - sed - cmr' '[ingrde-tchoutchui-noumbissi;ingrid-tchitcheui-noumbissi;ingrde-teutchou-noumeni;ingrid-teuntchou-noumeni]; [NROUBANG] (dôme) [TCHUDDANG-séd-pré] [NGONGANG] 'Hôpital Jamôl' 'assassins;délingués.' 'LAURENT-tchandeu-henriette-pola' 'VOUFFOU manuela-psy-malade-mentale' 'alain-elame' 'Francis magloire come nkoulou' 'ZOUUMPE-jacky-diane' 'Pelagie METOUMO, epse tchoutou; hors-mis maître Pelagie METOUMO, epse tchoutou' 'BIYA (Paul et Chantal en particulier)' 'DAILMERCHRYSLER AG' 'Belvianne meleu nossi' 'Jean LOÏC sieve' 'GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl' 'maman THERÈSE de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joel.' 'rigobert; géomètre; JEAN-bernard de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joel.' 'Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA; hors-mis maître Synclaire SCHULZE-SMIDT' 'Franck biya' 'M. onguéné (S2TBED-biya-franck)' 'David (GATE SOLUTION CENTER)' 'KREYENHOP (BLG logistics, CDU politicians)' 'Achilles Kouam (PAUL fokam kammgone)' 'Thierry Nyamen (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)' 'catholic-church' 'Criminal-DST.' 'MOISE-yamkam-tebiwo' 'REZA kopae (riskview inc.)' 'Thomas NDIE DJOTIO' 'Christelle-akamba-et-autres-noms-de-akamba' 'VALERIE' 'ALT LE PLUS' 'Nestor KENPACK (N.K. quincallerie)' 'atanga-nji-paul' 'Daniela-siemens-OCS-erlangen' 'Menguéné Mvindi' 'TCHIEUFFA' 'Audrey NGUETTE tchangma' 'MBA-Claude bisseg' 'samaneh navabpour; amirhossein vakili' 'JHANE-ayachi' 'ZABER-algérien-bremen' 'DZUKOU-tate-foiso-viviane' 'ROSTAND-moungam' 'KOM-marcel-rostand-mepo' 'Irene-ines-ngakou-temou-FAINEANTE-nesse-bordellerie' 'VANELLE-JUNIOR-laure AZEFA-gang' 'GODRICK chekete H.' 'pasteur Landry' 'Eric Joël KOM SIPA' 'Grégoire Owona (CPDM general secretary)' 'SANGO (Spouse Bernadette NOUNDOU(CMR-dgre)' 'gendarme essono en civil (loga-loga-aurelien)' 'GÉNÉRAL DE CORPS D'ARMÉE boubou.' 'consortium-conrad-black-ROTTSCHEIDT' 'GALAX-YVES-LANBRY-ETOGA-chien' 'jean-yang-CMU' 'HOGA-HOGA-AURÉLIEN' 'BORIS tossou; mbuembe-kevina-laure.' 'mezang-atmev INGRID.' 'TOM ball-mrs' 'maître-docteurs-professeurs.' 'JEAN-pierre moubeb' 'Chef-supérieur-douala.deido.-3ème degré' 'CHRISTIAN eyoum; laquintine; psy' 'SHANDA NDJATIE' 'MAXIME napoa eteme' 'sandy-séd-beidu; jo-atele' 'joanne atlee' 'chauffeurs-soudeurs-souffleurs-gardiens-jaune-SARL-société' '(a so called baptist church pastor) Dr. PAUL SIMON nomo, Psy.D.' 'Majeed Mike (quantstamp.com)' 'LEO passos (quantstamp.com)' 'Iuc; masc. hypolithe tekeu.' 'Eunice GAPIE Yemte' 'Yves Francis DANTEU' 'TEUNTCHOU-chandriand-noumeni' 'Winnie-shanda-joel..' 'Alexis TCHIEUYA' 'Gervais Nana' 'JEAN CLAUDE SHANDA TONME' 'JACKSON-séd-njeutcha (Conquète.)' 'Jean-Paul YAMTICHE (Afriland first bank; Intelligensia)' 'BISSCKE; nkondo-sodomiseur' 'JEAN-PIERRE kamgain' 'Bernadette NOUNDOU, Epse SANGO (cmr DGRE)' 'agent-santé.' 'Gailie-idoite-dodo.' 'RAOUL Prince njonkep (SED)' 'ERIC BODEN' 'Prof. Dr. Xavier Siew Noundou (CMR-dgre)'. 'M. André Édoucké' 'Michéle mvondo-psy;biya-régime' 'JULES neta noundou - (cmr-dgre)' 'temp FABRICE-WILFRIED-siemens-canadian-armed-forces; Prof. Dr. med. Norbert SIEMENS (CMR-séd)' 'Pharmacy fiango-ngoe-peter-AKUME' 'Ondréj Lhoták' 'Dr. Chantal NOUNDOU, Epse ... (cmr DGRE)' 'ANNIE METIAM' 'terreur - ;HONORÉ WOUCHÉ' 'POKAM-KWAM' 'Serge, jérusalem apostolat' 'NOUMBISSI' 'Guimezap' 'GEORGETTE' 'Victor Noundou Koliou cmr-séd' 'CHRISTIAN rikong ngyeung' 'Hilaire-yimidoj-bertrand-nguere; ancien-séd-gras-savoye.' 'igc-clovis-telecom-assassin'; 'CLOVIS-kemmegne' 'Jeanne MVONDO' 'CHETA' 'rodrigue-alain-sienchie-ngongang' 'angela WOLFGANG fernand JR owona' 'fanfan (GAUTHIER) SHANDA tonme' 'DR. GADJEU francis aimé tchana' 'lute' 'Patrick lam, Ph.D., P.Eng.' 'JON eyolfsson' 'Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Jan Peleska' 'Patrick'; ALL-others to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.
- People like PAUL BIYA shalln't be called president of all Cameroonian anymore because as CPDM ruling party, they harass people that don't call themselves from RDPC!

CONTACT

- Address: YECEFOIQ - "Immeuble YERITH"- barrière - Simbock, Mfoundi 6, Yaounde, Cameroon
- located opposite side of Biya's S2TBED forestry society (since 2015 officially) !
• Email: Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com

CITIZENSHIP ; PLACE OF BIRTH

Cameroonian, no other citizenship ; Douala (Littoral, Cameroon)

UPLOADED a copy of national id (N.20190242230510554) onto "https://www.facebook.com" this year 2024.

TEACHING STATEMENT

- [Teaching] and [Advising] is my priority at time since in Cameroon Software inception is very long and tedious because Cameroon authorities, Especially SED.
2. My 1st professor and best educator is [prof. dr. rer. nat. habil. JAN-peleska], at the University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany; The 1st best teacher as of now was "prof. dr. dr. ULRICH KRAUSE-dépsé, at the University of Bremen; as well"; THE 1st best leader & 2nd best teacher as of now was "Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick] Lam, at the [University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA]".
3. I endeavor to teach what makes my research vivid ["RM: Program Software Runtime Monitoring"] and useful for young and adult people around the world; I can teach almost everything in Computer Sciences; I haven't practiced Computer Graphics, and Computer Imaging programming at all.

RESEARCHING GOALS IN COMPUTER SOFTWARE ENGINEERING - [CONTINUED]

- Create a very cheap and pragmatic Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software: (e.g. YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM[?]).
2. CREATE a market place where stock exchanges occur real-time; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME] is used as platform for valuation of stocks; And for stock exchanges. THE market place is a physical place in "YERITH-R&D building"; THE physical stock exchanges occur outside of "YERITH-R&D building"; just a plot of land '5 meters' away on the opposite side of road leading to "YERITH R&D" !
3. CREATE a computing device for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that would be a certified product with at least ISO, and CE stamps : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]; See also Fig. 22.

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING ASSOCIATIONS MEMBERSHIPS

- Current: "acm: The Association for Computing Machinery"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING LITERATURE REVIEWS

- OOPSLA 2010

PROFESSIONAL INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCES

- IMRT radiation therapy at SIEMENS OCS Erlangen-BAVARIA-Germany 2008; [FSE-soqua 2006]; PLDI 2009; IBM CASCON 2010; MITACS ONTARIO 2012; PLDI 2012

PROFESSIONAL RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS / INTERESTS

- [JUDICIAL information] | [PUBLICATIONS] | [Figures] | [Tables] | [Trang] | [TALKS] | [Latest] | [Resume / CV - Overview] | [Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise] | Publications list on "www.zenodo.org"
• Operating System Debian Linux Distribution Contribution for customers of "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"; "YERITH-NISSI.". Bash; DEBIAN LINUX; Jan. 2017 -
• ERP Software: "YERITH-ERP-9.0"[?]; git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0 C++; Qt 5; Mar. 2015 -
• Software Engineering-Formal Methods [?] | [1c] / Software Validation / Software Verification CASE tools [YRI_QVGE[24.24], RT-Tester, MBT[1b]]
• Software Testing [22.22] (also with "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH"). YRI_QVGE[1b], [MASTER THESIS[?], RT-Tester, MBT[1b]], JUNIT 4 Tutorial[1]
A. Web [JAVA Dynamic Taint Analysis[3] | Qt 5-Designer as WYSIWYG Tool | Development (YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0) | Cyber-Safety | Security]
1. JudoDB, with "Dr. Patrick Lam (doctor-Ph.D. advisor of mine)"; git https://github.com/patricklam/judodb GTW, PHP; JAVA; June 2014 - Nov. 2014
B. WEB Cyber-Security[2] [?] [3] [?] (PLG SEMINAR AT DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)
C. Information Flow Policy Control; Typstate-API usage rule checking; Dynamic Program Analysis Monitoring
1 A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library; git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; June 2022 -
1 Algorithmic trading [13.13.7] | YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime
FOSS Code location, EXCEPT for commercial CASE drawing tool : git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif C++; Qt-Dbus; June 2022 -
3 A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus; git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis JAVA; Firebug; Jan. 2013 - Apr. 2013
D. Static Program Code Analysis Verification; Compilers; Verifiable DSL (Verifiable Domain-Specific Languages)
20.20 Open Source (FOSS) Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; git https://github.com/yerothd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; July 2023 -
1d Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata Set-Algebra; Sep. 2004 - Dec. 2004
34 Ph.D. disser.: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM; git https://github.com/AmesianX/saint LLVM; C++; JAVA
1d A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language; git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; Apr. 2023 -
32 JAVA static code analysis [34] | Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software LLVM; SOOT; JAVA

SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION — HIGHLIGHTS — [CONTINUED]

- "Management Psy Human Resource Course" - Collège Integ, Douala, Littoral, Cameroun — Taught by "Dr. Jean Moubeb, Psy.D." Jan. 2020 - June 2020

CHEIFTAINCY / MISCELLANEOUS

- KING YERITH-NISSI. (Prophet of Jeovah-nissi, "Isaiah 45" (SINCE nov. 14; 2014) in HOLY BIBLE, PAROLE DE VIE-(Amis pour toujours) - French language)
• I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 12".
• I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 1", named 'Fidèle, et Véritable'.
• Creator and Professor at YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), a subsidiary of YERITH R&D
• "High Qualified Person-migrant in CANADA (Québec, then Ontario) for 9 years until August 2014".
• Driving license class B - Cameroon & Canada

PROFESSIONAL TOOLS AND PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0, MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** [YRI_QVGE](#)[13.13], UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, [VALKYRIE YERITH](#)[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming & Compiler Frameworks:** DIFF, Patch, Tx1, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

UNIVERSITY LEVEL TEACHING (AS A TEACHING ASSISTANT PH.D. CANDIDATE; THEN A "DOCTOR-PHD")

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (OCTOBER 2009 – APRIL 2015)

- [Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance \(ECE 453 / SE 465\)](#) | [Methods and Tools for Software Engineering \(ECE 650\)](#) | [Foundations of Software Engineering \(ECE 651\)](#) | [Programming for Performance \(ECE 459\)](#) | [Computer Networks \(ECE 428\)](#) | [Compilers \(ECE 351\)](#) | [\[C++ Laboratory \(ECE 250\)\]](#).

ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 1

- [Start-up YERITH R&D, Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON](#) March 2025 – Currently
PROFESSOR DOCTOR-ENGINEER (PR. PROF. DR.-ING.) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]), at YECEFOIQ, CEO
- [IUC \(Institut Universitaire de la Côte\), Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON](#) 2019
Web Software Developer Consultant (NUMERHIS-ERP Web Application Development); advised by Hypolithe Tekeu, MASC
- [IAI \(Institut Africain d'Informatique\) Cameroon, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON](#) 2016
Professor (Prof.) – Consulting Lecturer (Computer Architecture for Software Engineers in anglophone section); advised by: Ing. (B.Sc.) Salabessi (and Mr. Nanga)
- [Professional and Academic Degree \[Ph.D. in Computer Science \(Specialization : Programming Languages\)\]](#) March 10, 2015 !
University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA
PhD Comprehensive Examination (DR.-ING. (PhD)) – ECE-University of Waterloo December 20, 2011 !
PhD Research Seminar [TALK] – ECE-University of Waterloo April 16, 2014
PhD Dissertation Defence (Ph.D.) – CS-University of Waterloo January 2015
doctoral "Ph.D. degree" dissertation (Excerpt of Full not required text, by Patrick LAM, Ph.D.): *Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM*
(January 14, 2026) Addendum of co-related research in Program Analysis: *Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software by Program Analysis FOR Safety & Security* (<https://zenodo.org/records/10990601>)
- ★ [The University of Waterloo \(ECE at WatForm\), Ontario, CANADA](#) September 01, 2012 – March 10, 2015
Professor (PostDoctoral Fellow; Prof. – Expert in a domain of science) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]) at ECE (*program analysis & software testing research, and teaching (also related courses) | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 8 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.*
"Graduate-student 1: Divam Jain (CS-MMATH, JAVA-SOOT) | Graduate-student 2: Zheng (Felix) Fang (ECE-MASc, Divam's research continuation) | [ALL STUDENTS]"
"Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Igor Ivkovic | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh | Advisor 3: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Sivoththaman Siva"
"Colleague 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Colleague 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naem | Colleague 3: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni | **Colleague 4: Prof. Dr. Godrick H. Chékété** | **Colleague 5: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. mahesh tripunitara** | **Colleague 6: Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside** | **Colleague 7: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. LEO passos** | "Colleagues in christianity (Prof. Dr. Yaw Boakye-Agyeman, Nana Yaw, Eric Brefo-Mensah, Chiwanza Kasanga, Mushota Kasanga and spouse Timi) – -ATTENDED "koinonia church in bloomingdale, ON"; "apostle continuation church in brampton, ON"."
- [IBM CANADA Ltd., Markham, Ontario, CANADA \(SABBATICAL-year from The-University-of-Waterloo-Ontario-Canada.\)](#) January 01, 2012 – August 31, 2012
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer IBM Canada LTD before starting employment.
Graduate Intern (JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compilation Optimization for IBM Websphere); advised by Prof. Vijay Sundaresan; and Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam
- ★ [PROFESSIONAL \(AND ACADEMIC\) DEGREE. Doctor of Engineering \(academic equivalent to a "doctoral PhD in Electrical and Computer Engineering"\) \[D.ENG. \(DR.-ING. in "French"\)\]](#) | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 7 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
[Engineering Doctoral Ph.D. degree Program \(Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD\)](#) at The University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011 !
► **"DOCTOR-ENGINEER [DR.-ING. (D.ENG. in "English")]" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing & Verification & Analysis)**
► **Successfully Passed PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011" – Overall Grade 88% [A+] Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering (ECE)**
Research Proposal (doctoral Ph.D. Thesis in Electrical and Computer Engineering): *Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software*
Mathematics Subject Classification: 68—Computer Science
Computer Science Subject Classification: Software Engineering, Program Verification, Program Analysis (static code analysis, dynamic program analysis)
Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naem | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Advisor 3: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- [The University of Waterloo \(ECE at WatForm\), Ontario, CANADA](#) September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011
Teaching Assistant & Research Assistant for Computer Software Engineering (program analysis (static code and dynamic analysis) research, and teaching assistantship in computer software engineering); Advised by Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, and Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- [Post-Master Work with SIEMENS Healthineers \(OCS – Varian\), Erlangen, Bayern, GERMANY](#) November 01 2007 – July 31 2009
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer "SIEMENS AG" before starting employment.
Software-Engineer (Junior Software Developer) (CE-FDA certified software code development; Radiation Therapy DMIP communication control protocol C++ development); advised by: Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAVIDGLIA, and Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG.
- ★ [PROFESSIONAL \(AND ACADEMIC\) DEGREE. Diplom-Informatiker \(academic equivalent to a "Master 2 in Computer Science"; 270-ECTS points\) | around \\$400 Euros for a semester payment; 11 semesters including GERMAN language courses time included.](#)
I HAVE SACRED this diploma certificate ("Duplicate by Prof. Dr.-Ing. UTE bormann and Prof. Dr. Kerstin Schill; from November 01, 2017)" in front of BISHOP at St-Patrick Church in Toronto-downtown, ONTARIO, CANADA; just 3 weeks after resigning my shit-CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP at KITCHENER-WATERLOO criminal justice court [Living in Salvation Army Shelter near Justice Court.]
[Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree in Computer Science Program](#) at The Elite-University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY October 01, 2002 – May 25, 2007
► **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing) – Grade 1.6/4 [A+] Department of Mathematics and Computer Science**
Diplomarbeit (Master Thesis): *Statistical test case generation for reactive systems* | Advisor: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- [AGBS at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY](#) September 01, 2006 – February 28 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (A 'UML 2.0 profile statecharts' plugin for 'Borland-Together'); advised by: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- ["IMMIGRATION CANADA delivers myself a High Qualified Person-migrant permanent residency for CANADA"](#) 2005
FORMER-family member in Canada : "Théodore Wandji Ngongang (5850 Rue Souart Apt 7, H3S 2E8, Montreal, QC, Canada)"
I already passed my Bachelor's degree in CS ("Vordiplom in Informatik Certificate") before gaining High Qualified Person Permanent Resident Card
- [Bergmann Automaten GmbH \(now Gewete GmbH\), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY](#) March 01, 2005 – April 31, 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (WERKSTUDENT) (JAVA servlet and C++ communication protocol development); advised by: Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH (and Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER)
- [ZMML at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY](#) February 01, 2003 – February 28, 2005
(Part-Time) WEB AND "RAD" APPLICATION DEVELOPER (Creating websites, and RAD-server self tests evaluation programs); advised by Prof. Dr. rer. pol. Klaus Jürgen Bönkost

CONVICTIONS ABOUT CIVIL SOCIETY – CONTINUED – 2

- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like 'Jeanne-chantal andela;vendeuse-sauvette.' 'nguema;huissier-de-justice;tchopba' 'churches; in USA-abroad; or whatsoever similar; so-called humanitarian.' 'road-seller; seller anywhere else' 'relatives' 'agent' 'SOLITA-voisine-sed' 'IRIS Mbieukop; pof.' 'agent-ministère-défense-cameroun.' 'MARTIAL takala; DELAURE takala' 'JEAN LOUIS ROSTAND mougam; et associés' 'YVES mogo' 'henri-bertrand-ngatchou (Best Car Care & SERVICES)' 'YAGER MABOMA; to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.

		SCHOLARSHIPS & AWARDS
• Ontario Graduate Scholarship (OGS; 4000–\$CAD per term)		2009 – 2015 (a total of 15 terms)
		FREE TIME HOBBIES
• Aikido, Swimming, and "Gospel Choir 'GEORGIA MASS CHOIR'" listening.		
		ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 2
■ HABILITATION, equivalent ♦ Topic: "Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime" Start-up YERITH R&D , Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON Proposal: YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (Details at link 1)		June 01, 2022 – Currently
■ Start-up YEROTH R&D , Yaoundé, CENTER region, CAMEROON Software Verification & Validation Fellow, CEO		October 2018 – November 2023
■ Start-up Yeren Labs, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO		September 2017 – September 2018
■ Start-up Yeren, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO		April 2015 – August 2017
× [PKFokam Research Institute, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON] Professor (Prof.) Ph.D. -seeker (Static Code Analysis Research from WATERLOO.); advised by: [Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne], & [Dr. Ing. JUSTIN-bomda]; [and M. Samuel-DIMITE] "JAN-peleska" & "University of Waterloo" try to hijack myself through this 2-days-job-contract- [All people pro-eminent persons I have seen at his banks, "including Deceased gay-pd GERVAIS mendoze", are in prison !!! (419–scam)]		
■ Judo-Québec , Montreal, Quebec, CANADA (Part-Time) Web Development Consultant (JAVA SE 7, GWT, PHP) for JUDODB; advised by: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam		JUNE 2014 – NOVEMBER 2014
■ RiskView Inc. , Toronto, Ontario, CANADA Software Consultant for Finance Software Security (SCALA servlet development for Finance); advised by: Reza Kopae, M.Sc.		January 2013
■ We4IT GmbH , Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Software Development Internship (J2EE, MySQL web application for medical personal training management); advised by Dipl.-Inf. Stephan Sucker		June 2005 – July 2005
■ SGS Cameroon , Douala, littoral REGION, CAMEROON System administration internship (Computer networked installation; employee desktop technical support; (MS Windows NT, MS Windows 2000, etc.); advised by CHENGWA, & ...)		September 2004
■ bremen4u GmbH , Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Web development internship, System Administration (MySQL, RedHat linux, JSP, PHP, HTML5, CSS); advised by Martin, B.Sc.		March 2004
■ IWT at The University of Bremen , Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY (Part-Time) Student Metal Processing & Measurement Helping Scientist; advised by: Dipl.-Ing. Sven Bengelsdorf.		October 2002 – January 2003
■ DaimlerChrysler AG , Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Industrial Chain Worker (Kfz-Schlosser Helper); setting of Mercedes personal cars seat belts		June 2002 – August 2002
■ Briël & Kjær , Technology Park – University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY (Part-Time) Student Helper (event management); advised by: Dipl.-Pol. Torben (and Dr. Woehring)		July 2002 – September 2002
■ Cyberix , Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON Web Development Internship (HTML, CSS); advised by: Ing. Fogueum (and Théodore Wandji Ngongang)		October 2001 – November 2001
■ GCE A Level in Exact Sciences; BACCALAURÉAT C (Mathematics, etc.) Grade of "11.59 / 20" Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		2000
■ GCE O Level in Exact Sciences; PROBATOIRE C (Mathematics, etc.) Grade of "12.09 / 20" Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1999
■ B.E.P.C (Brevet d'Études DU PREMIER CYCLE) Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1997
■ C.E.P.E (CERTIFICAT D'ÉTUDES PRIMAIRES ÉLÉMENTAIRES) Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1993

PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION LANGUAGES

- FRENCH, and ENGLISH CAMEROON; NATIVE
- "GERMAN DSH LANGUAGE CERTIFICATE", Sehr Gut (Very Good) April 2002 (UNIVERSITY OF DORTMUND, DORTMUND, NRW, Germany)
- "ENGLISH USA TOEFL-IBT", Grade 86 June 2018 (Hamilton, Ontario, Canada)

[SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION] – ADDENDUM

- "Online Software Security Course" – Stanford University, California, USA June 2013 – August 2013
- "CUT 1 – Certificate in University Teaching1" – University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA 2010
- "First Summer School on Formal Techniques" – NSF, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA May 22, 2011 – May 27, 2011
- "Graduate Student English Training Course" – Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Montreal, Quebec, Canada Aug. 2009
- "Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) Preparation Course" – Concordia University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada June 2007
- "C Programming Language Preparation Course" – UY 1, ENSPY, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon — Taught by "Master-1 Mr. Donfack (ENSPY)" Aug. 2001 – Sep. 2001

5. **CREATE** a software component full-featured that enables ERP-stock data import using a technology Kind-of VOICE-to-text !
6. Create a framework that allows for formal method specification of static dataflow analyzes as temporal property verification formulas;
Such a framework generate code software as static staged dataflow analyzes for its users.
More importantly, I will try to reuse previous work done for [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#) research work, as part deliverable.
7. **TRY** to integrate research results on software security in "YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum "; from Vijay GANESH research (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>); MOST possibly using "SDMM".
8. Automatic generation of web HTML pages from a Domain Specific Language (DSL) that is more approachable for a high level programming language perspective (i.e: similar to C++ / JAVA): YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0[27.27].
9. Create and render software analysis, debugging, and testing tools as easy as possible to use, with only finite automata theory background; and / or Typestate-API usage rule checking typestate-API knowledge (e.g.: [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#), [SDMM\[1d\]](#), [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#), VALKYRIE-VALGRIND[20.20]).
10. Prepare a course on "Software System Security Vulnerability Detection and Analysis". I prepare this course material so to implement a software system for protecting other software from malware.
11. Create a stand-alone software product that enables medical physician to augment their efficiency in terms of patient work flow throughput : 'yerith-sante-organigramme'
Even Dr. Christian EYOUM find this utility-tool very impressive in terms of effectiveness & simplicity if this could be really in his world (PSY) implemented !
12. Create a stand-alone tool that generates code for creating statechart C++ code for mealy machine state diagram ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).
This tool is specifically created and programmed for generating code that uses checkboxes to select options for Graphical User Interface [GUI] code.
13. Position "static dataflow analysis research and techniques" as similar as runtime verification (i.e.: circle 4 in Figure 18; e.g.:PH.D. THESIS[32], [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#)).
14. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an CE—ISO—related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE—ISO certifications for Healthcare : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

1.1 CAMEROON new country name based on CHRISTIANITY-jesus-of-nazareth-NAME-and-TRIBES-number

Changing CMR onto YERITH as country name since JESUS-OF-Nazareth utilizes 12 237 as number of tribes for its ISRAEL tribe.

2.2 National Currency BILLS and / or COINS

- CMR YERITH NATIONAL Money currency as 'YERITH-dollar ("JESUS-OF-Nazareth"-dollar)'.

THIS money currency bill and / or coin system will be backed by computing systems from YERITH R&D; AS open-sourced products :

- 1.) YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME; A software-system product created out of Enterprise Resource Planing Software YRI_QVGE[13.13.7] that is also usable as an algorithmic trading system !

3.3 National Identification

1. A system allowing any of the 3 documents cited below as valid official identification for any official or unofficial activity shall be implemented in Central CEMAC:

1. Valid NATIONAL IDENTITY CARD
2. Valid PASSPORT CEMAC—CEDEAO
3. Valid bank account id.
4. ALL PERSONS working with weapons or force by law have to be identified with names on badge wherever they are outside of their working places.

A bank account id IS in effect linked to a Valid national identity card.

""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" for instance, a cousin paternal "French—germain" of mine, Could afford for a law school with a bank account that wasn't really linked with his by birth official IDENTITY documents !"

MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87) also possesses a diplomatic passport at least or equivalent because he also works for MINREX.

IN effect, "MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" was a diplomat before joining the LAW-school in LAGOS—corrupt.

I could notify this since the law school of lagos he attended didn't issue for a certificate with exact same official birth identity names as written thereof.

THIS COUSIN OF MINE IS A CRIMINAL in all systems of justice worldwide.

2. 1 system, computerized, and / or, a text registry book shall be created to register any Cameroon citizen with no need for any citizen to walk around with a national identity card.
3. There are some drawbacks as for instance mentioned on the website of FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION, in the United States of America (USA), to have a centralized registration system for citizen or People living inside a country !
4. "A gervais nana (gersatelgmail.com)" I know somewhere in YDE, seems to be connected as a free-mason to ""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO"" .
"GERVAIS NANA" must be investigated since I know "TEBIWO—YAMKAM—MOÏSE" Is a murderer in all systems.
5. I remember having an issue with a screen of a laptop I bought to a place (GERSATEL) owned by "Gervais NANA" ; after 1 day, A blur appeared on the screen and I wasn't reimbursed.
6. It seems "WELADJI" a burglar that I went with at Gendarmerie D'AKWA—SUD in 2023 because he apparently tried to steal 20, 000 FRANCS as a non used money for a purchase item that I ordered from his shop at DLA—douala—bar;

"WELADJI" WAS NOW in position in another shop where I started buying stuff for my customers. "Moubeb-Jean" is working just at opposite side of this computer hardware shop in Douala: "COLLEGE INTEG".

7. "ISAAC TEUNTCHOU-poltron-peggist" , a father in law of 1 uterine sister of my person; "Ingride NOUMBISSI TCHITCHUI (heiratet (SPOUSE): Dipl.-Ing. (FH)—CHANDRIAND Teuntchou Nouneni, MSc.)" is trying to hijack from my propriety all my real-estate.
8. ~~shanda tonne jean-claude; bob tabet-peggist-Deido-plage-poisson-braisé, the idiot that sleeps with rose-sangnou my genitor; AND with her sister Dorothee shanda owona~~ " (LEVITICUS 20 : 12 — 14)."

"OLAMCAM (tel.:6 52 12 65 57 — —georges-kamdem) (peggist working in Douala shipment-haven) owner Tabet-bob (OWNING a house in "bonaberi"; money from bribery in ONTARIO according to JP-kamgain sayings) & friends GEORGES-kamdem; & JP-kamgain; they have tried to sodomize myself with Christian-eyoum-c.p.d.m [by trying to say to JP-kamgain-to act as a friend-of-myself]. "

"BOB-tabet is an ancient jail-black-attendee of ONTARIO justice system that escaped Canada by talks I heard [of KAMGAIN].""

"[Culprit-JP-kamgain] told me once [TABET-ROBERT] wanted HR-module payment services for his employees in DOUALA.'

9. ISAAC-teuntchou, the idiot that sleeps with his daughter—in-law; TEUNTCHOU-nouneni-chandriand is currently trying to hijack my property of DLA-cité-des-palmiers-beedi, BY Sending INGRID to my attorney of law so to try to say that SHE wants some money from my current ongoing rental agreement with a so called MELEU-belvianne, AND her fiancée called SEWE-idiot-toie.
10. "Audrey-NGUETIE-tehamga" shalln't anymore go and seek people from my former places of work to try to tell them I abandon her after 1—night.
THIS disgusting megere wasn't capable of understand I cannot be fornicating with someone that Cannot imagine herself as a wife in a non-gay homosexual matrimonial house AS i could observe from her gay—white-salsa friends & sister "YOLLANDE-nguetie married at that other senegalese in Montreal
"TCHAMAHA ntaata GUTTEMBERG" & "Remi POUASSI-taata" who are my blood-family (father-theo-chien-noumbissi-batchieu—babouantou) cousins & 'also blood-village people of MAURICE-nguetie' & 'Audrey-nguetie-tehamga'; SHALL know that Homosexuality is a disease from a BORN—again christian point of view: ITS cure is living without any sexual encountering as proclaimed in " 1 Corinthians 7 : 1 " & " 1 Corinthians 7 : 38—40 " !
11. When you say to your children not to open a door when a child of you senior or whoever arrives at your home when you are not there; YOU—victor should think that you were coming to my house when I was aged under 7 years old.
YOU should think that never my father or my mother said that to you. IT means you were may be trying to kill someone in that marriage; AS you are coined today by ROSE who told me not to eat anymore from your household !

12. VICTOR-koliou-serpent—Tchandeu-gay thinks he is linked to myself by my late father; I Have already told this culprit & wretched canadian-traveler as a assassin that could be even arrested just at airport; Like I was faultily arrested by canadian-faked police so to destroy my luxurious image !

THIS criminal worldwide, since he even called before I attended 3 days & nights at his junior-est brother DEMO—noundou house in Hamburg—Germany; to say that Demo could even not even respond to any call of myself because I did not notify him—demo when I was leaving Cameroon.

There is a fake idolatry—people like "bamileke" demo & tchandeu-family-noundou; That if you want to attend a living at someone place, you must call onto him before you arrive. THIS kind of guja—assassin-diplomat schizophrenic-idea is in fact to listen to calls & organize fake routes with spies everywhere so to dictate how your daily life shall look like !.—MVONDO.

Following items from previous page; JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

9. Multiple or DOUBLE citizenship **SHALL NOT be allowed** since Africans are not well behaved to use and observe strict rules that are due to protect civilians with only 1 citizenship appurtenance.
10. Double citizenship with following countries that harasses honest Cameroonian like myself shalln't be allowed:
- Canada
 - United States of America (USA)
 - Germany
 - Any country where a gay-homosexual-marriage is pronounced in a so-called **"JESUS-OF-NAZARETH"** congregation: I.E: such a country shall be considered a scam **"(LEVITICUS 20 : 12 – 13, and Romans 1 : 26 – 28) !"**

SIMPLICE-kameni and alike people must be imprisoned.

HJACKING properties and down-casting businesses of elite-intellectualist from abroad like myself and others I may not even know about is what make them have a life luxurious around C.P.D.M and SED-yves-landry-galax-etoga-idiot; so called secret-services.

" THERE is also another "negger" working on behalf of simplice-kameni as LEAD of the so-called-cocaine-reseller wood-factory S2T-BED, called IDIOT-repeating-christian-signs; that behave like so-called "TONTON-makout' in HAITI-movies; (<https://wwwurl>) YOU see this kind of people that kills under behalf of a politician like BIYA; AND that you cannot even prosecute because there is no whereabouts of his origins or identities here in Cameroon-official-Communaute-URBAINE-de-YAOUNDE. "

" !! ALSO this biya-cpdm-gang against a proper african descendant on AFRIKA-soil Has a motto: ABSURDITY !!! "

FACTS:

1. kill where life is supposed to be saved;
Example: USE your own blood-giver to hijack your life and properties [REFERENCE.]

HOSPITAL is used to destroy lives.

2. destroy where it is supposed to be killed;

POLICE and ARMY kill people that go to them for seeking help after being robbed or whatsoever here in AFRIKA;

so called **UNITED-nations** (<https://www.un.org>) are only a replacement for colonies by white-supremacists.

- IT seems it is cameroon-cpdm-people who are UNITED nations workers here in CMR; HERE.

4.4 JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

1. [~~Dr. PAUL Siméon nomo, from MONATÉLÉ came to my private house in YDE-AAHALA, to arrest illegally without any notification or whatsoever, using a firefighter truck and 3 firefighter to molest myself in front of several neighbors so to discredit my life as a peaceful citizen of Cameroon.]
HE seems this criminal assassin from BIYA private places is now living in Maryland, USA; since I went back to Canada to resign from CANADIAN-shit citizenship.
Another cousin of mine so called "[Rodrigue Alain Sienchie]", told me that 1 day armed soldiers with uniforms came to arrest him in the house of his parents, sent by "[Dorothée SHANDA-NDJATIE OWONA]"; THEN went to sodomized him at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL.
"SO I SUSPECT this criminal LAURENT TCHANDEU-DJATIE DOROTHÉE OWONA to have sent to my private house in Yaounde in 2017 this 'so called baptist church pastor Dr. SIMEON NOMO, PSY.D.'."~~
2. "Eyoum Christian" idiot's immunity of justice because he is a psychiatrist Must be investigated !
3. 'S2TBED', finally repairs our main common road: They destroyed a previous road with LATERITE so much that IT must be fixed with concrete !
4. 'S2TBED', biya's illegal industrial forestry enterprise society, an illegal neighbor of "Immeuble YERITH" of mine, IS constantly disrupting electrical energy current supply.
5. ALL my real estate in Douala (3 3-bedrooms apartments) need to be released by a genitor of mine THAT is not anymore wanted in my life because of all atrocities SHE CONSTANTLY commits with SHANDA GREGROIRE OWONA Wolfgang TCHAMOU angela ndjatie. !!!
SISTER'S of Rose Sangnou my genitor, Dorothée Shanda Ndjatie, IS CONSTANTLY harassing her to take me to any psychiatric institute by force, Even though there is already a criminal investigation against her and Rose Sangnou at DLA-ndokoti justice palace; DOROTHÉE is a criminal PERSON !
6. 'MADO's brother CAPTAIN pierre marcellin emana nkoa' must reimburse back my 210 000 FRANCS since SEMIL (Sécurité Militaire) told me in 2016 THAT THEY CANNOT convoke them SINCE receipts were signed by his cousin "JEAN-DE-DIEU onana".
"MY NEIGHBOR CARINE LELE NJOUGEPE TCHANA", seems to be here because of them, so to deteriorate the quality of life of legal people living here, and promote their own-beings through propaganda LIKE 'it seems THE colonel living THERE above of the hill IS the one that FIXED the road leading to your compound !
7. JUSTICE FOR BREAKING AND torturing myself (Xavier noumbissi Noundou [DR-ING. PR. PROF.]) in front of at least 17 people in front of my inherited personal domicile in Douala-Béedi-Cite-des-Palmiers MUST be finalized before Cameroon election 2025.
8. 'JUSTICE president and certain types of judges must be apolitical: I.e.: THEY CANNOT BELONG TO A POLITICAL PARTY !
9. MARTINEZ ZOGO assassin AMOUGOU BELINGA justice criminal court must be finished before Cameroon election 2025.
10. PEOPLE responsible for the drama of Edea Railway Failure in .. MUST be judged in a civil criminal court before Cameroon election 2025.
11. MILITARY SOLDIERS that killed about "7 women and their teddies in north Cameroon must be judged."
12. "EDGARD ALAIN MEBE NGO'O" criminal procedure in military justice courts must be achieved before Cameroon election 2025.
13. Military Soldier must have their own facilities and amenities in cities, and not mixed intermingle anymore with civilians, AS THIS IS CURRENTLY THE CASE when they DON'T wear military attire uniform !
In fact, MILITARY SOLDIERS or Alike don't have a same behavior justice as civilians; Not talking about habits and gesture.
14. Bepanda drama because of 'general MPAY' must be re-recovered in a justice palace court of civilians and / or military justice !

5.5 ACADEMY and Technology Research Institutions

1. Promote creation of research centers for solving problems located specifically in central west Africa:
 1. Another source of revenue for CMR
 2. Improving life conditions for CMR and neighboring friend countries.
2. Enable a financing WITH non reimbursement option for doctors in science and / or engineering.

6.6 Employments and JOBS creation for adult people

1. THERE must be a minimum amount of jobs offer for each society that was funded by the government for researching and improving life quality in CMR and neighboring countries.
2. *WOMEN that are selling goods outside of their home like "CAROLE mangue" (la fille de "MA-bernadette" au secrétariat-d'état-yves-idiot.) shalln't be part of SED or any governmental secret or not agencies !!!*
THIS culprit shall also try to not resell goods that were illegally imported into CMR.
3. ALL PEOPLE that were trained by the BIYA-regime as illegal para-military personal, MUST go into peace-keeper corps organization of the UNITED NATIONS or somewhere else so to keep cities and villages free of fire and all other destructive people.

FOR instance people like "PASCAL dayang", working at "S2TBED" of the culprit franck-biya has insinuated to myself that HE will disrupt any business activities that I-doctor-of-engineering Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU will perform in my compound !!!

["S2TBED"- "PASCAL dayang mercenary SED soldier" as threat in CMR !!!]

4. Transform all wood factories within city of YAOUNDE in computer desktop and / or laptop assembly production units

7.7 JUSTICE and DIVINITIES

1. *Destruction of all secret services units in Cameroon !!*
 1. "OUATARA people shall not anymore be opponent to christian people here in Cameroon as it is the case with Shanda-TONME jean claude" presently.
 2. People like SHANDA OWONA harass other people because they feel as safest as possible because of some kind of impunity based on their appurtenance to DGRE special unit forces ("JEAN CLAUDE shanda tonme and spouse" weren't for instance infringed in DLA-NDOKOTI palace for breaking into my compound, closed at night, with around 9 burglars; So called Technicians of "PSY-laquintinie"; around 23 : 30 at night while I was sleeping IN february 2021 in DOUALA).
 3. Politicians shall be reduced to be people applying criminal and civil laws instead of people trying to make their own ideas come through via ENTERING private life of people like "Shanda TONME jean claude" has done in the past 30 alike years with my personal family and life ('Family NOUNDOU michel', and 'Family JEAN NGONGANG') !
 4. 'SEMIL' and special alike units of Cameroonian army shall be dismantled because of reported proved or not really ATROCITY facts.
 5. 'SEMIL', 'DGRE', 'SED', etc.; all former people wearing weapons shall be displaced into military caserns so to avoid mixing MILITARY alike people with civilians !
 6. IMPUNITY of all people wearing weapon must cease with tribunal applications of criminal laws.
2. *Create an electoral public and common website for all information, and / or official application documents for all elections in Cameroon !!*
3. *Create a website for publication of all laws in Cameroon; including presidential decrees, acts, and / or acts, and so on ...!*
4. *Reforming judicial system with computer software digitization so to PROMOTE equity and justice by laws !*
5. *EACH CITIZEN or person living in Cameroon SHALL officially declare its lifestyle philosophy and / or religion at a 'Chefferie De Block' when moving inside that area of the city !*
 - a. This enables to solve issues based on this declaration in a fairly manner; according to a new reformed judicial criminal law system !
6. *PROHIBIT any type of religious or associations that don't have well openly presented and written codes of laws, Abiding to CAMEROON criminal laws !*

8.8 TRANSPORTATION and CITIES transportation

1. *Reduce airplane travel costs between cities in Cameroon.*
INSTANCES:
 - a. {DLA → YDE} with one way at 12 000 FRANCS.
 - b. {YDE → BAFOUSSAM} with one way at 18 000 FRANCS.
 - c. Etc..

9.9 Technology And Development

1. *Schooling shall be created and managed to be in harmony with Religious, and / or Philosophy lifestyle of parents that intend to have children in a school; BOTH primary and secondary.*
UNIVERSITIES could mix students of all horizons: so the student and leaders of next Coming Cameroon could learn how to live harmoniously.
2. *State schools for civil servants shall be banned in favor of UNIVERSITY education and of an additional training on the job when hired !*
3. *Universities shall be autonomous and not depend anymore of the PRESIDENCY OF THE REPUBLIC*
4. *Create an industry for solar electrical energy with cars and buses as consumers in a lapse of time of 12 years starting 2026.*
5. *Assemble DIGITAL computers in Cameroon in less than 12 years of presidency.*

10.10 MARRIAGE and INTER-PERSONAL sexual corporal Relationship

1. *PROHIBIT sexual actions IN OUTDOOR by laws.*
2. *REMOVE TRADITIONAL SYSTEM of justice because of its unfairness; Based on WOMAN precedence in power:*
 - a. *SINCE Christians don't need to marry to a woman or any gender, as described in 1 CORINTHIANS 7 : 38 – 39 !*
 - b. *SINCE people could stay without marriage, In Christianity, marriage is THE EXCEPTION, But not a sin;*
 - c. *Any person that is not married and that is a born-again Christian cannot be managed by a married person ! THIS is because A MARRIED person couldn't qualify to understand a life at a certain level as He is living constantly with another gender !*
 - d. *People that have marriage in traditional system normally cannot undergo a civil marriage in a christian church (I.E: TRADITIONAL system allows for Impudicity, Which is prohibited in Christianity !).*
 - e. *Born-Again Christians don't marry at all in any type of marriage !*
 - f. *"SHANDA-TONME jean claude's first and last son": Late (justice of attorney) "Me. Shanda Sanou Cabral Patrice" was apparently killed brutally since his body was missing from people assisting SHANDA's family for obituaries.*
 - g. *"HIS (jean-claude shanda-tonme) OBITUARIES in next coming years must not be public since He hasn't been a good citizen for at least hundreds of young cameroonian" that I have hear about for the last 12 years since I started by immigration process back to my homeland country Cameroon of C.P.D.M-R.D.P.C !*
3. *Automatic Splitting OF INHERITANCE after parental death between children:* Because there are a lot of troubles to leave this task to a family with not enough money for paper and bureaucracy work at notary justice palaces !
4. *LEGALIZE homosexual UNION.*
 - a. *People in this union cannot have children adopted from another non-homosexual union at ALL; AND VICE-VERSA for couple married in non-homosexual life style !*

11.11 MUNICIPALITY Reform (AND WASTE and DISPOSAL of garbage)

1. *chefferie de block: This administrative territorial unit is based on traditional tribal lineage ! THIS SHALL BE ENDED AS EACH CITIZEN is subject to the same civil law:*
 1. *currently, a 'chefferie de block' is based on common and traditional law. Since common law has precedence over tribal traditional law, A CITIZEN living must be subject only to COMMON CIVIL LAW where he is living, OR NOT.*
2. *There shall be created AN INDUSTRY for recycling and displacement of waste-garbage USING ecologic burning container:* Each "chefferie de block" shall have its own burning destroying waste-garbage ecologic container.
3. *There shall be at least 1 municipal playing and recreational area of at least 400 m² in each city quarter ("quartier").*
4. *There shall be at least 1 municipal library in each city quarter ("quartier").*

- UNITED STATES OF AMERICA (U.S.A)

- 1.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), CONCORD, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (JANUARY 2008)
- 2.) SRI International, MENLO COLLEGE, MENLO PARK, ATHERTON, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (May 2011)

- CANADA

- 3.) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ON, canada 2009 – 2015
- 4.) MITACS ONTARIO, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, CANADA (October 2012)
- 5.) IBM CASCON 2010 (IBM CENTRE FOR ADVANCED STUDIES CONFERENCE), Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham, Conference Centre, Markham, ON, CANADA (November 2010)
 I attended this conference to present "my doctoral thesis in a simple manner that could be defended in front of several researchers worldwide" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); With different backgrounds; As well as practitioners from IBM toronto software laboratory in MARKHAM (<https://www.ibm.com/ca-en>) .
- 6.) PLDI conference (Programming Languages Design And Implementation), Toronto, ON, CANADA (November 2009)
- 7.) Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) PREPARATION COURSE, CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY, MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (June 2007)
- 8.) Graduate English Training Course, UNIVERSITÉ DU QUÉBEC à MONTRAL (UQAM), MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (AUGUST 2009)

- GERMANY

- 9.) UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY 2001 – 2007
- 10.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY 2007 – 2009
- 11.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), HEIDELBERG, BADEN-WÜRTTEMBERG, GERMANY 2007 – 2009

This section reports and summarizes our current and actualized knowledge on the subject of software licensing.

20.20 SOFTWARE LICENSes

- o "Summary of MOSTLY used software-licenses":

[Software ~~Hardware~~ Certification authorities; "O.H.A.D.A"; CENELEC; CE; ISO; "A.R.I.N.C"]

Table 1: Software LICENSes summary table.

SOFTWARE license type	Peculiarities	Uses	URL for legal writing specification
1. "CSCS : Close Source Code Software"	Software / Programs AUTHOR exclusive copyright & ownership	YOU use only a binary.	Each retailer provides this on a case by case request.
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			

- CSCS : Close Source Code Software (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- Open source code software (OSS (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)) :

- OTHER forms of free software license (FOSS (<https://www.wikipedia.org>))

- APACHE-BSD license (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- APACHE
- ["BSD"]

- GNU licenses : (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- GPL
ANY software that uses this piece of whole source code and / or binaries have to also be licensed GPL.

- "Lesser GPL - LGPL" ✓
Program binaries could be used in a commercial project without any request and / or payments to the owner of the source code. Modifications of the source code follows certain rules specified as follows :
 - 1.) Mention of the authors have to be explicitly written in headers of code sources as directed by rules explicitly sampled at following URL : (<https://>).
 - 2.) YOUR own using software source code must also abide to the LGPL GNU software license according to what is written at following URL : (<https://>).

- BERKELEY-style license (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- BSD

- MIT-license; "also called AS-IS-no-warranty-AT-ALL" (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- MIT ✓
THIS kind of Open-Source Software (OSS) programs is provided in a state that no reclamation could be done because it could be very tedious to determine liabilities between parties such as a provider, and a customer and / or client.

The so-called MIT License are part of the AS-IS no-warranty code; ALSO all GPL typed licenses in general.

Programs using AS-IS no-Warranty code software licenses generally stipulates either following text, OR similar surrounding text around following :

- o ["The program is provided AS IS with NO WARRANTY OF ANY KIND, INCLUDING THE WARRANTY OF DESIGN, MERCHANTABILITY AND FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE."]

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

21.21 Documents for certification for "YERITH R&D" software – hardware PRODUCTS engineered in AFRICA–main–land

Table 2: *Design Documents* for the CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool YERITH_QVGE.

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 3: *Design Documents* for the Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF].

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 4: *Design Documents* for the Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

A personal computer tablet for SIMPLIFYING runtime monitoring on–the–fly

Figure 20, Figure 21, and Figure 22 illustrates a sample product usage of the toolkit YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that permits and allows for its users following actions and tasks to be solved fluently :

1. Send tracing logging for a developer and / or engineer trough 1 of the following communication interfaces :
 - 1.) *Design Documents Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification;*
 - 2.) *USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);*
 - 3.) *Module Description (Module Functional Specification).*

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

22.22 TOOLS used for Qualification AND / OR Certification of Software-hardware PRODUCTS at "YERITH R&D"

Table 5: Tools used for Qualification and / Or Certification at YERITH R&D.

TOOL	VERSION	Uses	LOCATION
1. "BUGZILLA (https://www.bugzilla.org)"	"N.A"	Bugs and Defects registration & following-up.	
2. "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (https://www.gnupg.org)"	2.2.27-2	Digital signing check-in source code & documents.	
3. "Git (https://www.git.org)"	1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2	COMMIT, and following-up source code for certification authorities.	

Table 5 illustrates some programming and / or debugging tools I use at YERITH R&D for developing certified products with "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)", etc.; Certification organizations :

- o Bugs and Defects Management Software : "BUGZILLA (<https://www.bugzilla.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current BUGZILLA software installations" : "N.A".
 2. "Location of BUG report-free database website URL" : "www.digital.ocean.com/YERITH_QVGE_HTTPS_url (<https://www.digitalocean.com>)".
 3. "Location of BUGZILLA software installation" : "Intern to YERITH R&D".
- o Software for electronically signing (e.g.: Source code, Design Documents, etc.) : "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (<https://www.gnupg.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current GNU Privacy Guard-GPG software installations" : "2.2.27-2".
- o SCM (Source code Management) software : Version Control Management Software : "Git (<https://www.git.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current Git software installations" : "1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2".

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

23.23 Yerith_QVGE Legal Software and/or Hardware CERTIFICATION Artifacts

- o "Yerith_QVGE Legal Software CERTIFICATION Artifacts":

- YERITH_QVGE DESIGN AND TESTING SYSTEM[13.13] : A product for qualification; CE.

23.23.1 "CERTIFICATION Tools used at YERITH R&D"

[Certification TOOLS.]

23.23.2 "PRODUCTS for Engineering And/ OR Finance Engineered Computing"

- 1.) YERITH_QVGE software design CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“June 2022” – Currently]

Figure 1: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

- 2.) YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET ; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“Nov. 2024” – Currently]

Figure 2: A screenshot of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL error event log running on YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.

Figure 3: A sample YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET in action.

THIS hardware computing device, WITH software that uses "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could be used for "on-the-fly" runtime verification monitoring & Recovering manifold :

- One connects YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET to either an Ethernet network connection, or serial interface communication port RS-232, and / or Universal Serial BUS-USB interface port ;

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (a screenshot is found in Figure 2) is started on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET", and connects to specified processes, on the attached connected other computing device (E.g.: in Fig. 3, a control console for "Siemens-LINAC"); In a configuration panel. THE open source version of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a bit different of the non-free upgraded version installed on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET".

This section reports and summarizes all efforts needed as far AS I could learn and experienced as seasoned software developer at "IBM-toronto-software-laboratory"; And at "Siemens-medical-solutions".

24.24 Years of experience as Software Developer for Legally APPROVED products

o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact":

■ **YERITH_QVGE LEGAL documents for Qualified Products from AFRICA—main—land.**

■ [SOFTWARE licensing.]

■ "Communauté Économique et MONÉTAIRE de l'Afrique Centrale – (C.E.M.A.C)" (<https://www.cemac.int>) : THIS central Africa certification applies for Accounting and Finance.

I.) "O.H.A.D.A (<https://www.cemac.int>)" ; for "**FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE**"

■ **TüV-Nord (<https://www.tuv-nord.com>)** in North-West GERMANY : This german authority in Science and Engineering reflects better our initial commitment as a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?], even before a [MASTER-OF-SCIENCE] degree was created at the UNIVERSITY-racist of Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>).

A.) "CE - EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en)" ; "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)" ; "FDA - FEDERAL DRUG ADMINISTRATION (U.S.A) (<https://www.fda.gov>)" for "**MEDICAL SOFTWARE**"

1. **Bugs and Defects** are to be managed by a software such as "IBM-CharmNT (<https://www.ibm.com/us>)" ;
2. **Design Documents** are to be updated annually at maximum time based on regulatory deadlines of **AUTHORITIES That Delivers Certificates** ; **I think at least ONCE-ANNUALLY**;
3. **Design Documents** are electronically signed by an author and reviewers;
4. **Design Documents** are saved in an ERP software such as "SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)", etc.;
5. **Design Documents** have a table to indicate changes within the document for each modification of it;
6. **Design Documents** USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);
7. **Design Documents** Module Description (Module Functional Specification) with Diagrams; E.g.: "Finite State Machine Diagrams", etc.;
8. **Design Documents** Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification; Runtime Memory Error Detection TOOLS.
9. **Source code** is to be stored in a control version management system such as "Rational-ClearCase", etc.;
10. **Source code** changes are to be reviewed and electronically signed using a key-card like the ones used by ["SIEMENS-healthineers-OCS"];

B.) **CENELEC (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>)** for "**RAILWAY**"

A sample railway software related product regulation is : "CENELEC EN50128" (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>).

C.) **A.R.I.N.C (<https://www.aviation-ia.sae-itc.com>)** for "**AVIONICS SOFTWARE**"

Sample A.R.I.N.C specifications : "RTCA D0178-B"; "RTCA D0178-C".

- Static Code Analysis Verification conforming to "MISRA-C" (<https://www.misra.org>) ;

["MISRA-C"]

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

25.25 Years of PRE-Doctoral & years of Doctoral Research at University-racist OF waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA

ML; C++; Java; OSI; Eclipse; Intel-Pin; Open-MP Haskell, GWT, Python, IBM, Quercus, Bash-scripting	<i>Program Analysis (Static, Dynamic).</i> a-la-KILDALL-Gary;LFDS-Reps; datalog; Soot; LLVM	Courses taught: 1. Software Testing, Quality Assurance & Maintenance 2. Programming for Performance 3. Tools & Methods for Software Engineering 4. Foundations of Software Engineering 5. C++ Programming Laboratory 6. Compilers 7. Computer Networks
<i>(ADVANCED) Compiler Technology</i> Yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang; Alias Analysis, Comp. Opt.	<i>Program Verification (Isa.-HOL, etc.); Model Checking</i> SDMM; CAV - Computer-Aided Verification; NuSMV; Alloy	
Programing Languages OOP; Functional	Software; Programming; Testing Alg.; Rel. Eng.; Security; Par.-Comp.	} Foundations of My Doctoral Ph.D. / Post-Doctoral Works in Computer Science (Software Engineering)
	Formal Methods; Kripke Structures Automata theory (NFA, DFA, etc.)	

- o [PublicaTIONS.]
- o "Software LICENSING".
- o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact".
- o Contacts with NORTH-AMERICAN scientists
- o Contacts with other Scientists
- o Issues & MISUNDERSTANDINGS at the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada
- o TIME at the University-racist-of-BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, Germany:
 1. "2 years" STudent Software Developer PART-TIME job – Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Germany.
 2. "2 years" WERKSTUDENT at ZMML-university-sexist-racist of bremen, BREMEN, GERMANY.: February 2003 – February 2005.
 3. "4.5 years PRE-time" in GERMAN-racist program : "'DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]'".
- o Doctoral years of research at the university-racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA-idiot:
 1. "2 years PRE-time" at SIEMENS-idiot medical solutions.: November 2007 – JULY 2009.
 2. "Summary of teaching training certificates
 3. PAPER conference peer reviewed : OOPSLA 2010.
 4. GIVEN PREsentation : IBM CDp Cascon 2010.
 5. Visited courses.
 6. Independent assisted research summary as a "Master of Science (M.Sc.)"
 7. VISITed SUMMER-school /workshops / conferences summary
["1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"-2011] | [PLDI 2009] | [IBM CDp Cascon 2010]
 8. PSYCHOLOGICAL-Care with PRACTICE of SWIMMING at THE university-racist of waterloo every other day during almost 4 years – "Degree-Swimmer-5 / degree-MASTER-Swimmer-6" successfully attended.
 9. "Year 1" : 09/2009 – 08/2010;
 10. "Year 2" : 09/2010 – 12/2011 – [with PhD Comprehensive Examination.];
 11. Doctoral THESIS Presentation / PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011"

o QUALification as a "Professional Engineer in Ontario, CANADA":

THE requirements to qualify myself as Professional Engineer in ONTARIO are all met after 1 year supervision under PATRICK LAM "(2011)"; because I have already 48 months of professional engineering work experience before entering the professional academic doctor of engineering program in ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER Engineering at university-racist-white of waterloo.

"AS a "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" graduate [abbreviated "Dr./PhD" in French; In french, "Dr./PhD" only nowadays means doctor in engineering; and no fellowship at all; I AM A FRANCOPHONE.]; THERE shouldn't be any need to again acquired a professional designation "Professional Engineer", since "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" is already an Engineering titled degree. So as a francophone from dark-afrika-heimat, I am not interested anymore in any Engineering, or whatsoever designated vocational position in whiteist-world !"

"ALSO as a born-again christian, I CANNOT BE member-ed in any fellowship of iron-rings, female-peggist; etc. ."

"JON eyolfson for instance has a "Bachelor-of-Engineering"; so he doesn't need to apply for a "Professional Engineer"; BUT [Wenzhu-man has a "Master of Applied Science (MAsc)"]; AND no "Engineering titled degree from CANADA and /or USA"; SO for her needs she must apply for P.Eng.; so to get government oriented positions !"

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

26.26 Years of POST-doctoral Research; a Summary Report – 2nd page

- o *POst-Doctoral (Ph.D.; Prof.) years of research at the university–racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA–idiot:*
 1. "Year 1": 01/2012 – 08/2012 – [*PROfessional Internship at IBM Toronto–idiot Software Lab..*]
 2. "Year 2": 09/2012 – 08/2013
 3. "Year 3": 09/2013 – 08/2014
 4. "Year 4": 09/2014 – 04/2015
 5. STUDENT advising summary
 6. TEACHing assistantship summary
 7. "Summary of teaching training certificates"
 8. *Independent & Collegiate Research Summary as "D.ENG. [DR.–ING. in 'French language'] (PH.D.)"*
 9. Visited courses as post–doctoral (POST-DOCTORAL STUDIES) fellow.
 10. VISited ONLINE courses /workshops / conferences summary
[Software-Security–online–"stanford.edu" 2013] | [MITACS ONTARIO 2012] | [ICse 2012]
 11. RESEARCH outcome hindrance
 12. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism
 13. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism-continUED
 14. GIVEN–co–taught courses at the University–racist of Waterloo in ONTARIO, Canada
 15. ACADEMIC HELP from other people aside from DEAR-idiot PATRICK-lam
 16. *!!! PhD Research Seminar TALK. as an ECE graduate talk. !!!*
 17. *!!! PhD Dissertation Defense at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015" !!!*
 18. *IAI–cameroon–bande–d'idiots au service d'1 B.E.P.C–chantoux*
- o [*TRAINING on the job of young engineers*]:
 - Runtime monitoring for Web Apps
 - API usage rule checking for 'C' programs (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
- o *STARTUP entrepreneurship research & development project YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM:*

After I left the university–racist–of–waterloo in ontario, IN MARCH 2015; I went to live in Cameroon–yaounde for almost 2 years, working on a free and open source software for Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP).

POST-Doctoral Research at YERITH R&D since MARCH 2015:

 - I) *Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise;*
 - II) *YERITH_QVGE legal artifacts for QUALIFICATION certified products Engineered in AFRICA;*
 - III) *A web-site Domain-Specific Language (DSL) Processor for generation of HTML5, PHP, CSS, etc. combined web–applications named YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (Accompanied with a WYSIWYG-Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL !)*
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9>
 - IV) *A realtime component (for operating system DEBIAN LINUX) is in preparation for trading stock exchange erp system "YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME": YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM;*
 - V) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification "state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)" C++ Library :*
 https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf [*I*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 - VI) *A State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) translator–compiler :*
[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567\)](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567) [*1*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
 - VII) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification runtime container for "SDMM" :*
 [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481\)](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) [*1*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - VIII) *Simple to use and pragmatic Enterprise–Resource–Planing (ERP) software :*
 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) [*?*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 (Cyber-Security & Web Deployment Development)

27.27 WEB PAGES HTML and others Generation with YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0

27.27.1 Motivation

Table 6: A SOFTWARE architecture overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (["An SDMM usage scenario by IBM-websphere"].)

Figure 4: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 generates legacy web files from Qt 5 interface files (".ui" files).

Figure 5: A Stack Stapled Architecture Overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0.

YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 is a novel project that constitutes the base for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM ([git https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem](https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem)) that endeavors to create web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations that use YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM without much additional programming of web interfaces and / or interactions; AT such, web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations will emerge as easy as pressing a button.

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 is a Domain Specific Language to [describe WEB SITES programmatically]; SUCH as a C++ program imperatively, AND well structured; So to automatically generate STATIC DYNAMIC WEB SITES BASED ON HTML (HYPERTEXT MARKUP LANGUAGE) AND CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) language constructs : [WWW - World Wide Web \(WWW\) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)".

Numerous companies in Cameroon might evaluate this new research software system product to simplify and speed up their software development process :

1. "Dr.-Ing. PAUL dayang (2013, University of Bremen)"; currently employed at the University of Ngaoundere in Far North of Cameroon.
 - This researcher and lecturer, employed by the University of Ngaoundere, has never replied to my long time email as an alumni of the prestigious University of Bremen in Germany where I graduated with a "Diplom-Informatiker degree 2 years before him !"
 - I could see he started a web graphical system (also with "ANDROID-google platform" (<https://>)) html-based to promote online afore-provisional shopping of food provisions in Africa for his dissertation as a "Doctor of Engineering". I was sad not to see this project emerge as a commercial start-up here in Cameroon where there is only "www.cm.coinafrique.com" (<https://www.cm.coinafrique.com>) that I deem as a serious competitor in this era of work.
 - I believe the programming abstraction I will provide for "DAYANG and RÖDIGER (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/~roediger>) work" would help them both in "Ngaoundere" and in "Bremen" to promote Free and Open Source web shopping for Africa where even a clean market is not existing in Main city Yaounde !
 - AT the university of bremen-white-racist, I Visited a course titled "E-business technologies 2"; I don't remember the name of the professor but I DID SO while I WAS in my 3rd year as part of so called "ANGEWANDTE INFORMATIK" ("Applied Computer Science"). IN graduate level course "E-business technologies 2", I learned about n-tiers web architectures, SOAP-Service Oriented Architecture Protocol, etc.

ALSO, in my 2nd year, there was a small "practicum" where I learned on PHP, and MariaDB; "ERIC-cuon-pd STREIBL" was the organizer.

2. "DUT-Diplôme Universitaire de Technologie" CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong" (Start-Up)

CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong is a seasoned software developer that creates large to medium-sized websites; AND Google-android mobile applications for his clients around world.

"CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong, that I schooled with in Douala secondary school — "ALFRED SAKER HIGH SCHOOL" — would also not be against such a tool-framework that could reduce his development time and effort, since BLACK-USA entrepreneurs cannot afford tremendous amount of money for tools sold by MICROSOFT CORP., FACEBOOK INC., etc. ! " (<https://www.creezycreates.com>)

3. "Dr. (B.Sc.) Claudel Noumbissi" (Start-Up)
4. "Ing. (B.Sc.) Arthur Zang" (Start-Up)
5. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Ibrahim Nguena Moukouop" (Start-Up)
6. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Thomas Djotio Ndié" (Start-Up)
7. "Institut Universitaire de la Cote", Douala (Start-Up)
8. "Santa Lucia – AHALA", Yaounde (Currently using Odoo ERP web & thick-client) !
9. "DR. (M.Sc.) Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni" (Start-Up)

Fabrice WILFRIED siemeni could generate sample website pages with no programming knowledge at all.

10. etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 – CONTINUED –

Table 7: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL keywords and meaning (An excerpt).

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 keyword	(level) Nested in keyword	Programming related meaning
1. yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN		Contains web site all pages description
2. web_html_page_menu_bar_headers	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Contains web site each page menubar pages names
3. web_html_page	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	A HTML page description
4. yri_html_page_title	(3) web_html_page	A HTML page title
5. yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar	(3) web_html_page	Inputs a menubar onto this HTML page
6. yri_html_page_text_SECTION	(3) web_html_page	Describes a text section on a HTML page
7. VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH	(6) yri_html_page_text_SECTION	Defines text paragraph within a HTML page
8. text_yri_font_size	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a font size
9. text_yri_width_box	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a width for a text paragraph

Figure 6: Webbrowser-based software architecture : at least 4 layers logical software architecture (Image modified from online pdf paper "FlashCache: A NAND Flash Memory File Cache for Low Power Web Servers" [<https://doi.org/10.1145/1176760.1176774>] by Trevor et al.). YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runtime monitors communication layers.

27.27.2 RELATED WORK at YERITH R&D; Software System Architecture of ERP Systems

- "Our paper not for publication in a conference paper, [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[?\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); reveals common web system architecture patterns and structure, INCLUDING ([CYBER-SECURITY\[34\]](#)) software system security vulnerability analysis; As observed these last 10 years at least from "January 14, 2026".
- ["WE have visited, in year 2013, an online software security vulnerability detection and protection course with the STANFORD-university-racist while attending our degree [DOCTORAL PH.D.-program at the University of Waterloo;] THIS required acquired knowledge helps us creating safe and secure software systems by Construction."]
- "WE previously, in our "3rd semester", at the University-racist of Bremen, Bremen, GERmany-idiot; Have visited a course for undergraduates named "Information Security 1" given by "TZI.DE (Technology Center for Computer Science) (<https://www.tzi.de/en>)" founding member "Prof. Dr-Ing. Carsten-cuon-obèse Bormann-nazi" (<https://user.informatik.uni-bremen.de/cabo>)."
- ★ ★ "I could also achieved a running taint analysis ([git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)) for the Quercus PHP JAVA web application server during my post-doctoral studies & work at the university-racist of waterloo in ontarian Canada-idiot. IT was a graduate course taught by "Frank-idiot-nazi TIP-gay-cuon". "] ★ ★

27.27.3 WHAT YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 Would Service & Provide

- "Qt 5 software development platform" enables auto-deployment for Android-google platform." (<https://>)
YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem>) will reuse this functionality to generate legacy web source code files (HTML5, PHP, CSS, Javascript (GWT (Google Web Toolkit))); VIA a translation program-technology from "Qt 5-ui (user-interface)" files onto YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 input file coin as DSL-specific YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 files ("spec_html"); Figure 4.;
- We at YERITH R&D could then use any "Qt 5-Designer tool as a WYSIWYG Tool for generating Web-HTML-PHP pages : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" !
- "We plan at mid-term to be able to generate "Software architecture proof testing-programs", both for GUI-interfaces (thick-client), and Web-interfaces (thin-client); automatically just by specifying certain behavioral interactions using state diagram mealy machines ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).";
- "The so-called "Software architecture proof testing-programs" will have certain warranties about [cyber-security], about [cyber-safety], [runtime-memory usage] and [user-defined usage rules]."

27.27.4 Implementation Technologies

I use "flex and bison compiler / translator generation technology" for creating YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL. I plan to automatically generate code for enabling runtime monitoring of the generated web sites. A first version of this FOSS (Free And Open Source Software) is available at URL: [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9) .

27.27.5 YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL Keyword Table

Table 7 depicts and explains commands and directives for creating web-based HTML pages sites.

We plan also the generation of web sites based on an "n-tiers architecture pattern", illustrated for instance in Figure 6; that demonstrated solid resistance in practice for more than 10 years now as demonstrated by applications server existence and usage such as :

1. Apache tomcat application server
2. Glassfish application server: mainly used in combination with JAVA OSI component-based software development architecture.
3. Quercus PHP server interpreter application server
4. IBM websphere

All this work has to solve the issue of generating certain portion of web sites for customers and users of ["YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM"\[?\]](#) Enterprise Resource Planing software in a time period in-between of 3 years from this year 2024 !

"ALL THIS UNDER THE PROTECTION OF OUR LORD AND SAVIOR JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN."

28.28 Securing Websites

Figure 7: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine file.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_TaintAnalysis
2. {
3.   START_STATE(T0):NOT_IN_BEFORE(in,yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers_methods)
4.   ->[not_in_sql_event_log('SELECT.i0#sanitize',STATE(T0))]/'INSERT.i0#in'->
5.     FINAL_STATE(TF):IN_POST(i0,yri_tainted_analysis.tainted_values).
6. }

```

Figure 8: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine.

$\underline{Q_0} := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(op, yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers) ; \quad \overline{Q_F} := \text{IN_POST}(i0, yri_tainted_analysis.tainted).$

28.28.1 Motivation

Numerous security vulnerabilities towards and against web applications exist :

- **“SQL injection“** : “A user tries to make a software execute a SQL query on a software-connected database by passing for instance; **THROUGH user credential input SQL-code to destroy part or all your database.**

user-name: 'Insert into users ('user_name', 'user_password') values ('drop table users', 'drop database');

- **“Format Strings“** : A software has part of it receiving directly input from an outside-world interface and using it without checking it is proper formed. Any malformed input can cause a mal-interpretation of data & could then caused for instance; **A CRASH of the software under analysis !**

int variable_x = 0; scanf(%, variable_x); // Wrong format is expected by scanf !.

// scanf currently expects a string instead of an integer.

- **“Cross-site scripting attacks“**; **“Buffer-overflow“**; **“Man-in-the-Middle“**; etc.
- **ALL cyber-security types** We previously wrote about in this listing items could be detected by removing all tainted values of an application; I.E.; provide a validation function and / or method, for each tainted value.

THIS is best done during testing of the software product before delivery of an end-product to clients and / or customers.

A recovery from a fail state accepting error program location can be done by adding a generic recovery validating function and / or method that Could identify; and provide; best sanitizing / validating method for each tainted input.

SINCE YERITH_QVGE provide only forbidden trace specification, a recovery and detection is generally only possible after at least 1 violation of the SDMM specification property automaton has been achieved !

A usage scenario with in future coming dedicated PC-Tablet computer YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; could be found in Figure 1.

Our approach to add more security & safety to open-source webshops generated by our technology YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL is manifold :

- 1.) **USE of runtime verification & monitoring platform YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) :
 - **USE of standard security vulnerability breaches detection mechanisms** as for Instance illustrated for Taint Analysis in this Subsection 28.28.3 !
 - **USE of developer-otherly specified security vulnerabilities patterns** expressed as SDMM, & similarly described as for instance in Figure 8 !

28.28.2 Event Race Parallel-Concurrent Processes

- 1.)

28.28.3 Dynamic Taint Analysis for Web Security

- 1.) *IN a previous work at the university–racist of waterloo, in Canadian–whitte ontario [3], we've implemented in web–server Quercus; A dynamic taint analysis using JAVA as programming language.*

We plan to re–use Quercus as web–application server for generated webshops from YERITH–WEB–DESIGN–TOOL.

- 2.) *Currently, we have created YRI–DB–RUNTIME–VERIF, 1 runtime monitoring container generator that enables creation of taint analysis engine with no coding for a developer; IT only requires to deliver a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) specification expressed using a textual description DSL–language called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [1c] : Figure 7;*

This textual description (Domain-Specific Language) offers also, when a state diagram mealy machine has more than 2 states, a reference communicating processes parallel specification for the problem under analysis since processes are synchronized on each event after a 1st event because each state of the state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) represents a potential other parallel running process state; Illustration follows for instance in Figure 8.

28.28.4 Warranties on Web Pages–Security

- 1.) *[Warranties on Cyber–Safety].*

29.29 WEB-QT Assembly : A comparison with [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)

- WebAssembly-technology of QT-trolltech uses a platform independent binary format (called emscripten) to deliver website functionality for QT-application out-of-the-box;

Technology emscripten is not open-sourced and it is not as simple as "use of [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)".

30.30 WYSIWYG-Tool for generating websites

Figure 9: YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL : A SCREENSHOT of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 generator within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.

Figure 9 illustrates a design engineering modeling window frame originating from ERP-software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for automatically generating webshop for its users.

30.30.1 Motivation

Numerous users of ERP-YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum would be also interested in having a WWW-online presentation for interacting with their clients and / or customers.

In our white-black paper [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[?\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); we motivate why we prefer fat-client software-system architecture over thin-client (also called website-architecture).

However we also want to enable our users to be online on the web easily by just pressing a button since costs to develop another system might be very impressing. THAT is why YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum offers now for its users and / or developers an interface for automatically generating and deploying website-webshops solutions that reuse any information already present in the database created & running as a fat-thick-client (QT) architecture.

30.30.2 Steps & Technology

- Selecting QT-trolltech ui files to transform into web-HTML5 and / or PHP files;
- Pressing a button that generates PHP-HTML5 files via a step-by generation of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 files.

Our use of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 has advantages of preventing us of drastic changes in either HTML5 standards or platforms since YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 represents a website architecture as a high-level programming language (e.g.: C++, JAVA, etc.).

Listing 1: A sample very limited for explanation & illustration purpose YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 Source code !

```

1  yerith-web-pages-generator-MAIN YECEFOIQ-WEB-PAGES
2  {
3
4  web-html-page index
5  {
6  yri_html_page_title: 'Bienvenue au centre de formation qualifiante Yecefoiq !';
7  yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar[web-html-page-menu-bar-headers];
8  yri_html_page_MENU_BAR_link_string: 'yri_index !';
9
10 yri_html_page_text_SECTION (HTML_HEADER_H/3; 'Description du Centre de Formation')
11 {
12 VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH variable_paragraph_1
13 {text-yri-font-size = 5} :
14 {text-yri-width-box = 5cm} ==
15 "PLEASE read following list items ordered !:"
16
17 li_begin: '1st list item'
18 li: '2nd list item.'
19 li_end: 'Last list item.'
20 };
21 };
22
23 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers {
24 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers_Position = 'vertical-left';
25
26 yri_html_page_section[index,
27 programme_des_cours,
28 contenu_des_cours,
29 impressum];
30 };
31 }

```


31.31 Software Validation with YERITH_QVGE (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)

Figure 10: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart; Example created and / or inspired from QT-trolltech sample; in Documentation present; Statechart found in some place I don't remember yet..

Figure 11: A sample ping-pong parallel process depicted in Figure 10.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_PingPong
2. {
3.   START_STATE(pinger)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('ping', STATE(pinger))]/'pong' ->
5.     STATE(ponger): IN_POST_NOP
6.     ->[in_sql_event_log('pong', STATE(ponger))]/'ping' ->
7.       FINAL_STATE(pinger_two): IN_POST_NOP.
8. }

```

Software System Validation checks whether certain software system properties are **IMPLEMENTED CORRECTLY** according to its specifications.

1. **Software VALIDATION** as an automatic test case generation runtime monitoring instance from **YERITH_QVGE** !

a.) A test case is generated without checking for test data using a constraint solver engine because it can be acquired only by manual interaction with the software under analysis.

31.31.1 Cyber-Safety Warranties & Others

1.) **Warranties on Cyber-Security**.

12.12 Software Verification Engineering Modeling with SDMM

Figure 12: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE(dept_exists):NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('DELETE.dept.YRI_ASSET', STATE(dept_exists))]/'SELECT.dept'->
5.     ERROR_STATE(dept_exists):IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET,stocks.dept_name).
6. }

```

Figure 13: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A SQL-database based only in a disk-file with not much roundabout code could also be used instead of a full-featured database management system such as MariaDB (<https://www.mariadb.com>).

$Q_0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)$; $Q_1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.dept_name)$.

"SDMM state diagram formalism is more powerful and expressive than David-harel statechart formalism. I.E. As depicted in fig. 15, a drawing-design is not well capable of scaling for a software-system with for instance 9 sub-systems events and / or states."

Figure 14: A David-harel statechart modeling of a temporal property expressed as a finite state diagram machine of mealy-GEORGES in fig. 13.

Figure 15: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart.

1. Software Engineering Design & Verification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM), runtime monitoring & static code analysis :

- WE are working & researching on translating automatically viable statechart specification onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) runtime monitoring verification specifications;
- USER requirement elicitation & specification is easily transcribed into a formal SDMM automaton-formula; Even by a mathematician with not much knowledge in Computer Technical Programming; As THIS is required when developers use David-Harel Statechart visual formalism as you can observe in Figure 14 !

A temporal property specification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires use of the following mathematic elements :

- Logic formulas to describe propositional formulas as conditions to trigger software system state-transitions; AND also to describe "GUARD-condition" to be checked 'VALID' before a software-system state-transition is triggered & executed by YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, a runtime monitoring verification container.
- Variables : to describe states & state-conditions (pre- & post-conditions).
- Formulas mustn't be drawn because there exists also a textual description language coined as a Domain-Specific Language called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [1c] : Figure 12 illustrates for instance a textual description for the mealy machine state diagram drawn in Figure 13 !
- "Statecharts by David-Harel, BECAUSE it is a visual formalism; Requires knowledge of code of drawing squares & other signs and keywords." !

- Modeling a temporal property specification added with state-transitions pre- & post-conditions is very tedious and complicated to realize using David-harel Statechart.

THIS kind of modeling is impressively more easy to realize using finite automata formalisms such as depicted in Figure 13; This figure depicts a temporal software system safety property designed with Mealy-machine, "And formalized as a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d]) by myself" !

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is extremely efficient in usage and / or specification because state-conditions ("pre-condition underlined" & "post-conditions over-lined" are executed by a runtime execution "expansion algorithm" called "Method YRI_trigger_an_edge_event" that checks at no costs for users.)

- With statecharts, specification of software system with parallel subsystem doesn't scale well starting for instance with 8 subsystems, because all 8 subsystems must be drawn 1 inside others !

ON the contrary side, state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires specifying an finite state automaton with more than 2 states, and linear in space & traversal algorithm complexity; Which is done automatically for a developer by the runtime monitoring verification generator-container YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !.

- "OPEN-source version of the software system programming library QT-trolltech offers since version (at minimum number) 5.15 (around year 2020) a package called SCXML that implements David-harel statechart programming capabilities" !

13.13 Software Verification with YERITH_QVGE

A library or plugin at any layer (OR a combination mixture of layers) of a software system architecture could be verified and validated using YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF by applying a receipt: IT would be sufficient to map each system call wanted for call sequence verification and / or validation to a MySQL query: So one doesn't need to re-create new QT-DBus interfaces for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: E.g.: "SYSTEM V libc". [A sample use case for IBM-Websphere server web !]

Figure 16: Software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: it is also a runtime monitor container for software verification.

Figure 17: YRI_QVGE software stack dependencies.

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR DYNAMIC runtime analysis and monitoring of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software (Figure 17 illustrates graphically interdependency between these under described sub-projects.).

- a. **YRI_QVGE** (an extension of Qt-QVGE): A "CASE (computer-aided software engineering)", CLOSED SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (CSCS), for creating and generating MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAMS as GUI (GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE) TOOL. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
[model-based testing, DSL – domain-specific languages]

"[THE GUI TOOL YERITH_QVGE] (See Figure 23) GENERATES A FILE CONTAINING A MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAM SPECIFICATION using YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG; this file could be used as input for the compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP, so to gather a C++ package to run as runtime monitor within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. THIS TOOL COSTS 2,500 EUROS."

- b. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: A Dynamic Program Monitoring Recovering Analyzer Generator for any software emitting QtDBus messages per sockets (See subsection 13.13.3 (Runtime Verification), and / or Figure 21; and / or Figure 24).

"THIS IS at time (January 14, 2026); State-of-art technology; comparable technology are for instance RT-Tester with TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System); State Diagram formalism From "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (RT-Tester, MBT[?]). TDIOHS complies fully with all semantic elements of HAREL-statecharts !

"AND technologies "IBM Purify Plus"; "LOGSCOPE" ("Specification-Based Monitoring in C++") and "DejaVu" ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic") by [Dr. Klaus Havelund] at N.A.S.A (https://www.nasa.gov)."

- YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

- c. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP**: a compiler using flex and bison, for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF specification language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG), so to automatically generate C++ code for runtime monitors implemented in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. [04/2023 – CURRENT]
[compilers, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages]

"COMPETITORS from LOGSCOPE and DejaVu; AND RT-Tester, MBT[?]; have similar description state diagram language; but work all of them as SPECIFICATION OF WISHED PROGRAM BEHAVIOR; whereas SDMM[1d] works at SPECIFICATION OF FORBIDDEN (fail) PROGRAM BEHAVIOR."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- d. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG**: A SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE FOR STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) extended with pre-/post-conditions on STATE DIAGRAM TRANSITIONS and with a final state. (https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567) [04/2023 – CURRENT]
[statecharts, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages]

"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG complies fully to David-harel statecharts ["Statecharts: a visual formalism for complex systems" (https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf)] which is a visual formalism for states diagrams."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- e. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS**: UNIT TESTING PROJECT for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
"THIS test unit suite is there to check peculiarities of project YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF; As a Free And OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (foss), I strongly recommend using it before committing changes to the main git-branch project."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS

- f. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF / YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime [06/2022 – CURRENT]

[model-based testing, reactive system analysis, computer software program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software integration testing with SQL and GUL, runtime monitoring]

"YOU SPECIFY USING A STATE DIAGRAM AN ERRONEOUS SUT (System Under Test) TYPE STATE STYLE BEHAVIOR with YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. USING YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, YOU CHECK AT RUNTIME WHETHER SUCH AN ERRONEOUS SUT SEQUENCE BEHAVIOR OCCURS."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

13.13.1 TAXONOMY : Software Verification vs. Program Code Verification

Figure 18: "Program verification (including model checking)" is a subset (C) of "SOFTWARE VERIFICATION". (See also research goal 13.)

Figure 19: Embedded program verifier notifier within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a background process service.

Software System verification is a discipline to verify whether a software, meaning a product use at customer level and full-featured, conforms to certain software system user related usage properties.

In contrast, **program code verification** checks only program at the level of their source code or binary code product against code programming related properties. And not necessarily at level of a full featured user level product. Thus all code programming related properties could be cast down to certain software system related properties. **It follows PROGRAM VERIFICATION is a Subset Of Software (System) Verification: illustrated in Figure 18 !**

Program Analysis by Xavier-yerith (<https://zenodo.org/records/10990601>) !

13.13.2 How to use YERITH_QVGE

A software component or a whole running software binary could be verified against SQL correctness temporal properties by USING **YRI_QVGE**, as illustrated in Figure 16:

- The 1st layer illustrates the runtime verifier tester monitor engine: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, that entails several custom runtime monitor specifications, provided by user.
- The 2nd layer shows the **SUT (System Under Test)**; or **PUA (Program Under Analysis)**; layer that communicates with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF through QT socket calls (via Dbus messages). Each event message is sent to all runtime monitors. **The SUT source code has been instrumented first**, so to specify which program statements actions are to be packaged as messages to YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. **"INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could also be used to instrument program binaries at runtime directly, Avoiding recompilation and even usable where source code of SUT (PUA) is unavailable.**
- The 3rd layer illustrates a library or plugin (i.e.: **MySQL**) that is being monitored via instrumentation of the **SUT**; in this case, the **SUT** is YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum. **Other providers could modify An Open Source Code Version (FOSS) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF to verify and monitor another library-plugin other than MySQL.**
- The 4th and last layer shows the Operating System (OS) layer and its communication via systems calls with the 3rd layer of the library-plugin.

13.13.3 How to use YERITH_QVGE in relation to verification cyber-security detection remediation methods.

1. Model Checking (<https://wikipedia.org>):

Temporal logic formalisms, such as **LTL (Linear Temporal Logic)** (<https://>); Could be used to create **State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM)** (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) [1d] and generate a binary executable of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to perform runtime monitoring, and runtime SQL recovery of Graphical User Interface (GUI) supported software (And also not supported GUI software). Users must only note that "SDMM" specifications are **fail (forbidden) trace behavior specifications of a program under analysis (SUT)**.

Structures could be created on how to translate simple LTL constructs into simple "SDMM"; So to ease usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

2. Runtime Verification (Monitoring; including Software Cyber-Security Exploit Detection Remediation):

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from:

- **Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;**
- **WEB-APPLICATION RUNTIME MONITORING[?]; Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;**
- **Firewall security rules enforcement filtering;**
- **Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement : (E.g. : Figure 20);**
- **Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;**
- etc.

Could be solved by usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF GIT-REPOSITORY[1b]: **git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>**. **"Pr. Prof. Dr. Jean Yang, Ph.D." from CMU-"Carnegie Mellon University (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>)" could be a potential competitor in this area of research.":**

A. "Jeeves Programming Language" – last updated "October 2015" (<https://projects.csail.mit.edu/jeeves>)

- **API usage rule check at 'AKITA Software (<https://www.akita.com>)' in USA; California (CA).**
- **"Jeeves Programming Language" enables static typing;**
- **Dynamic code source rewriting to achieve Semantics; implemented as an embedded Domain Specific Language (DSL) in Python programming language (IT is unclear in which document [PROFESSOR JEAN yang checks] that this code is correct).**

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

Table 8: Jeeves Programming Language Versus (Vs.) The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

"Information Flow and Policy Control"	YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Jeeves Programming Language
1. Specification as a Domain Specific Language (DSL)	Yes (stand-alone SDMM (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d] DSL specification; Based on MEALY MACHINE AUTOMATON; "HAREL-statechart (https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf) compatibility") ✓	yes (DSL embedded into Python)
2. False (Positives) Warnings	No (1 formal proof exists in journal paper (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d]) ✓	* yes (CHECK A REFERENCE)
3. DSL Specification CARRIES DATA too	Yes (as Qt-DBus NETWORK data parameters) ✓	yes (as local stack function/method parameter)
4. As program annotations	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes ('Jeeves' instructions)
5. USABLE in a any programming language	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	no (Only Python)
6. ONLY usage with Python	No (any programming language that could emit Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes
7. Embedded in a programming language	NO ✓	yes (Python DSL library)
8. CRASH could occur during analysis and / or policy enforcing	NEVER	YES
9. Execution runtime overhead	No (concurrent event stream analysis monitoring verification) ✓	Yes (Embedded Python runtime dynamic source code rewriting)
10. Persistent storage technology	Yes; "MariaDB (https://www.mariadb.org)" ✓	Yes; "PostgreSQL (https://www.postgresql.org)" ✓

Table 8 compares tabularly the "Jeeves Programming Language" and "The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF". In contrast to the "Jeeves Programming Language" that specifies information flow policy and control enforcement for Python, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is not implemented as programming language feature, and thus could be used for any software system that could emit Qt-DBus signals ; Thus, information flow control and enforcement is run as a separate process, concurrently to the system under analysis (verification or monitoring) as pictured in Figure 16.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample SDMM ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d] specifying that a "FILE SHALL NOT be written-updated after it HAS BEEN CLOSED-DELETED".

13.13.4 Runtime Dynamic Program Interpretation Rewriting with "Jeeves"

The information flow policy control and enforcement solution provided by the "Jeeves Programming Language" is as follows :

1. A domain-specific language (DSL) is defined and embedded in a modification of the dynamic interpreted programming language Python. The drawback of an embedded DSL is a non re-usability in using other programming languages and framework other than those related closely to Python;

2. Only certain cases are flow policy control and enforcement are solved statically by "Python-Jeeves" type system;

It means that 'false positives warnings' cases still exist in programmer code and couldn't be removed by static compilation and / or dynamic code interpretation.

In contrast, "the mixed formal methods – runtime dynamic analysis monitoring" I used in "YRI_QVGE", don't allow by construction for 'false positives warnings': A 'false positive warning' is a message from the analyzing system that indicates an error accepting state while THERE IS IN EFFECT NO ERROR found yet.

3. Flow policy enforcement is solved dynamically at runtime by dynamic code rewriting; WE HOPE that this feature could be proved sound for all program statements because it might create uncertainty of valid flow policy enforcement at all.

Differently, "YRI_QVGE" uses SQL database statement query for performing error accepting state recovery (or—also—called "Information-Flow-Policy-Control-and-Enforcement").

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

13.13.5 Sample Comparison BETWEEN Object-ORIENTED programming languages”

Table 9: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++, Python, AND JAVA. JAVA has an (interpretative and / or JIT-compiled) virtual machines that are in FACT reactive systems (E.g. : A "GUI software" is as well a reactive system) ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)

FEATURES	C++	PYTHON	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	”	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓	✓	
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓	✓	
11. MULTI THREADING	✓	✓	✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓	”	✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM			✓

13.13.6 "Formal Methods – Runtime Dynamic Analysis" Vs. "Compiler Static Analysis Technology"

Figure 20: Runtime Verification Monitoring with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Figure 21: YERITH SDMM based runtime monitoring verification analysis.

Figure 22: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

I advocate :

1. Solving problems using compiler static analysis technology; that is based on lattice-theory is more safe than formal methods algorithms at first because MANUAL model checking has to be used to prove formal methods solutions correct, which could be very tedious and lengthy; "OR EVEN INTRACTABLE". SEE the state explosion problem (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Model_checking).

On the other hand static dataflow analysis algorithms based on lattice-theory are safe by construction and don't need no more proofs of consistency and validity as long as they only follow the base-pattern algorithm as for instance defined by "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)".

THE previous statement also applies when using an instance of a static dataflow analysis based on the IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) algorithm from "THOMAS reps" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) at "The University of Winsconsin-MADISON-mad". (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

2. The formal method approach I use in solving problems listed in "Subsection 13.13.3"; a combination of formal methods with runtime dynamic analysis is as perfect as the "static dataflow analysis" standard algorithm by "Gary A. kildall", because **YRI_QVGE** uses only "fail (forbidden) traces" specifications and only exactly 1 outgoing edge for each transition in a state diagram mealy machine specification (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]:

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from :

- Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;
- Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;
- Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement: I.E. ...
- Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;
- etc.

3. Runtime Verification Analysis Results Combined With Static Dataflow Analysis Algorithms à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" as ; for instance implemented in "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) :

- o One could combine runtime verification analysis facts with static dataflow analysis so to reduce fail state accepting code source location paths.

For instance, applying **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to find an API violation rule such as a "FILE-Write-AFTER-FILE-close" as specified in Figure 33; that specifies a "SDMM DSL code (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]" for finding a write after close program execution :

- a.) WHENEVER such a "file Close-WRITE API rule violation usage" is found by a runtime monitoring verifying analysis program binary, this information could later on be used by a static analyzer on code sources to eliminate manually from the program code sources code the found API violation RULE.
- b.) Our work : "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) on detecting tainted path with an application for finding API usage rule violation in C++ code as ILLUSTRATED in Figure 35, COULD be used for instance !
- c.) Symbolic Execution / test-cases-test-data generation :

WHENEVER a fail-state accepting state is found by a run execution of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

- 1.) Such a run could only be executed with some test data stored somewhere in the SUT; a test case is also available for free since of the trace event log.

Such acquired test cases & test data could then be used later on to create some "testing suites" to exhibit this fail-state accepting error sequence run !

Symbolic execution run with finding of test data using a constraint solver like "Microsoft-Z3" (<https://www.microsoft.com/research--idiot--z3>) for instance, is only needed in case more test data and / or test cases are required for this fail-state accepting run.

13.13.7 CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) TOOL for Software System Verification

Figure 23: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS.

Figure 24: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL ERROR EVENT LOG.

1. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an ISO-related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE—ISO certifications for Healthcare: [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

Figure 25: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS:

- a.) "ON-the-fly (Add-hoc)" online / offline RUNTIME Verification MONITORING of all financial transaction operations at a financial institution; ATTACH a device at each computer and / or server using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A comparable instance figure is illustrated for a control console device at Figure 25; WHEREAS one replaces a "control console LINAC" device with SERVER / Computer.
- b.) A linear accelerator control console communication protocol runtime monitoring (E.g.: Figure 25). A more detailed explanation graphical occurs in "Figure 20, Section 13.13.6";
- c.) A railway track controller program runtime monitoring console at site;
- d.) An aero-plane Maneuvering Characteristics Augmentation System (MCAS) runtime monitoring device
- e.) etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems (ERP; Software & Hardware)

Figure 26: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 27: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

1. **CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC enterprise resource planing (ERP) software system** [Mar. 2015 – CURRENT] [STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA; agile development method, [enterprise resource planing software], software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]
 - a. RENDER ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE SYSTEM USAGE AND MANIPULATION AS EASY AS READING A LEISURE OR RECREATIONAL BOOK SO TO REDUCE USER STRAIN SIZE ! (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 - b. CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCE POVERTY BY IMPROVING SOFTWARE SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY FOR ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP). (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 1. All following advantages of using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum contributes to reduce waiting files; THUS increase the number of customers and clients of an entrepreneurial organization !
 2. Best and accurate technology SHALL REDUCE management effort and produce more reliable and cost-minimized business financial accounting information that enables to anticipate and reduce time of decision making.
 - 1.) Gathering an overview over all financial and commercial; And customers / clients transaction information comes in JUST 1 button pressing from business dashboard window.
 - 2.) Exporting data onto Tabulator software such as 'LibreOffice-Calc, etc.' as Comma-Separated-Values (CSV), is as easy as selecting requested database table columns and Export them by pressing a button;
 - 3.) Calculating beneficial and interests costs is just as easy as reading it from business financial dashboard report generated automatically real-time and real-data from sales and customers, and / or Acquisitions databases tables.
 3. Best and accurate technology reduces time execution of commercial business transactions, and thus, associated costs.
 - 1.) Business Analytics : Ranking about sold and transferred goods and / or item stocks is best and just as easy done by reading it from a business commercial window dashboard; Ranking data decides what to order next for a better business turnover for your commercial financial entrepreneurial organization;
 - 2.) Ordering new item stocks is as easy as reading item stocks quantities from stocks window stock's inventory value.
 4. So entrepreneurial commercial organizations could reduce a selling price without reducing its profit.

14.14 R&D Hardware & Software System Components

- o YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET [docs] — for Security / Safety.
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA [algo] [docs] 📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
- o YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?] (🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9))
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] 📄 YRI_QVGE[1] (🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif))
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

14.14.1 Detailed Presentation View

1. **HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring:** ★ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.
FOSS documents location to..come..on..github.com/yerithrd (<https://github.com/yerithrd>)
2. **ERP software itself:** ★ YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
FOSS code location; 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
3. **Component 1:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-configurations-data": Configuration data for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
This software component entails:
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9.0.properties" that contains MariaDB database connection parameters data.
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9.0-system-local-configuration-ENGLISH.properties" that contains local computer device and storage configuration parameters data.
 - A folder "yerith-erp-9.0-sql-backup-restore" where YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM database backups will be stored.
4. **Component 2:** ★ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?]: Web Sites Generator Software Component.
FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
5. **Component 3:** ★ YRI_QVGE[1]: Runtime Monitoring Analysis Verification System.
FOSS code location 1 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
FOSS code location 2 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)
FOSS code location 3 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
FOSS code location 4 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS)
6. **Component 5:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon": Service daemon for alerts over inventory stocks, assets, and HR-payments.
FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems ("Adversaries systems")

Figure 28: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 29: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Table 10: Comparison between 'YERITH-ERP-9.0' and 3 top tier-1 ERP systems

Features	'YERITH-ERP-9.0' (≈ 10 years old)	'Contr-ALL' (≈ 7 years old)	'Sage Gescom i7' (≈ 40 years old)	'SAP Business One' (≈ 40 years old)
★ HR & CRM & Accounting full featured ERP	YES	NO	YES	YES
★ runtime monitoring checks enabled	YES (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	NO	YES	YES
★ Documentation online available fully	YES (Here For Instance) (https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724)	NO	NO	NO
separate views per user role	YES	YES	YES	YES
complete training (or solution)	at least 4 weeks	at least 3 weeks	at least 2 months	at least 3 months
★ difficulty in navigation	easy	easy	very difficult	very difficult
usage language in software	easy everyday English	simple	simple	technical
financial accounting knowledge	no	no	no	useful
advanced marketing knowledge	no	no	useful	useful
★ internet connection	optional	useful (not at all internet means no access to any of your business resources.)	optional	optional

Table 10 illustrates 3 other top-ERP Systems that I deem to be serious competitors of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for now and in future time because of the quality of their design and / or features; As Implemented for now As I could find out.

Some Observations

1.) 'Contr-ALL' is a youngest one with only at time of initial investigation after an interview Questions & Answers with its creator "Rostand-MOUNGAM", 7 years old !

"Rostand MOUNGAM" rents 1 of my apartment for his legal living & business consulting services, Together with "NAOMIE" his wife !

2.) 'Contr-ALL' seems very close to a good ERP System like 'Sage Gescom i7' !

'Sage Gescom i7' is at time of writing (June 2025) around 40 years old !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 3 – "ALGORITHMS CREATED / INVENTED"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC enterprise resource planing software (ERP)

[Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]

["YERITH R&D" Publications, STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

15.15 Summary of Created And / Or Invented ALGORITHMS in this ERP Project

Figure 30: Manager Main Window in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)

1. *Non intermingling of QT-timer & User-button-pressing events for Cancellation Confirmation.* ["class YerithERPCancelModificationTimingObject"]C++; YRI_QVGE.
 - a.) *Dynamic selection of Cancellation withing each window frame based on user interaction.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
2. *Concurrent algorithms using semaphores so to allow disk configuration data usage between multiple users.* ["class YerithPOSUser; class YerithWindowsCommons"]C++; Qt 5.
3. *Manual Selection & Viewing of user QTableView columns.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5; mathematics-geometry.
4. *Checking of daemon service running processes & emitting signals onto user viewing buttons.* ["class YerithAdminWindow"]C++; Qt 5; Bash; lxqt-sudo.
5. *Automatic online English / French translation algorithm.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
6. *Password detection & MD5-hash-Coding / Decoding for QT-widgets automatically.* ["class YerithPushButtonPASSWORD"] C++; Qt 5.
7. *Selection of each ERP sale-service function within only 1 window frame.* ["class YerithEntrerWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) *Graph coloring algorithm to find paths.* FSA; Graph-based algorithms.
8. *Pagination of QT-table data structure view-layout("QTableView")* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
9. *Printing & Creation of PDF documents based on LaTeX documentation system* ["class YerithTableViewPRINT_UTILITIES_TEX_TABLE"]C++; Qt 5; LaTeX.
 - a.) *Progress bar automatic Delivery for PDF-printing.* ["class YerithProgressBar"] C++; Qt 5.
10. *Online textual search & display of database query for window table frame items.* ["class YerithAbstractClassYerithSearchWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
11. *Automatic upgrade of SQL database between versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0.* [folder "yerith-erp-9-0-upgrade-sql/"] Git, Bash; SQL.

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA — Algorithms Excerpt

<https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>

1. *BASH-scripts to automatically generate a ".deb" file that entails configuration data for ERP-system software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum !* DEBIAN LINUX 11; Bash.

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)

1. *Translation algorithm from QT XML interface design-drawings onto YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 !* ["class YERITH_WEB_SYSTEMS_MAIN_GENERATOR"]Qt 5-QXmlStreamReader.
2. *Translator to generate PHP; HTML5; CSS code sources from YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0.* ["yerith-web-pages-generator/src"]YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0; flex; bison.

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)

1. *FSM based communication RPC algorithms to monitor and verify temporal properties scheme of [GUI] software.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"]DBus; C++; Qt 5.
2. *BNF grammar YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG Translator into a State Diagram Mealy Machine FSM.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] flex; bison.
3. *State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) library that enables runtime monitoring on-the-fly.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) *Fully compliant to David-harel statechart visual formalism.* David-harel [statechart](https://www.david-harel.com/).
 - b.) *O(n) graph traversal algorithm (Method "YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(string)").* finite state automaton; forbidden (fail) trace specification.
 - c.) *Grammar in Backus-Naur Form (BNF) for specifying State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM).* BNF (Backus-Naur Form).

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

1. *THREAD conform compliant algorithm to process stocks, & stocks-based alert messages triggered on time and / or quantities.* C++; Qt 5.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 2 – "DOCUMENTATION"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software (ERP)*

[Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]

[STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

16.16 Summary Documentation of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 31: *Generic Schema of Trading Realtime with YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (French language)*

■ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)a. *Database network connectivity – FRENCH*

Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)

https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-multi-sites-base-de-donnees/YERITH-ERP_multi_sites_base_de_donnees.pdfb. *Installation GUIDE – FRENCH*

Installation GUIDE – FRENCH

<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8060217>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA

◆ <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES II – Dissertation Thesis Doctor–PH.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering

Figure 32: YERITH-SAINT (LGPL license) : Accessing JAVA code with "Polyglot LLVM frontend"

A Mealy Machine State Diagram (SDMM) Specified Using Figure 33: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF Specification Language for NO-WRITE-AFTER-CLOSE memory check API file usage rule.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_Write_after_close_file
2. {
3.   START_STATE(closed):IN_PRE(g, is_alias(g, f))
4.   -> [in_set_trace('DELETE.file.f', STATE(closed))] / 'UPDATE.file.g' ->
5.     FINAL_STATE(WRITE_AFTER_CLOSE):IN_POST(g, is_alias(g, f)).
6. }
  
```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by static dataflow analysis mainly for the JVM-Java Virtual Machine; by late **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

a. **Research Proposal (Doctoral Ph.D. Thesis) in Electrical & Computer Engineering :**

🔗 **"Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software;"** (Advised by **Nomair Naem** | **Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** | **Patrick Lam, Ph.D.**) |

[UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH STATE DIAGRAM MEALY

[June 2024 – June 2024]

MACHINE (🔗 SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d]))

[YERITH R&D — [Software Safety], API (application programming interfaces) typestate checking;, tracematches, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, YERITH R&D — [computer software cyber-security, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION]

17.17 RESEARCH WORK OVERVIEW

THIS IS A PRELIMINARY WORK ON CHECKING TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES USING A TRACEMATCH-ALIKE SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE; SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) AND DATAFLOW ANALYSIS IS USED TO PRESENT A STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS.

TRACEMATCHES alike specifications enable developers to specify API usage rule drawing, as a deterministic finite automaton (<https://www.wikipedia.org>). Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented short overview slides of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010 ! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>). PDFSAM (<https://www.pdfsam.org>), and sample other Open Source Code Software (FOSS) ARE USED as benchmark for project evaluation.

18.18 SOLUTIONS WITH LLVM BY CHRIS LATTNER AT "APPLE LTD."

Instead of the 1st proposed Java-Soot approach as a whole program static dataflow analysis, a whole program context-sensitive dataflow static taint analysis for C using LLVM could successfully be implemented and described in 🔗 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34].

The 1st YERITH-SAINT algorithm was implemented for programs written in C programming language, and used a pre-processing step for analyzing points-to set using "poolalloc" (<https://github.com/poolalloc>) from Chris Lattner (<https://www.llvm.org>).

BECAUSE our static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework (Example : <https://github.com/polyglot-compiler/JLang>); See for instance Figure 32 !

20.20 RELATED WORK: DYNAMIC PROGRAM ANALYSIS API-RULE CHECKER "TRACERORY"

"Unread memory verification" is an instance of API (Application Programming Interface) usage rule checking.

"TRACERORY" runtime unread memory verification tool of Jon Eyolfson" (<https://www.hdl.handle.net/10012/6206>) ; "Detecting Unread Memory Using Dynamic Binary Translation at RV 2013 in Turkey" (<https://www.YRITOLOOKFOR.org>) , Of my former office roommate at "ECE-Waterloo-formal-method Davis Center Room" (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>), 1st floor, and colleague in static dynamic program analysis, could be outperformed with use of 🔗 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b]: "a runtime monitor container for state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)".

"TRACERORY" uses runtime program binary code instrumentation in "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) to instrument running programs for purposes of detecting unread memory; I ignore whether "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) has an open-source FOSS competitor at time yet; — Jan. 15, 2025 —.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample "SDMM" specification with instrumentation of source code with statements 'DELETE.file.f' and 'UPDATE.file.g' for runtime verification monitoring of API usage rule for checking memory write integrity: Runtime function "is_alias(g, f)" tells whether heap variable "g", and "f" refers to the same memory address. Such a "SDMM" specification is synchronized against a running program within a runtime monitor container: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .

21.21 CONCLUSION

"Due to incompatibilities with Patrick LAM; after March 10, 2015, I abandoned this research idea because I couldn't afford being laid-off without any letter or any other formal mean of communication other than telling a lie about a supposed ["Ph.D. Research Seminar"] at EIT building in Waterloo main (200 University Ave West) Campus! " (Ph.D. Dissertation Defence at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015")

It is easier to specify forbidden-fail-traces instead of saying how traces shall be like. Required 2 courses from overall 4 courses to pass where completed in year 2013-(CS846 & ECE750); in addition to before Examination completed courses (ECE725 & CS744). 4 experts in software systems were committee members of my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination AT UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA :

1. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.

Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca

2. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca

3. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca

4. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: lintan@purdue.edu

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Courses I VISITED while at the University–racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[ECE 725 / CS 745 – "Fall 2009",
CS 744 – "SPRING 2011",
First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques – "SPRING 2011",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
YERITH R&D — [program verification],
model checking,
compiler design]

Summary–PAGES

Table 11: Visited Courses at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 725 - Nancy Day" / "90%"	Fall 2009	Computer–Aided VERIFICATION	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 744 - Ondřej Lhoták" / "86%"	SPRING 2011	Advanced Compiler Design	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "1 st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques" / "N.A"	SPRING 2011	First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques	menlo–racist–college (https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml)

Table 11 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral Ph.D. in electrical & COMPUTER engineering degree program at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

- 1.) [Visited courses as a post-doctoral researcher.]

- 2.) [Advanced Compiler Design]:

This project–racist–based course gave me the opportunity to learn perfection my theoretical knowledge and foundations in the following topics:

- COMPILER structure and optimizations

- 3.) [Computer–Aided VERIFICATION]:

This assignment-based course gave me the opportunity to learn foundations of the following topics:

- MANUAL THEOREM proving (also interactive theorem proving with "interactive theorem prover" ISABELLE–HOL (HIGH ORDER LOGIC))
- MODEL checking (EDMUND clarke et al.)
- Temporal LOGIC

The course instructor NANCY idiot day, was very verse in this material and could answer almost all questions without searching somewhere else than herself.

- 4.) [1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques]:

This marvelous experience gave myself opportunities to meet and hear-listen from best talented researchers in following areas of industrial research among other topics that I CANNOT ALL REMEMBER :

- "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS"
- "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation"
- "Hardware / Software Co–Design"
- "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)"

I AM ALWAYS GRATEFUL to professor idiot NANCY day for having given myself this marvelous experience through her personal recommendation, As required for admission in the summer school !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED AS POST-DOCTORAND-FELLOW – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. [Courses I VISITED while at the University-racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]

[ECE 750 – "SPRING 2013",
CS 846 – "WINTER 2013",
Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme – "WINTER 2013",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
program verification,
model checking,
YERITH R&D — [Cyber-SECURITY],
compiler design]

Summary-PAGES

Table 12: Visited Courses as post-doctoral researcher professor at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 750 - Patrick Lam" / "88%"	SPRING 2013	Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 846 - FRANK Tip" / "88%"	WINTER 2013	Program Analysis for Web Apps	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme" / "85%"	WINTER 2013	Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme	Stanford university adult education online

Table 12 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral PH.D. studies degree program in Electrical & Computer Engineering at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

1.) [Program Analysis for Web Apps]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to DISCOVER, design and implement a web-based dynamic TAINT analysis for a PHP-JAVA interpreter; I.E. a "JAVA application server" that also interprets and use PHP libraries and code :

📄 "A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) :

1. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)
2. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)

2.) [Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to design and implement a static TAINT dataflow analysis: 📄 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293/>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

I didn't appreciate that instructor PATRICK-lam came to contest my Correct and Righteous definition of taint source and taint sink in front of class during my presentation; AND THAT he was wrong when he said we shall check the internet media; IT DOESN'T make sense to contest something that a doctor-PH.D. has prepared at least 4 weeks in advance such as he did !!!

3.) [Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme]:

I took this software security course to acquire more knowledge in software security vulnerability analysis and detection from a pioneer-leader as university in this area of research as demonstrated by publications and startups created by alumni.

MONICA-lam (<https://stanford.edu/suif>) for instance is a very renowned scholar and tech-entrepreneur in security vulnerability research and analysis. This online web course was very interesting from a content point of view for me as a doctor-of-engineering-ph.d..

ESPECIALLY because I WAS working on my "YERITH-SAINT algorithm" (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) FOR detecting, with static dataflow code analysis "à la "Gary A. Kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)", and fixing the HEARTBLEED-security breach bug in "OpenSSL-1.0.1-f" source code (<https://heartbleed.com>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

"BUT i could notify when i started passing the online examination for getting a printed sent per mailbox certificate; THAT there was a kind of re-make in another stand so "that I WOULD NEVER PASS with more than 95%" as required to acquire that certificate – (I HAD PAID around \$500 USA dollars for attending this online graduate adult education course)" !!! "

"I Was almost always getting a "84% grade" ("3 times") ! THIS actually represents the successful passing required academic grade for a doctoral level course at WATERLOO."

"I HAD EVEN visited the premises of STANFORD university together with SANDY-beidu-gay-idiot-from-ghana-cuon-pd "in year 2011" while attending a formal method techniques school at AHERTON-COLLEGE nearby "by around 40 minutes drive"."

YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

- I have prepared, and presented a static dataflow analysis in November 2010 at *IBM workshop CDP CASCONE 2010* (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>).

[Workshop-CDP; IBM casCon 2010]

The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software.

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for courses:
 1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)";
 2. "Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)".
- I have successfully attended the course ("CS 745 / ECE 725") – *Computer-Aided Verification* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>), taught by "Prof. Dr. Nancy Day". I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-ECE 725

THIS psy-professor is somewhat "a culprit of canadian armed robber forces only for black-descendants; Including iranian; holy-bible-CYRUS-ISIAH-45" (<https://www.sainte bible.com/lsg/isaiah/45.htm>).

1. OCAML functional programming language
 2. Propositional Logic
 3. First Order Logic (Predicate logic)
 4. Higher Order Logic (Lambda Calculus) "with Haskell"
 5. Theorem Proving
 6. Interactive Theorem Proving with "Isabelle HOL"
 7. Model Checking (with use of "SMV model checker")
 8. etc.
- *I have met in-person "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem" (HELP with understanding of static dataflow analysis algorithms): "Especially with context-sensitive parametric analysis".*
 - *I have as roommate and best-friend [Diplom-Ingenieur-Informatik (Dipl.-Ing.-Inf.)] THOMAS REIDEMEISTER, 'aus MAGDEBURG'. He is also a computer engineer graduate student "in ECE at THE university of Waterloo, ON".*

THOMAS (<https://www.reidemeister.com>) is so much helping to myself including recommending myself a "JAPANESE toyota corolla LE 2003-(plate BLAB 045)" car as buying tip because of low costs in maintenance in ontarian-Canada.

I learned at least 80% of a happyfull life in ontarian Canada from THOMAS as a kind of senior brother of mine.

- (a) Difference between brunch and lunch; with an invitation for a brunch in KITCHENER: I cannot remember the name of this very nice restaurant by a sunday-morning;
- (b) Farmer's market in Kitchener;
- (c) * * *—*Asian food market stores in Kitchener*—* * *;
- (d) etc.

"THOMAS moved-in into our student house as replacement for a nigerian so called CHRISTIAN-faked TOMIWA ADAMURULA (tom)."

"AS I have matured myself, "today, in 2024, "September 1st," THOMAS must be from NAZI-ss-combat engineering against black-descendants like "cameroonian MARTIN tchangoue", employed at LABFORGE.CA (<https://www.labforge.ca>)".

I could remember being very happy all time with * * *—*JOHN and ANNA GULDEMOND*—* * * the sweet-nice landlords.

20.20 YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

— I have met in-person Prof. Dr. Eric Bodden at our (Xavier, JON eyolfson) office room in "Davis Center".

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. **"Program Verification (Ph.D. thesis from Patrick LAM)"** (<https://patricklam.ca>)
2. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book **"Introduction to Algorithms"** ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVFeDlBzcVOqunH6HMFduvfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwlldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFG3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));
3. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;
5. Static Dataflow Analysis by Gary A. KILDALL (<a href=));
 - a. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>);
 - b. **"Tracematches formalism by Hendren, Lhoták, et al."** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>)

— *I have attended following workshops and conferences:*

[IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

1. **"IBM workshop CDP CASCON 2010"** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)
 - a. I could talk briefly with Patrick Doyle from **J9-JAVA** (<https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/configurepricequote/10.0?topic=machines-j9-jvm>) JIT-compilation team at IBM Toronto Software Lab
 - b. **Maxime Boisvert Chevallier** (<https://scholar.google.ca/citations?user=ISg6I8gAAAAJ&hl=en>)

[OOPSLA 2010]

3. "I have attended the conference **"Programming Language Design And Implementation (PLDI 2009)"** in Toronto:"

[International CONFERENCE-pldi-racist-extreme; PLDI 2009]

- o **Pr. Prof. Dr. JEAN yang, she was a then Ph.D. student and candidate at "MIT"** (<https://people.csail.mit.edu/jeanyang/index.htm>) " (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>) .
- o **"Nurudeen Lameed (from Nigeria)** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~nlamee>)", "and other **SABLE-mcgill** (<https://sable.mcgill.ca>) graduate students" and I presented to each other;
- o **"Pr. Prof. Dr. Tom Ball from Microsoft Research (MSR)** (<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/people/tball>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Florian Zuleger (from Austria)** (<https://informatics.tuwien.ac.at/people/florian-zuleger>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Stephan Zucker, PhD (from Switzerland)** (<https://>)", and I presented each other.

21.21 YEAR "2011"

Summary-PAGES

— "December 20th, 2011":

I have prepared and successfully passed my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination in front of at least 4 experts in Software System:

1. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.
2. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
3. Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
4. Prof. Dr. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

— I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for course:

1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)".

— I have successfully attended the course "CS 744" – **Advanced Compiler Design** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/cs744>), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták".

I could learn about following topics:

1. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)
2. Meet Over Paths (MOP)
3. Basic Block (BB), Control Flow Graph (CFG)
4. Three-Address-Code ("3-Address-Code")
5. Static Single Assignment Form ("SSA form")
6. Pointer (Alias) Analysis
7. Static Dataflow Analysis by **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall);
8. Transfer flow functions
9. Components of an advanced Compiler (E.g.: Optimizer, backend, etc.)

COURSE-CS 744

— I have met in-person "**Michael Pradel**". (https://software-lab.org/people/Michael_Pradel.html)

— I have met in-person "**ALEXIE tcheuyap-idiot-cuon-pd**". (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheuyap>)

— **I have, in summer 2011, received a personal visit of "Mae Wandji", baby of my uncle maternal "Théodore & Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoun": she was accompanied by "her mother Aurélie Yagno Wandji" ! "Mae Wandji", and her mother "Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoun", I dedicate a successful PhD comprehensive examination ! "**

— I have met in-person **Prof. Dr. MARTIN vechev**. (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aZ1Rh50AAAAJ&hl=fr>)

— I attended successfully the summer school: "**First Summer School on Formal Techniques**" (<https://fm.cs.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>); organized by The "National Science Foundation (NSF)" located at SOFTWARE RESEARCH INSTITUTE INTERNATIONAL (SRI International), at "Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA" from May 22, 2011 until May 27, 2011.

[ATHERTON-COLLEGE] / ["1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"-2011]

Topics we learned about and practiced where among others:

- o "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Natarayan Shankar")
- o "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. David Moniaux")
- o "Hardware / Software Co-Design"
- o "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Villem WISSER-neger-racist-stelenbosch-university-SA")

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book "**Introduction to Algorithms**" ([Holy-Ghost. YERITH-NISSI. \(JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN.\)](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-to-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHkskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVFeD1BzcVOqunH6HMFduvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));
2. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
3. JAVA component-based software development by OSI architecture and Eclipse IDE (Integrated Development Environment);
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;

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22.22 YEAR "2012"

Summary-PAGES

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick & Derek Rayside & Jon Eyolfson & Leo Passos, etc. for courses:
 1. "Compilers (ECE 351)": *Python scripts were written to automatically correct programming assignments from code source repositories.*
- *I went for an academic and professional internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab;*

I wanted to improve my programming languages design and implementation skills as well as BASH-scripting.

I spent 2 Academic terms (8 months) in Markham (Ontario, Canada) for this internship.

I worked there under supervision of [*Patrick Doyle, M.ASc.*,] and then "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*".

 - o I worked principally as a tester for certain optimization features of the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server (Servlet container) *IBM Websphere* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_WebSphere_Application_Server) under "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*". I was writing BASH-scripts to run and evaluate implemented certain optimization features for the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server.
 - o I could attend to lectures given at IBM Toronto Software Lab by "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Clark Verbrugge*" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>) from "*McGill University*" on Creating Optimizations for Compilers.
 - o I could improve my skills with the following tools among others:
 1. "GNU-bash" (<ftp://ftp.gnu.org/pub/gnu/bash>)
 2. "GNU-vi / GNU-vim" (<https://www.vim.org>)
 3. "GNU-screen" (<https://savannah.gnu.org/projects/screen>).
- "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*" wanted myself to be back next summer for another internship with him at IBM: unfortunately I resigned from this engagement because I felt I had to go back in my home country: Cameroon !
- I befriended myself at IBM with "*Aayush Prakash, M.ASc. (Waterloo, 2013)*" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>).
 1. I had a toyota corolla 2007 LUXUS EDITION; that's why Aayush PRAKASH 1st contacted me so I could help him mornings.

I tried trice but I COULDN'T anymore because I COULDN'T wake up so early; because MARKHAM is a very big city with so much traffic. BUT WE STAYED friend for ever.

THX. BRO.
 2. We then became roommate in Waterloo the following fall (September – December) term; I COULD appreciate someone nice and very comfortable with my living style since I am the one that was principally renting the 2-bedroom apartment on 16-457 ALBERT-STREET.

HE never not paid his subrent; and was also kind to learn more about how to better maintain a common washroom.

THEN he moved to IBM after successfully graduating with a M.ASc. in Electrical & Computer Engineering from PROFESSOR-racist HIREN-patel-racist !

I then went several times to visit AAYUSH when he moved to Toronto.
- I befriended myself in Toronto with the following fellow Cameroonian:
 1. "~~Prof. Dr. Alexie Tcheyap, Ph.D. (Laval, "French Literature", Quebec, Canada, 2008)~~" (~~GAY-maker-assassin !~~) (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheyap>);
 2. "Erick Djeuyou Pokem, B.ASe. (Lilles, "Business Informatics-MIAGE", France, 2007)";
 3. "Audrey Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc. (Laval, "Actuarial Sciences", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 4. "Judith Ngaleu, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Telecommunication Engineering", Quebec, Canada, 2005)";
 5. "Eunice Gapie Yemte, B.Sc. (Luxembourg, "Software Engineering", Luxembourg, 2008)" (assassin);
 6. "Valérie Yogho, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Electrical Engineering Power", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 7. "Tobie Guilliane, M.Sc. (Paris, "Financial Accounting", France, 2008)" (ASSASSIN);
 8. "Francis Mbiele Kamga, MBA (ESG, "Business Management", Paris, France, 2007)" (ASSASSIN).
 9. "~~FABRICE wilfried siemeni, B.Eng., (FH Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2005); Diploma (IHN, "applied HOLISTIC NUTRITIONIST", Mississauga, Toronto, Canada, 2012); -M.Sc. (FH Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2006)~~" (ASSASSIN).
- *I have attended following workshops and conferences in 2012*, together with "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM, Ph.D.*" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>), after completion of the internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab (*IBM Canada Ltd* (<https://www.ibm.com>)):

[WORKSHOP-local MITACS Ontario; International CONFERENCE; PLdi 2012]

 1. "*MITACS Ontario* (<https://www.mitacs.ca>) at the University of Waterloo on how to behave properly when having lunch and dessert with other professionals."
 2. "*Programming Language Design and IMPLEMENTATION (PLDI 2012)*" (<https://>) in Toronto downtown.
 1. *I COULD TALK TO several researcher among employees of GRAMMATECH-racist-negger* (<https://www.grammatech.com>) from THOMAS-reps at WISCONSIN-madison. (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

23.23 YEAR "2013"

Summary-PAGES

— I talked in-person with "Mahesh Tripunitara" about some of my non understanding about Doctor-PhD advisor of mine "Patrick Lam"; "MAHESH TRIPUNITARA" said I shall look for research collaborations within University of Waterloo and just put the name of "Patrick LAM" at end of a publication !

I AM STILL VERY GRATEFUL for this insight into my life as a scientist that led me to try and talk successfully with following pro-eminent fellow computer scientist:

- "Vijay Ganesh"; very proud of having learned much of how to write a paper and / or reviews of other papers with him; I cannot be a Ph.D. or doctor without this collaboration !

THIS IS SOMEONE very good at teaching research skills only. I cannot say much about his private behavior since I generally don't mix my private life with professional life !

- ["Mohammad Hamdaqa" from THE STAR research lab (<https://star.uwaterloo.ca>)]
- "Aayush Prakash" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>) (from IBM internship in Markham)
- "Leo Passos" from Generative Software Development research group at university of waterloo (<https://gsd.uwaterloo.ca/~lpassos>)
- "Frank Tip" (from IBM Research then as Professor at the University of Waterloo): AT all the very much inspirational about 'A SO CALLED taint analysis' in my research area at all.

Before visiting CS846 of "Frank Tip", I cannot know anything about what is a Taint Analysis (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

THIS CS846 (Program Analysis of Web Apps) is my best course as a graduate student in terms of working on related papers and writing reviews. Frank Tip is a very good and proud research manager !!!

"Only 1 tip, and you get all the clue about what you really need to do."

- "Pavel Parizek" (https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=M_9_-WsAAAAJ&hl=en) (from Programming Language Research Group (PLG) (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>), invited by "Ondřej Lhoták")
- "BORZOO" (<https://>) (very respected in RV conferences series)

THIS [friend-kkk] of *sebastian fischmeister from AUSTRIA-adolf-hitler* (<https://uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>) is so kind that he let myself in his office to present what I really want to perform as research. BUT i could notify an office with kind of ground-tapestry for WHAT-the-fuck.

24.24 YEAR "2013, 2ND PAGE"

Summary-PAGES

— I co-taught and assigned marked with "Mahesh Tripunitara" and "Igor Ivkovic" for courses:

- 1.) "Computer Networks (ECE 428)";
- 2.) " * * * Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) * * * "
- 3.) " * * * Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) * * * ".

Several employees from "Google Waterloo Inc. (<https://www.google.ca>) " attended lectures ("Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651)", and "Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650)");

[DIVAM JAIN racist from CA-U.S.A. even tried to make me hired there once ...].

— I started implementing a *LLVM context-sensitive solution to my Research Proposal Thesis* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) ; Because *SPARK pointer analysis in SOOT* (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) didn't permit for pointer-analysis data as a stand-alone pre-processing step, as *my early design of the static dataflow analysis suggested* (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

— I have successfully attended the course [Program Analysis of Web Apps ("CS 846")], taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr. Frank Tip" (<https://northeastern.edu/~ftip>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-CS 846

1. web applications
2. Javascript
3. dynamic analysis
4. static dataflow analysis
5. "Quercus server" dynamic taint analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) [3] by practicing within a personal single project
6. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have successfully attended the course Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE) ("ECE 750"), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-SASE-ECE 750

1. dynamic analysis
2. static dataflow analysis
3. "static taint analysis" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34] by practicing within a personal single project:

"I am the only one who had this idea of performing static taint analysis, because I previously did a dynamic taint analysis in FRANK-TIP-CS846—racist-course. *THE CS OF UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO wasn't* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca>) even capable of [finding this racist-cs846 segregative course curriculum] when I asked for it in year 2022; Even FTP, the creator of it WASN'T confident to give it to a black from AFRICA ! "

[r-IT Seems NDJATIE-from-rotary commanded again FTP from the inside.]; *EVEN her husband ["pr. shanda; YVAN-plumber-bafang-babouantou"]*, is very well recommended by YAOUNDEACS these days. (<https://>)

[AHHHH, also THE general of science KLAUS HAVELUND from N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov/YaoundeACS>) was also invited by my emails so to acquire some knowledge about [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF] since his paper with SFISCHME wasn't very proper.] (<https://www.ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>)

4. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have On the website of *stanford university* (<https://www.stanford.edu>) in the state of CALIFORNIA; IN-the-U.S "unsuccessfully (with "84% grade") attended" the course *Software Security*. I could learn about following topics:

[STANFORD.EDU—online-course-software-security 2013]

1. PRIVATE / PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE—key (GPG); CERTIFICATE—authority
2. CYPHER DECYPHER CRYPTOGRAPHY—algorithm
3. SSL-Secure—socket—layer protocol on HTTP protocol
4. ATTACKS strategies:
 1. SQL injection
 2. Buffer—overflow attack
 3. MAN-IN-MIDDLE attack
5. etc.

25.25 YEARS "2014" – "03 / 2015"

Summary-PAGES

— I find a very imposing book that explains in my better terms algorithms fixed point static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>):

- "*Advanced Compiler Design & Implementation*"; ISBN: "978-1558603202", by Steven Muchnick.

THIS book doesn't destroy your brain like the book:

- "*PRINCIPLES OF PROGRAM ANALYSIS*"; ISBN: "978-3642084744", by Flemming Nielson.

I implemented my own static dataflow fixed point algorithm in C++ object-oriented, and I published it on my student Ph.D. page <https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~xnoumbis>; And on my defunct GITHUB.COM-web-page: <https://github.com/xnoundou/saint>.

I then improved and finished my static dataflow taint analysis, and starts preparing my Ph.D. research seminar as presented in booklets present in "ECE graduate students room" in EIT building !

NOT very long after this online internet-web publication; I LEAVE WATFFORM for Cameroon where I created YERITH R&D, and affiliated software systems programs.

— I met Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) in-person for a review of my created LLVM context-sensitive static dataflow analysis: HE WAS RELUCTANT only because of 1 missing application of the analysis.

— *I assisted students in the LABORATORY for coding in C++ during 2 weeks:*

C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)

1. "C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)".

[!!! Iranian canadian university of waterloo professors !]!!

My colleague JON EYOLFSON (<https://jeyolfson.com>) with Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan (<https://ece.star.uwaterloo.ca>), went to suppress my appointment illegally since I legally, according to ECE department regulations for 2 weeks vacation for personal illness purposes, sent JON eyolfson as a replacement laboratory instructor to myself to LADAN !

I couldn't recover my job as teaching assistant in laboratory at my stay-return from JON EYOLFSON that I sent to Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan, for only 2 weeks replacement of myself !

— I have prepared, and presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis in January 2015 at a DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE programming language research group (PLG) seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Dissertation Defense at PLG]

I had this work successfully approved at PLG by "dear-racist-idiot Ondřej Lhoták" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>).

The title of my talk was: **CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM** (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) ; the presented application was the finding of a buffer-overflow security vulnerability in SSL (Secure Socket Layer) protocol as found in the "HEARTBLEED bug" (<https://heartbleed.com>) .

"Dr.-PH.D. ALI TELAGHANI was the 1st iranian university of waterloo Ph.D. Candidate I reviewed. A former trainee of nancy day from watform. (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>) "

AT THE conference presentation table were present among others :

- (a) Pr. Prof. Dr. MAGNUS MADSEN (<https://www.cs.au.dk/~magnusm>)
- (b) Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. "Peter Alan Burh" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/about/people/pabuhr>)
- (c) etc.

— I have prepared, and successfully presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis on "April 16, 2014" at an ECE graduate seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Research Seminar]

The title of my talk was: **CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM** (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) .

There was around at least 20 other students attending this seminar (kind of lecture).

[The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software by static dataflow taint analysis.]

26.26 RESEARCH OUTCOME HINDRANCE

Summary-PAGES

IT WASN'T POSSIBLE TO IMPLEMENT THE STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS AS PRESENTED because of the non possibility to acquire points-to information as a pre-processing standalone phase/step from SPARK POINTER ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK IN SOOT.

It wasn't in my research interest for a "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering" to dive into recreating a pointer analysis for SOOT by modifying for instance research outcome work of "AAKARSH NAIR, MASC (2009)".

It would be more productive to perform research with "Ondřej Lhoták" in "Mathematics Department at DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) rather than with DR.-PH.D Patrick LAM at ECE Department. So I stayed out of this area of research for the "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering"; Computer Software Engineering is more focused on developing methodologies around software rather than creating complex computer algorithms for calculation purposes; AS this is done in Computer Sciences (E.g.: "Ph.D. in Computer Science").

It is somehow also feasible for a "Computer Software Engineer" easily to implement a "pointer analysis as a Ph.D. in Computer Sciences could do whenever needed" !

I ("Doctor–PH.D. of Engineering Xavier Noubissi Noundou") have, for instance demonstrated, I could at least at level of a pointer dataflow analysis design and implementation performed by implementing the 1st openly (FOSS) published on the internet (2015): [CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC DATAFLOW ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ! \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\) \[34\]](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) : "git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>".

27.27 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM

Summary-PAGES

1. 1st of all, I need to mention that JON eyolfson has tried to remove all connections to my person in his documents I could see on the internet media and / or wherever else.

FOR instance, JON eyolfson doesn't mention anymore he reviewed papers for OOPSLA 2010; I ASSUME because my name stays also in the document viewable from the web I COULD SEE last .. (https://dl.acm.org/action/showFmPdf?doi=10.1145%2F1869459&ved=2ahUKEwibYOExb6IAxXdgP0HHfm0A2YQFnoECCIQ&usq=A0vVaw0DwvmxPoRXI7v__J6preu)

"Doctor–PH.D of Engineering JON EYOLFSON" (<https://www.ece.utoronto.ca/people/eyolfson-j>) could for instance implement a Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall) static dataflow pointer analysis based on my research outcome in ["XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU'S DOCTORAL EXCERPT DISSERTATION" \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293); Even though he didn't cite my previous work and also Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

Instead, HE WENT ON TO CITE "John B Kam and Jeffrey D. Ullman", in 'Monotone Data Flow Analysis Frameworks' !

I could also notify that the description of the flow functions in JON EYOLFSON's doctoral thesis, Acknowledged by "Professor Doctor–PH.D of ENGINEERING "Ана-Міланова" from RIP (Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute) (<https://www.cs.rpi.edu/~milanova>)", Wasn't compliant to the highest academical standard as IT IS DUE for a university in ONTARIO–CANADA.

"Jon" instead of performing a pre-processed step pointer analysis result searching, went on to implement a whole program static dataflow analysis, INCORPORATING an LLVM-based pointer analysis, copied from my work, Without citing it ("I finished that work in 2015", While "JON Eyolfson" defended his Ph.D. thesis containing this pointer analysis in 2018).

"I could also note it seems ["Ondřej Lhoták"] wasn't a member of JON eyolfson dissertation defence examination committee (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), even though HE ('Ondřej Lhoták") is the most famous scientist in this area of research at the UNIVERSITY of WATERLOO based on his publication and citation record (<https://dblp.org/pid/05/469.html>). "

Better said HE is kind of a JOHN–Hopcroft level academical professional scientist based on my research time worldwide & abroad of GERMANY & Cameroon–Africa !

2. " My intellectual and copyrighted work with "DIVAM JAIN, M.Math", now at ["Google Waterloo Inc."] (<https://jobs.google.com/about/>), has by now produced at least 11 scientific published papers worldwide, with money rewards, [without my name on neither on them.]“

INSTEAD, other people reward from it:

1. Dr. Patrick LAM;
2. Dr. Reid Holmes;
3. Dr. Derek rayside;
4. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc. (<https://dblp.org/pid/170/1472.html>)"; (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)
5. etc.

QUARRELED PAPERS:

1. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

Plagiarism

28.28 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM – CONTINUED – 1

Summary-PAGES

1. "Professor Araving Machinry" also used code sources results from my Static Dataflow Analysis without any citation of it in his Award winning USENIX paper; I mailed him in 2017; HE said that my work wasn't published by a peer-refereed conference and/or workshop, or whatsoever, THAT'S WHY he couldn't cite it.

Instead of citing the 1st original publication of a Free and Open Source Software code (FOSS), 2015, As I have published in on 'www.github.com (git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>)'; ARAVIND cited instead my competitor BODDEN-ERIC (<https://www.bodden.de>) (from Germany (<https://www.fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Allemagne>) and Previous colleague of Patrick LAM (<https://www.patricklam.ca>) at McGill University (<https://www.mcgill.ca>)).

Long after terminating my research collaboration with Patrick LAM at University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA; I could then notify that he was talking especially to "ARAVIND machinry my competitor about my research under his supposed supervision without telling it to myself!"

2. A ghanaiian ignorant, wretched worldwide called SANDY-beidu thinks he could behave so to alter my JEOVAH-NISSI-confidence at his underground-peggist home in bavaria-waterloo.

BEcause I rented a "ford fusion" during my travel to the "1st summer school on formal techniques" in ATHERTON, california; So to be mobile because I HAD TRAVELED to united states of america before when I WAS an employee of bavarian Siemens-medical-solutions; THIS guja went on to buy as his 1st car a similar "ford fusion" since he thought I WANTED to show up in front of him and ANOTHER black-afro-descendant from long-islands.

I AM EVEN wondering how this lady from basement science could be invited to the summer school ! AT ALL ! may be a call-girl !

FROM academic level point of view, this ignorant doctor of philosophy in computer science, SeEms to ignore what I COULD BUILD AS [enterprise resource planing (ERP-system) software !!!!!!!!]

3. JAN peleska from GERMANY, didn't say anything about the law against myself in Cameroon because he is the one who went to report false behaviors of myself to Cammeroon authorities about my living style in Germany without telling anything to me about.

Even at German Embassy in Yaounde, I could notify a strange behavior of people working there against myself while I came to complain against FRANGK-BIYA, son of PAUL-BIYA. THIS-GAY-with-my cousin-PATRICE-GABRAL-SHANDA-SANOUE (deceased by now since March 18, 2024 went to destroy my investment by creating a forestry society just opposite of my lawful building for peaceful habitation usage) !

JAN peleska from GERMANY, also seems to be the one that said and commanded PATRICK LAM to destroy my career because I reluctantly refused to pursue doctoral Ph.D. research (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/gesy>) under his supervision at the University of Bremen; I.E. Jan peleska insulted violently myself in front of HELGE LOEDING (<https://www.LOEDING-ONLINE.de>), SERGE FOPOUSSI NONO ACHILLE (<https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/person/gnd/141875240>), etc.

I cannot live with racial segregation !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 2 – Dissertation Thesis Doctor–PH.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering – continued - 2

Figure 34: YERITH-SAINT ([LGPL license]) Algorithms Architecture. "poolalloc" pointer-alias analysis tool from "Chris Lattner" at "APPLE Ltd." is re-used.

Figure 35: A sample **API rule violation** as tainted path "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i)) L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" (**orange colored lines of code**); on LLVM THREE-ADDRESS-CODE.

```

1      ssize_t write(int fd, const void *buf, size_t count); // taint sink
3      uint SAVE_Document (unsigned x, int fd, const void *buf, size_t count) {
4  L1: uint sum = 0;
5  L2: uint i = 0;
6  L3: if ( x == 2)
7  L4: close(fd); //API rule violation(--taint) source; "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i))"
8  L5: else //not VALID api rule check !
9  L6: sum = 0;
10 L7: if ( i >= x)
11 L8: goto L12;
12 L9: sum = sum + i;
13 L10: i = i + 1;
14 L11: write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i));
15 L12: goto L6;
16 L13: return sum; }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of [Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by taint analysis] – Continued

b. Doctoral "Ph.D. degree" Dissertation in Electrical & Computer Engineering: "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"; (Advised by Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem | Pr. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Frank Tip | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh) |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[SEP. 2012 – AUG. 2015]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH TYPESTATE-API USAGE RULE CHECKING; STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM[1d]))

[JUNE 2024 – JUNE 2024]

[Software Safety, API (application programming interfaces) tystate checking, tracematches, temporal safety property verification, cyber-security, software security vulnerability analysis, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION, Disputation-january-2015-DC-room-PETER-ALAN-BUHR]

The same class of problems that solve taint analysis issues resolve also API usage rules checking for specification of forbidden usage rules as a tystate specification. A violated API tystate (tracematch-alike) usage rule corresponds to a tainted path or a sub-tainted path (E.g.: path "L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" in figure 35).

You specify a **forbidden (fail trace)** [sequence of method calls that shall not occur in the source code]. Using static dataflow taint analysis, you check whether this specified forbidden (fail trace) corresponds to a tainted path or a subpath (of a fail trace).

"API (application programming interfaces) usage rules [tystate formalism is a similar paradigm of specification possible for input for this static context-sensitive taint analysis; "subsequent research of mine alone reveals state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) as a subset of tystates (SDMM[1d]),"] of JAVA or C++ library are another realm of application of this static context-sensitive (parametric) dataflow taint analysis."

"In contrast to Tracematches that specifies WISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM TRACE) of API user interface rule calling method sequence; as illustrated in "Hendren, et al. work" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>), "state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) BY XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU, SPECIFIES UNWISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM FORBIDDEN FAIL TRACE)" (SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d])."

"One effort could be to give a formal translation methodology from "tracematches onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM)"; Thus enabling automatic reuse of all tracematch specifications directly into a runtime monitor engine like YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) ."

"Patrick has not at time understood that this application is also possible by static dynamic program analysis tool created by myself at YERITH-RD: YRI_QVGE[13.13]; a Free and Open Source Code Software (FOSS)."

"Patrick LAM my former advisor since '2015-MARCH-10' is missing !"

"Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented a short overview presentation of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)"

A SINK IS AN ACCEPTING (error) STATE; A SOURCE IS A START STATE. Sources and sinks are methods from the library (or plugin) used by the program under analysis (PUA). Edges are other method program instructions as seen by a THREE-Address-Code representation such as Jimple (SOOT), Gimple (GCC), etc., and, or LLVM three-address-code format.

Since YERITH-SAINT our (Xavier, Vijay, and Patrick) static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, and perform as well API USAGE RULE check.

IT means in effect that any programming language that could be inputted to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, COULD BENEFIT FROM THIS SOFTWARE STACK api (application programming interface) rule checker.

- YERITH-SAINT (Figure 34) : [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)
- [PH.D.—RESEARCH—SEMINAR TALK] GIVEN AT AN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING) GRADUATE SEMINAR TALK SERIES, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf)

"Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), A world renowned scholar and scientist from the University of Waterloo in Waterloo, Canada, Ontario; Has reviewed this work with only 1 recommendation: add an additional application sample example apart from the presented "FORMAT STRING VULNERABILITY (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncontrolled_format_string)" analysis done in the research paper."

1. **L' INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE—Yaoundé—Centre D'excellence PAUL—biya—rdpc.** |
INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE, YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION, CAMEROUN

"2016"

[1 institut (<https://www.iaicameroun.cm>) atypique,
ARMAND—claude abanda,
NANGA.]

Summary-PAGES

I. D'enseignant vacataire à ENSEIGNANT consultant "20 heures—la—semaine de cours" À "6,11 EUROS" par heure:

Mes rapports d'encadreurs académiques de SALABESSI—cuon—pgsiste de MBANJOCK :

1. JE postule via "4 heures" d'attente au sale bureau du courrier pour être reçu par 1 ingénieur inférieur au rang de "bachelor of science" (ndlr.: LICENCE en informatique);
2. Après être reçu pour 1 entretien special avec M. ARMAND—claude—abanda—idiot; je passe 2 interviews supposées professionnelles;
3. A l'issue de la 1^{ère} interview qui n'est qu'1 vérification brève du curriculum vitae et de très petites connaissances pédagogiques; L'ON ME propose plutôt 1 poste d'ENSEIGNANT consultant plutôt que celui de vacataire à 8 heures de cours hebdomadaire auquel j'ai postulé.
4. L'on ma redemandé de donner tous des cours que je pensais être en mesure de distillés; SUR cette palette de cours, l'on m'a octroyé "Architecture des ordinateurs" comme 1^{ère} mission pour la 1^{ère} année de GÉNIE—LOGIGIEL en section anglophone de leurs cursus d'études.
5. Après seulement "2 semaines et demi", 1 certain "salabessi" vient me donner l'injonction de commencer aussi à donner le cours "ADMINISTRATION SYSTÈME programmation système".
6. JE décide de partir de cette institution puisque ce rythme de travail serait insoutenable pour ma santé fragile à cette période de l'année au vu du changement du climat hivernale canadien au climat tempéré de YAOUNDE—raciste—tribaliste—mado—BIR :
 - a.) Toute heure de cours est payée ("8 heures par semaine" dans mon cas); IL ne m'est jamais mentionnée auparavant que 20 heures de travail la semaine ne concerne que la dispensation des cours au tableau.
 - b.) Toute autre heure de travail est impayée :
 - PRÉPARATION des données pour des devoirs surveillés;
 - CORRECTION des examens et devoirs surveillés;
 - RÉDACTION d'1 support de cours en langue anglaise.
 - [IL semblerait que 1 sœur utérine à ma personne; "Ingride TCHITCHUI noumbissi, Épse chandriand—TEUNTCHOU noumeni" serait allée dire que je suis 1 patient psychiatrique pour destituer ma vie, telle qu'elle aurait organisée en FÉVRIER 2021 avec le "rotary—club de abanda armand à ÉDEA".]
 - PARTICIPATION tous des mercredi à 1 réunion d'enseignants consultants; (EX.nihilo; je n'ai participé à aucune d'elle en 3 semaines de travail vu le temps d'adaptation à la localisation très éloigné du centre de cours de NKOLN'ANGA).

II. Mes Conclusions SUR LA QUALITÉ de cet institut de merde :

- 1.) [JP-kamgain, le cas d'échec patent de l'IAI cameroun !!!]
- 2.) PAS de suivi exact des besoins et difficultés de nouvelles recrues;
- 3.) ABANDA—amougou—belinga (<https://>), écroulé par des heures de cours sans avisé des enseignants :
2 fois consécutives, on me redemande de dispenser plutôt 4 heures de cours et exercices d'affilés plutôt que des 2 heures de cours prévues dans le "planning" pour CAUSE que l'enseignant du cours suivant s'est absenté.

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
Jon eyolfson—idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
SARAH—white—kkk—peggist; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. ["Professor RAYSIDE"]

2. ["Student JON eyolfson, then Master of Applied Science JON."]

" This idiot white-supremacist-racist, that is watching videos about a murderer called 'LUCIFER' in our common office room while taking his lunch, is JUST A DISGUSTING kkk."

THIS junior computing engineer couldn't create a website for Watform lab (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>) after around 7 years doing a PH.D. in Computer Electrical Engineering: HE Had been mandated to do so in year 2009 when I started my "Ph.D. degree in Electrical & Computer Engineering" program as a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]. from the so-called-elite-universität-BREMEN-germany-de. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)!

3. "Student Hang chu (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/2656af1b-8829-45fb-bc5b-d1f49762ad49>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science HANG—chu."

THIS very-well-to-do person from China main island came to myself for a recommendation into a position as software developer in MISSISSAUGA—Toronto—idiot; I Accepted and tried to be very honest and humble in a form request form that was sent to myself the same day by a lady from "PHILLIPS subsidiary company" newest created !

4. "Student Wenzhu MAN (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/5ac24928-7279-41f1-9c58-634873430305>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science Wenzhu—MAN."

THIS ugly lady from CHINA main island, came into the lab-space rented to us by PATRICK—idiot—advisor during my 2nd year of doctoral PH.D. studies.

SHE seemed very intelligent but very hostile to black people as I could see her behavior when I asked her if she would like to collaborate on my ongoing static dataflow analysis YERITH—SAINT project, after I ASKED for this with, a positive approval from our common idiot supervisor ["PATRICK—vietnamese—vietkong LAM"].

SHE was reluctant and we never had any opportunity to present and/or Work on anything together; AS this was the same with [JON eyolfson; Who instead copied my work only !]

5. "PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG, WEST REGION, CAMEROON)"

" THIS sample ignorant on "algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers" that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the "ELITE—UNIVERSITÄT—BREMEN" (<https://www.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON."

"I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes—FRANCE in "2004" when he visited "GRENOBLE laboratory" with PROFESSOR tchindo—gilbert."

"I tried to contact him during "September—2011" because I HEARD from MARCELIN TALLY, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?] " like our common age-class colleague Oscar MOURBARE from Ngaoundere—Cameroon. [Dr.—Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS—Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>). "

"HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone call while I was in Cameroon ! "

ISSUES and Misunderstandings 2 |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
 Jon eyolfson-idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
 SARAH—white—kkk-peggish; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:**6. "FORMER friend and now enemy Godrick CHEKETE H. from Benin—vaoodoo"**

I encounter this idiot and voodoo man as I just entered my second year of doctoral studies at the university—racist of waterloo in ONTARIO, CANADA

THE Ghanaian so called YAW BOAKYE-agyeman, that I EVER met 1st time in African student association of the university of waterloo: "AFRSA" (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>) as I was in my 3rd week in the city of Waterloo.

IT is the west—african student YAW, BOAKYE-agyeman, from ashanti—tribe that told myself that he would like to introduce me to another FRENCH-speaking student from WEST-AFRICA.

WE then met 3 of us in a restaurant inside the main campus located at 200 University Avenue West; I DON'T REMEMBER the name of the idiot-wwhite—racist restaurant for students.

7. "FORMER enemy MARTIAL ategomo YEMELE from Cameroon"

I encounter this vagabond because GODRICK—chekete recommended HIM (martial ategomo yemele to myself as a cameroon student in need of crucial help in life)

Normally I NEVER friend myself with such Cameroon people that seemed to have traveled with fake ID and other faked documents as I could imagine from his physical being.

IN year 2013, as I went to build a gate for my compound in YAOUNDE, Godrick and MARTIAL ATEGOMO YEMELE came ask myself that I sublet my bedroom-only for 1 month only to MARTIAL for "400 cad". I accepted and I needed afterwards to tell him very deeply to go out after "1 and half month" because HE seems to be wanting to stay even more than 6 months in my 2—bedroom apartment located at "16—457, ALBERT-ST., N2L 5A7, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA—racist-idiot".

Martial ategomo and Godrick Chekete H.; I stopped any collaboration with both these ignorant right after asking MARTIAL and GODRICK to leave my apartment around 11 : 30 PM at night.

8. "ECE Master & Ph.D. programs coordinator Sarah Landy, MSc."

THIS very racist girl with a master of science, arrogant at all wanted myself to believe that SHE is a professor of mine even though I am wondering even today if she could even work somewhere else than a place where systemic racism is the norm and not the ANORMAL life day—work !

"This slot for professors of ECE is the one that on "MARCH 10th, 2015" told myself; "as she was a PH.D. & MASTER program coordinator in ECE department" of the university-racist of waterloo: "[Patrick (lam)] sent an email to cancel the event (MY SO CALLED PH.D. RESEARCH SEMINAR) according to academic graduate studies regulations of year 2015 ! " "

" SARAH as I could experience even when I PASSED ONTO HER HANDS my doctoral thesis; called research proposal at ECE department, has a personal grievance to my person from somewhere I CANNOT even imagine; because THIS document wasn't published anywhere or registered publicly on the university-racist of waterloo internet, or intranet—world ! "

9. [Professor idiot lin tan]**10. P[rofessor Patrick LAM]****11. [Professor LADAN]**

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECÉFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "January 14, 2026"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA:

1. Doctor Christian Eyoum–sawa-rotarian–criminal–seasoned–psychiatrist (Laquintine HOSPITAL
DOUALA, CMR (<https://>))

[Around "2021"]

THIS seasoned psychiatrist that assassinates at least 500 persons a year was sent to me by "ROSE sangnou" my female genitor so to hijack my private–inherited apartment in "DLA-cité-des-palmiers" as I was just finishing a psychology family and personal treatment because OF "LAURENT-tchandeu", a criminal uncle paternal side of mine.

IT is at age of 6 years old that I lost my dear criminal genitor "THÉODORE noumbissi-salau"; I called this genitor of mine a "salau" because this freemason had a booklet on economy written by "KARL–idiot-mars" where I COULD SEE just a month after his sudden death, caused probably by NTOMANI–Racist, THAT theodore-noumbissi said: "GOD is stupidity and dirt !" !

IT is at age 35 years old that I understood that this mason of my genitor, "THÉODORE noumbissi"; tried to hijack myself but loose his own soul because mainly of his junior brother "LAURENT tchandeu".

"CHRISTIAN-eyoum" is only someone that destroys in all plans of life any person sent to him by "SECRETARIAT-D'ÉTATA-LA-DEFENSE (sed)", a so called SERVICE-SECRET.

IT seems the culprit eyoum sent some people from his hospitals to rent my 1st–storey house bedroom-apartment so to hijack people that want to travel to western countries.

I am suspicious of this because I cannot foresee an issue in the legal case I started at DLA-ndokoti justice palace in February 14th; After christian eyoum and state hospital laquintinie sent at least 9 people at night around 23 : 30 to hijack my real–estate property and life.

Also, eyoum walks with a walkie-talkie of cameroonian defense forces; SO he is somewhat a criminal of the army that must be arrested by SEMIL–ndlr.: Sécurité MILITAIRE: a so called anti-gang unit against criminal from cmr defense forces.

2. Doctor KLAUS HAVELUND–idiot (Caltech, California Technology Institute
CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (<https://www.caltech.edu>))

["2022"]

Klaus is an idiot because HE wasn't capable of coming clearly with his expectations as I contacted him to review my at that time ongoing and starting project on CREATING A RUNTIME MONITORING VERIFICATION testing framework 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[1d\]](#) for state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) having following characteristics compared to opponents like; "TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System)" implemented in real-time testing tool 📄 [RT-Tester \(https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf\)](https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) [?] of the society in germany: "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) "; AND opponent tool ""DejaVu" (<https://>) ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic")" :

- o A Domain–Specific LANGUAGE (DSL) for specifying forbidden traces (fail traces) of mealy machine, formalized as state diagram: "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG".
- o A compiler–translator that generates free C++ code as runtime monitoring verification module to be run and watched "within runtime monitor container 📄 ["YRI_QVGE" \(https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf\)](https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d]".
- o "fail (forbidden) traces specification".
ALL competitors were having 'wished behavior trace specification';
- o "NO FALSE POSITIVES"; guaranteed with a formal proof demonstration in "YRI_QVGE" paper: "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF : a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of [gui] software at runtime"; ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d]

Klaus is never clear–minded in terms of being humble because he even insulted myself in 1 of his email that I received at my email–address: "Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com".

MAY be because of his friendship, undeclared at the time I was under supervision of JAN PELESKA–cuon.

KLAUS havelund is part of the group of people who have been trying to cover myself with in-competencies by using my research-work results without mentioning my names or anything about source of their work.

FOR instance I have never at time seen a "FLEX–BISON" parser written by PELESKA or KLAUS havelund when I finished my compiler–translator [[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP](#)].

Let's observe what comes up in coming years from both deceptive white teacher–professors.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "January 14, 2026"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA — Continued – 1]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA:

1. Christopher-NGOSONG (MCGill, MCGill University
QUEBEC, CANADA (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) ["2012" – onward]

THIS guja came visit personally myself in my sublet basement apartment in MARKHAM-ontario around end of year 2012 as I was finishing my sabbatical-year-Internship with "J9-Java Just-IN-Time Compilation TEAM of VIJAY Sundaresan", at, IBM Toronto Software Laboratory (<https://www.ibm.ca>).

THIS male-female boy from BUEA-mutengene was sent to myself by an uncle paternal called "David Demo NOUNDOU", coming for a postdoctoral research stay in Canada after graduating his doctorate in agricultural studies from Germany.

I invited him to oversee my project in Yaounde for a small research institute combined with a technological entrepreneurship project after we had a dinner at a whittist-canadian Soccer-MMA-grill Bar somewhere in Markham, ON, Canada.

HE even manifested interest in co-creating this research technological institute by participating both in research & teaching as I can remember since we didn't communicate much after year 2012 together (NGOSONGK@yahoo.com).

"I could observe on the website of the University of BUEA (<https://>) lastly (2024) that HE became department chief for agricultural sciences. "

2. Dr.-B.Sc. Rodrigue Wankap Emmanuel MOGO—assassin (Rennes University,
FRANCE—assassin (<https://www.>)) ["2021" – onward]

THIS family MOGO where I could try to be investigated and cured for following diseases in their mansionian Hospital Clinic BUILDING in DLA-05 ème cité-des-palmiers;

- Disruption of well-function of my whole left leg after a fall on ground due to trying to send a small stone far away with my right hand;

A culprit-MD-anesthesiologist-trauma hired by YVES-MOGO, senior brother of my secondary school—ALFRED-Saker mate-colleague Assassin-WANKAP comes and tells me after around 30-minutes auscultation that MY left leg must be open-operated.

[I said I will think about this trying-to-open my nerves twice; THEN I DISAPPEAR from this assassination-begger-online MD-owona-rdpc-cpd.m-assassin funded Clinic.]

CANAL+ (<https://www.canalhorizon.com>) in France employs Rodrigue & YVES-mogo senior brother MD-assassin in HEXAGONE-assassin-slave-for-boyard & other TV-scam programs; EVEN sensual payments-only-viewing.

SISTER GHISLAINE-MD-mogo is kind-of CHRISTIAN-eyoum-rotarian-club in USA; Last news in MARYLAND-MA, a psy; IN cameroon she could get her secondary-school-final-certificate BAccalaureat via a payment to a certain deceased minister JOSEPH-owona-kono !

- HYPERGLYCEMIA because of not begin knowledgeable that CHRISTIAN-eyoum has tried to put into my blood via forced-in-taken pills and forced-in-taken injections;

The lady that is supposed to be a diabetes specialist medical doctor kind-of [EYOUM-christian-murderer] and that I don't remember names and / or whatsoever credentials; SHE gives myself insulin such at a high level that I stopped taking this promptly after 1 week, because I COULD sense that I DON'T HAVE ANY DIABETES !

3. Béatrice (IUT-Douala, University of Douala
Littoral Region, Cameroon (<https://www.>)) ["2025" – onward]

THIS super lady from my Grand-father neighborhood in Douala-NEW DEÏDO, is a professor at the Institute of Technology of the University of Douala since age 40 years old with a Doctorate-Ph.D. degree from China as I have heard from our common neighborhood.

HER husband that I have never met personally could help me with information on how to trace a prototype for YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET; As HE owns a super-chain of eye glasses from his China originating venture "BioLUXE".

ACADEMIA world worldwide contacts |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
 UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]
 [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA:**1. **MASTER–of–applied–science HYPOLithe–cuon-pd-TEKEU (IUC – INstitut UNIVERSitaire de la COTE, DOUALA (<https://www.myiuc.cm>), littoral REGION, CAMEROON)**

THIS megere-bamile tribe ROSE–sangnou, a genitor of my physical being went on to recommend myself to apply for a position at so called canadian–cooperation–institution IÛC.

I was 1st told I COULD earn "500 000 Xaf"; AFTER a prompt and passed successfully interview; WITHOUT any indication that I AM A socalled DR.–ING;

hypolithe–tekeu–pd–racist–tribal–bamileke–dschang–idiot offers myself "200 000 Xaf".

I COULD NOT say no period.

THIS idiot even put myself under a so–called professional master of engineering from his dirty and prostitution institute IÛC. JUNIOR–mbe; THIS junior–mbe–fosso is now as far I COULD OBServe in internet–world in socalled pragmatic-quebec-cuon-land-freedom–CANADA.

TODAY I can say that it is pretty much impossible for such a low–class institution to employ an ivy–level league USA graduate university ! GUIMEZAP himself culprit with all his children couldn't even get a doctorate degree outside of DSCHANG–village where they originate from in the OUEST.

This C.P.D.M–rosicrucian–sone institution also tries to destroy life of people together with SHANDA–tonme jean-claude of village BANGOU–batchingou in OUEST.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
 UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:**

1. **PROFESSOR thomas ndié djotio** (École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY (<https://www.polytechnique.cm>), CENTER REGION, CAMEROON)

This older than [myself] so called 'maître de conférence', English as "associate professor", was very kind to receive myself and to let me give him a short presentation of my professional and academic projects as "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.) (UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)":

- I. [YRI_QVGE](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [24.24] June 2022 – currently
- II. [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>) [?] MAR. 2015 – currently

I could identify "[Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié-Idiot]" through his online website located at: "<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>". I could also see his resume-online (~~<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>~~) that was asserting and presenting him as doctor-of-engineering graduated from the "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé" in year "2008".

ALL this afore mentioned websites were canceled by "THOMAS ndié djotio" it seems; For a more official resume (https://polytechnique.cm/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Biographie_Djotio-Ndie-Thomas.pdf).

HE 1st contested that I was a doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering because I didn't at that time of year 2022 asked for an official graduate transcript from the [UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, in Waterloo (Ontario, Canada)].

I could then obtain free-of-charge from "MRS. Nancy HEIDE" (nheide@uwaterloo.ca), at time of request As "Director of Student Services OF THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO", a certificate via electronic mail (Email) at my own request of "Official Graduate Transcript" that normally is charged \$20 CAD. I even had "Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié" copied-conform (cc) to my email since I am trying to get hired by "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé".

I CANNOT REMEMBER have failed any examination my entire candidacy of Doctor Ph.D., since I successfully graduated with "88%" as "Doctor-Ph.D. in electrical & computer Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)" on "December 20th, 2011"; with THESIS title:

["Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software"](#) [34]

I have appealed that I HAVE BEEN rejected from my [PhD research seminar] on "March 10th, 2015" by PATRICK lam that said 3 years later to myself when I was back in Canada to resign my canadian shit-citizenship, He didn't recall that he could foresee results from my program as pre-defined after we setup the PH.D. research seminar, together with my "PhD comprehensive examination committee members":

- A professor of age greater than 70 years old was the rapporteur:
- Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca
- Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca
- Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
- Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: lintan@purdue.edu

THE Ph.D. Dissertation Defense occurred in "January 2015" at PLG. IT was successfully approved by other following people among others:

["Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"](#) [34]

1. Peter Alan Burh, Ph.D. Alias ~~FABRICE siemeni-wilfried remp-canadian-armed-forces~~ Email: pabuhr@uwaterloo.ca
2. * Vijay Ganesh, Ph.D. Email: vganesh@gatech.edu
3. * Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@uwaterloo.ca
4. * Patrick Lam, Ph.D. Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
5. Magnus Madsen, Ph.D. Email: magnusm@cs.au.dk

ALL professors before mentioned marked with a "*" sign are collaborators in this project. Others approver were reviewers and were both ("Magnus, and Peter") present !

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR maïgari-idiot-secessionist (Former director, Cameroon-consulate in BRUssels-belgium (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "March-April 2015"]

2. PROFESSOR yves emvudu-cuon (INFORMATION SYSTEMS DIRECTOR deceased by now, Higher Education Ministry in Yaounde (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "August 2015"]

THIS idiot didn't even counseled me properly about the educational system employed in Cameroonian UNIVERSITIES. HE didn't even inquired on either my passed qualifications nor my credential documents; Since with his position, we could together query all required documents from an official position research in high education ministry for me.

HE just sent me to École Normale Supérieure so to meet a professor for MATHEMATICS that I forgot names and qualifications since I could never see him at ENS-yaounde.

THE other professor for mathematics I was supposed to meet, even though I AM foremost a computing engineer and developer was a MATHEMATICS professor at École Nationale Supérieure POLYTECHNIQUE de YAOUNDE. THIS man that seemed very kind but dangerous just gave me advise to put my publications of '<https://www.archive.org>'. "THIS older man than Yves-emvudu was a doctor from WEST-germany", whereas "YVES-emvudu was doctor from east-germany" !!!

ALSO, I was told by EMVUDU to apply for a teaching assistant position at SIANTOU-supérieur, and also Congo-CAMEROUN science university in a remote area of Cameroon I even don't remember the name.

"Merci au fainéant de Tonme de ne plus repasser où j'entre sur cette terre !!!"

[IT is exactly because of my "assassin-uncle-paternal-Laurent-TCHANDEU" that I went o search and encounter "YVES emvudu" of SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT A LA DEFENSE (sed) without knowing he might create a procedure to destroy me mentally because it might be inappropriate for a criminal like LAURENT to act directly on my body because of the blood-genetic-connection-with-his-own-kids !!!]

3. PROFESSOR bertin nyemb (École Normale Supérieure de Yaoundé – ENSY (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "May 2022"]

THIS very not humble professor for german language and cultural-ism is a very humble and not contestative person because he has always been trying to hijack myself as a member of DGRÉ.

I SUSPECT this idiot spy of biya-regime to have even sent false opinions of myself to german authorities at the UNIVERSITY-racist OF BREMEN after I MET HIM once again here in Yaounde in year 2022 !

SO this man of "Bassa"-tribe is at least 3 times recidivist in trying to check what makes someone like myself an ignorant by psychiatric methods like the ones [EYOUN-rotarian-CHRISTIAN] has been trying together with PR. DR. shanda-tonme, and EMVUDU.

I acknowledged at his request to be member of his stupid [Rotarian] organization so called PROvac ("PROMOTION des valeurs au Cameroun").

THIS has been more than 22 months now, he has never replied to any message about trying to computerized his membership list and cards using my humble open-source software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon–ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG (<https://>), WEST REGION, CAMEROON) [Around "September 2011", then around "September 2015"]

“ THIS sample ignorant on ”algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers” that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the ”ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN” (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON.“

“I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes–FRANCE in ”2004” when he visited ”GRENOBLE laboratory” with PROFESSOR tchindo–gilbert.“

“I tried to contact him again in "September–2011" because I HEARD from ”diplom–informatiker marcellin tally”, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.–INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?] " like our common age–class colleague ”diplom–informatiker oscar mourbare” from Ngaoundere–Cameroon. [Dr.–Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS–Bremen (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>). “

“HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone calls while I was in Cameroon ! “

2. PROFESSOR kolyang (University of MAROUA (<https://www.univ-maroua.cm/fr/node/76>), FAR NORTH REGION, CAMEROON) [”Around December 2015”]

“ I remember greeting him when entering an elevator as he was visiting Bremen while I was in my undergraduate level of education in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN in Germany where HE Graduated several years in front of myself.“

“HE didn’t answered at all and I felt he is not very comfortable with young cameroonian studying in BREMEN.“

“KOLYANG was then a DOKTOR–INGENIEUR (Dr.–Ing.), that could graduate from BREMEN with PROFESSOR BERND KRIEG BRÜCKNER (BKB) as DOKTOR–VATER (main principal PhD advisor).“

“Professor JAN peleska–cuon said I shall contact him in year 2016 when I was looking for a research position back in Cameroon 1st time, before returning into CANADA–shit to resign a CANDIAN–idiot–citizenship I acquired because I needed to travel via Europe without visa request at GERMAN embassy. I could succeed to send him an email at an email–address received from PELESKA–cuon, that I don’t remember; BUT I never got a return reply message at all.“

“WITH idiot–joseph–djoumessi that invited myself in his christian–rosicrucian–peg congregation CMCI–obili (<https://>); I heard from someone that was in academia at the UNIVERSITY OF YAOUNDE 1 that KOLYANG was not anymore in academia for working on research, But KOLYANG was doing agriculture !!! “

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "January 14, 2026"]

[*Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy, Color of origin payments, non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal, racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario, DEREK rayside idiot, INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING), racial systemic segregation]*

- I. ★ I Was very positively surprised to receive as POST–doctoral advisor, additionally to PATRICK lam; *An Ivy–league Stanford graduate called Dr. Vijay Ganesh* (<https://www.stanford.edu>).
- II. I came to this super MIT–graduate "*Patrick Lam, Ph.D.* (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)" because HE was from *Ivy–league–Massachusetts Institute of TEchnology MIT* (<https://www.csail.mit.edu>).
- III. *Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam* (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "*Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T* (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam :

1. *I spent 6 years under supervision of PATRICK-idiot-lam, (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=36fAXB4AAAAJ&hl=en>) without having at least 1 scientific paper published under his supervision anywhere in my visible and observable internet WORLD !*

[!!! I got this ([FSE–soqua 2006]) with only 2 years at THE university–racist-of-bremen.de !!!]

"THIS is the only time "PELESKA et al." could attend such a high–prestigious class–A conference in NORTH america of mine." (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/jp_papers_e.html#publications)

2. [JON EYOLFSON], an idiot that worked for PATRICK-lam as a MASTER student (M.ASC.) and then as a PH.D. candidate, **COULD COPY MY WORK** more intelligently & silently, and even 'EHHH' got a high paid position as an "**ASSISTANT PROFESSOR (teaching stream)**"; after 4 years at ~~UGLA~~–with–~~HARRY-XU~~ (<https://web.cs.ucla.edu/~harryxu>) as Postdoctoral fellow; AT THE ece–department OF **THE UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO** (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279–alexie–tcheuyap>), ontario, canada.
3. *Patrick recommended myself to IBM Toronto Software Lab manager "Dr. MARCEL mitran" after I told him I was looking for an internship just after my PhD COMPREHENSIVE EXAMINATION[32]; Before returning to University of Waterloo, ON.*
4. *Professor PATRICK lam gave myself a lot of presentation skills attitudes that I can today not all of them remember.*
5. Patrick sent me to several research academical venues through my doctoral Ph.D. studies at the University of Waterloo, ON:
- "*First Summer School on Formal Techniques*" (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) (2011);
 - *MITACS Ontario* (2012);
 - *PLDI – Programming Language Design and Implementation* (2009);
 - *IBM CASCON – IBM Centre for Advanced Studies Conference* (2010);
 - *ICSE – International Conference On Software Engineering* (2012).
6. Patrick gave myself 1st hand detailed explanations on static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" with help of his slides from *McGill University* (<https://www.mcgill.ca>).
7. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep my LaTeX document code straight and maxed 80 lines.*
8. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep reading papers as long as I don't really master them, before coming back to talk to him !*
9. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to dig very deep into researching and probing an idea before there is an excellent outcome out of it: THIS IS WHAT I APPLIED TO get my 1st implementation of my doctoral dissertation work YERITH–SAINT !*
10. Patrick gave me hints about contributing to open source projects by modifying their code source and reuse it for my research; I for instance applied this when creating Computer–Aided Software Engineering (CASE) tool *YERITH_QVGE*.
11. *PATRICK lam is also the one that permitted for myself to gain a TEACHING EXPERIENCE at the UNI–racist of Waterloo : I AM ALWAYS grateful to him for this great Experience at the UNIVERSITY–racist of WATERLOO in Ontarian CANADA.*
12. [PERSONALLY I am planing to pay him some money from my soft- and hard-ware revenue in the future.]

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "January 14, 2026"]

[Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy,

*Color of origin payments,
non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal,
racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario,
DEREK rayside idiot,
INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING),
racial systemic segregation]*

- I. Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam:

13. "PATRICK lam has never done a "program analysis by himself" as far as I have been working with either as his research assistant or as a scholar that could see this somewhere in a world. "

"They (PATRICK and FELIX) even attempted to remove my name from git repository (<https://>) history when "Divam Jain" left and PATRICK said to FELIX-fang to continue that research WITH me also as a supervisor under PATRICK-lam."

"AS far as I am knowledgeable, scientific conference and / or whatsoever papers that stem "from research work of Divam Jain", that I see as plagiarism since my name as a co–author has never been written, are existent because I am the only originator of this work; as a supervisor of DIVAM jain, at the beginning of his "Master of Mathematics (M.Math.)"; and this at request of dear PATRICK lam":

"Deceased idiot former dean of engineering "PEARL sullivan", [that I went to confront with facts about these plagiarisms], Sent by a black–idiot police officer from UWATERLOO racial–police services; Sent a british giant muscular idiot white–police–officer to arrest me illegally and very violently just at the ground level of the "Davis Centre BUILDING of racists." "

"BECAUSE i removed my clothes in front of surveillance digital cameras in a uw–office racial-police, Where the british–racist-police-from-scotland did tell me to sign papers that I DIDN'T EVEN had opportunity to read at all; THEY sent me in jail–custody to KITCHENER-waterloo criminal justice court. "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" let all investigations done and concluded that I HAD NEVER ASSAULTED this idiot police white-british office that charged myself with 'ASSAULT TO POLICE OFFICER' ! "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" told me she called "the office of THE president of the university of waterloo" to ask them to let myself defend my "Ph.D. degree dissertation"; BUT they told her with attorneys of law of the president of the university of waterloo: "What is a crown attorney doing in the office of president ?" "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" then on another did tell me that someone from the office of the president-idiot–racist of the university of waterloo; said that they have certain attitudes that are based on their local culture!

Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy

went on to harass the university of waterloo police ; ESPECIALLY (ambinns@uwpolice.ca); to say Like a HE-girl–pom–pom–shit that: "THIS black gay guy is so huge that he must be destroyed mentally !!!

this kind of race–sarah–landy MUST never be admitted anywhere else in this black world other than her anus....zizi.

[THIS happened in year 2018 as I WENT TO DESTROY my so-called—white-oblivier canadian–CACA–shit—citizenship–pegg–kkk.]

"I AM THE one who told to MRS. cuon-idiot–racist–white–quebec–tabawec—"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY", that THIS IS CALLED discrimination !"

- a. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

I. **Formal Training for occupying teaching positions** |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**TEACHING ASSISTANT training;**
CUT-1 - Certificate in University Teaching 1]

[Summary-PAGES]

1. **Training in ECE Department (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department):**

Before starting my 1st formal appointment as a teaching assistant at the University of Waterloo, ON, CANADA; In year 2009, I received a group training for graduate students of the ECE (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department).

2. **Passed QUALIFICATION interview to teach OBJECT-ORIENTED PROGRAMMING WITH JAVA:**

I SUCCESSFULLY passed a presentation slides lecture for qualification interviews OF 30 minutes added with "Q&A - Questions & Answers" session; to teach Object-Oriented Java Programming to 1st year students at THE university of Waterloo in year 2012.

NEVERTHELESS, I was not chosen as THE committee said: I QUOTE THEM: "Xavier might no be able to manage this very young age students in a class of 100 or more." I WAS AGED MYSELF 29 years old in year 2012 when this happened ! THX TO PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM

PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM is only 4 years older than myself. (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)

IT seems PATRICK and lin-tan-AGED-exactly as myself were trying to avoid a so-called-negger at a high paid position at UNIVERSITY-OF-WATERLOO. "Lin tan" is born 1983 like Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU ! (<https://cs.purdue.edu/lintan>)

THE class was given at the end to a seasoned professor named **SEBATIAN FISCHMEISTER** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>), that leads the **Embedded Research Group in ECE** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>).

3. **This was optional. CUT-1; Certificate in University Teaching – 1:**

"THE university of waterloo in ontario, Canada"; offers a formal training program in 4 certificates to qualify graduate students and / or whatsoever qualified persons for teaching at a UNIVERSITY.

I attended the level 1 certificate in 2010, but didn't pursue the last 3 levels because I felt I couldn't perform as fast as I wanted my doctoral research due to the high level of academic requirements due by researching in the "static code program analysis" area of research; At **WatForm (WATERLOO FORMAL METHODS group research)** (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>); led by "Prof. Dr. JOE atlee of the CS (Computer Science) Department" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>).

AFTER my free registration, at my own request and without asking PATRICK-idiot-lam; and attendance of all 1st level courses at "DAVEN-PORT library on main (200 UNIVERSITY AVENUE WEST) campus" of the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, I notice IT would be impossible to myself to finish my research in due time without issues with my doctoral advisor !!!

WE were around 10 in a sumptuous and luxurious carpeted room at kind of 3rd level in the main building !

ESPECIALLY added to the fact I WAS EARNING SUCH A LOW 999-CAD, so I HAD to TA-teaching assisting PATRICK lam.

THAT'S why I resigned.

[I EVEN feared PATRICK lam was trying to make myself sick because of the amount of stipend I HAD, compared to other students like JON eyolfson who also add other stipend from NSREC-CANADA !!!]

"I was under supervision of my doctoral Ph.D advisor Dr.-Ph.D. of Engineering PATRICK lam".

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[*TEACHING ASSISTANT training*]

- o SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '2' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses.
- o Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)
 1. Creating a "JUnit 4-tutorial" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14] and got it reviewed by PATRICK LAM; THIS is not a task PATRICK as instructor asked me to perform; I did this in my free time and put it as sample training material for students. – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 2. GOING in class to teach JUnit for exercise session – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 3. Creating SAMPLE solutions to assignments – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 4. MARKING ASSIGNMENT à la patrick lam – *"(+) Professor task level"*
I felt very improved for my teaching software technical testing skills.
- o Programming for Performance (ECE 459)
 1. *TAKING some time in my time of research for my ["PH.D. in electrical & Computer ENGINEERING"] to receive students visit at my office; and teach them what they couldn't understand either in class, and / or for the course material ! – *"(+) Professor task level"**

" Since my PH.D.-advisor patrick was the Director of Software Engineering study programs, I Think he thought I could replace him as a lecturer and he wanted to test these skills."
 2. "Really I didn't much like this course as taught by PATRICK because it was more a kind of programming course that wasn't very solid in mathematical and engineering foundations; Except for theories and histories on processor speed "MOORE-law" expansion and development ! "

"THIS was more to gain money because I was only earning \$999 Cad as a "master of science, PH.D. candidate" under supervision PATRICK-lam; coming from a middle level-paid good money position."

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Jan. 2012 – 10 MARCH 2015]

[TEACHING ASSISTANT training]

◦ SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '3' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses; '2' graduate ("Master", "PhD", "Ph.D.") level courses.

◦ Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)

1. Because of my resignation act in front of all committee members of my doctoral Ph.D. comprehensive examination and DISSERTATION COMMITTEE members;
I resigned !

◦ Compilers (ECE 351)

1. I did during my time in BREMEN, a course called ("Übersetzer GENERIERUNG mit LEX und YACC") that could be translated in English-white: "Compiler / TRanslator GENERation with LEX & YACc".
2. Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer programs as assigned for students in ECE 351 class of racist DEREK-GAYSIDE.

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650)

1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"

"deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "

"IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."

◦ Computer Networks (ECE 428)

1. "Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer client-server programs as assigned for students class of racist-idiot Mahesh-Rayside."

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651)

1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"

◦ [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)]

1. Working with "iranian in north-america", as being a black-afro-descendant is not recommended at ALL !

"JON eyolfson is a burglar incompetent GUJA that is not even capable of respecting an agreement of 2-weeks replacement for his office mate."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (TEACHING ASSISTANT — UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

- I. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
- 1.) [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D-advisor PATRICK].
 - 2.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of INSTRUCTOR "MAHESH rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Computer Networks (ECE 428)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"
 "THIS ignorant professor couldn't be even capable of clearly defining programming assignments, AS I had to tweak the Python code for automatically correct student code source from Gitlab-repositories created by a so called [PATRICK-lam]."
 [THIS ignorant didn't even know I was a perfect computer software developer since age 18 in Cameroon; as demonstrated by my professional record of employment in GERMANY that is at least trice more developed technologically than idiot CANADA.]
 - 3.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Derek rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Compilers (ECE 351)** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2012"
 "THIS idiot from massachusetts-gay institute of technology cannot even define what is mathematical relation WITHOUT saying: I quote him: 'a relation is like a table'... (<https://csail.mit.edu/sdg>)
 "I was kind of surprise that we MUST had to code source code to correct programmings assignments as "styles of programming for instance, comments, etc," MUST be also marked and more importantly advised, Especially from a performance confirmed seasoned software developer as myself: DR.-PH.D. of ENGINEERING XAVIER noumbissi noundou. (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) "
 "I was very surprised to see a [culprit called MATTHEW MA] that was Master of Applied Science of DEREK, COMING to myself with his mother and offer me "\$400 CAD so to code for his MASTER PROJECT in Computer Software Engineering from derek." "
 "Thinking that derek went to pay around \$30 000—CAD to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG, (<https://mathgenealogy.org>) so my free registration from "[PATRICK] AND rinard-martin; (<https://csail.mit.edu/~rinard>)" from 'PH.D.' onto 'ABD' be changed without any formal justification as specified [[here];] DEREK-GAYSIDE is only someone that hijacked to get a degree from renowned MIT." "
 - 4.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "LADAN":**
 - o **[C++ LABORATORY (ECE 250)]** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2014"
 "THIS in german so called 'HURE'-prostitute (<https://wikipedia.org>) Declares be a professor for software system.
 I cannot testify this as "her student MOHAMMAD HAMDAQA" was so ignorant and had a tremendous background in business but knew nothing on software system at all ! "
 "I spent hours talking to ladan via her idiot student from JORDAM-kingdom that seems to have even acquired a faculty position at so called "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL-qc-chien-tabawak-satan" (<https://www.polymtl.ca>) "
 - 5.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "deceased-Igor Ivkovic-idiot":**
 - o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650) Winter term (Jan-Apr.) "2013"
 1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"
 "deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "
 "IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."
 o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651) Spring term (May-Aug.) "2013"
 1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"
 - 6.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructors "Patrick LAM", and "LIN tan":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2015"
- II. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]
- 1.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Patrick LAM":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2010"
 "I AM THE one that creates the only sample solution to midterms. PATRICK is not very good at kind of creating technical solutions based on graph-theoretical foundations as for instance when creating equivalence class based test sequences solutions." — 📄
 "Sample TESTING material I Created." (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14]
 - o **Programming for Performance (ECE 459)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2011"
 I co-create with other teaching assistants such as [JON-eyolfson] solutions for assignments and / or midterms exams.
 I also receive students during predefined weekly time frame so to help them out with understanding of learning courses material.

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – APR. 2015]

[PROOF READING,
static code dataflow analysis,
SCALA,
JAVA, C++, *JUnit* testing,
research ideas talks and development,
computer programming teaching]

[Summary-PAGES]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. ["Matthew Ming Ma, M.ASc., Mechatronics, Engineering":]

- o How to configure a "developer" JAVA virtual machine under Ubuntu LINUX;
- o "I gave him contextual help in writing JAVA code for his Master of Applied Science project, under supervision of Derek Rayside".
- o HE then got a so called, at "**APPLE INC. LTD.**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) , **software in test developer** (<https://www.apple.com/jobs>) job;

That is why even a "**WIFI-connection**" to a laptop doesn't work with APPLE phones as I COULD experience myself in CAMEROON (a white phone paid for \$120 CAD).

2. ["DR. JON eyolfson, Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering":] (<https://www.jeyolfson.com>)

- o How to use efficiently and effectively double pointers in C++ function / method calling argument parameters;
- o "I gave him my full LaTeX doctoral Ph.D. thesis (ECE calls this a research proposal) document for helping him out with a template at his own request".

3. "Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering":

- o Thorough discussions and talks about his research ideas and on computer programming related topics (mostly on the "Watform LAB white-board").

4. "Divam Jain, M.Math., Computer Science", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Gave "DIVAM" sample code of my sample projects in JAVA about static code dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : A **unified approach to global program optimization** (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)"; As opposed for instance to static code dataflow analysis " à la **IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>)" from "**THOMAS-reps at the university of wisconsin-madison**" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) .

IBM provides WALA as library for working with IFDS framework. (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>)

- o Introduction and supervision on how to use **SOOT** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for JUNIT test case generation;
- o Declared "Master of Mathematics" title at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Detecting Test Clones with Static Analysis**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/7943>).
- o FOLLOWING plagiary by [zheng FELIX fang] and [PATRICK lam] originate from this seminal initial work where I contributed partly in code source writing:

A) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

5. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc., Electrical & Computer Engineering", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Overview of ["Divam Jain's"] previous work on SOOT and static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.;
- o "Declared MASTER OF APPLIED SCIENCE title" at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Test Clone Detection via Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/8831>);
- o FANG then got a position at MICROSOFT corporation in SEATTLE.
- o [1 scientific conference paper came out of this supervision-advising :]
 - a.) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. HELPIng black–descendant students from the UNIVERSITY of waterloo–racist–on |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Oct. 2009 – apr. 2015]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. "Amirhossein Vakili, Ph.D., Computer Science": (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili>)
 - o How to use MAKE;
 - o static dataflow analysis explanation.
 - o "1st at all functional programming with SCALA introduction".
2. **STUDENTS in cameroon association rowac. (<https://rowac.ca>) "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o **We at ROWAC (formerly CCAKW (Camerroonian Community Association in Kw)); Have invited ambassador-pd-idiot of Cameroon in OTTAWA (ontario) during summer 2014 if my thoughts are exact. THIS was during the soccer tournament we organized.**
 - o I presented and gave out certain documents I wrote about computer web software security vulnerabilities protection; AND measures to protect documents and computer–laptop during, after 1 general meeting evening around 06 : 00 PM.
 - o AFTER graduating, and came back into canada to resign an idiot-canadian citizenship acquired for travel-without-visa-purpose-only to EUROPE; I then discovered that several members of ROWAC were secret–servicess-agent of my assassin of paternal uncle LAURENT-tchandeu, PleniPOTENTIARY–minister:
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Vincent Nanga
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Innocent Tchigio
 - Dr.-PHARM. (M.Sc.) CHEONGWA wandzi-cheongwa@yahoo.com
3. "Godrick–chékété, Ph.D., French literature": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET "Godrick–chékété" via "YAW boakye-agyeman, ph.d. student in recreational studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA";
 - o Help in FINDING HIS way after his divorce from his spouse from BENIN (house searching, car fixing, etc.);
 - o HELP in looking for a financial loan at a Canadian bank.
4. "Eric Brefo–Mensah, Ph.D., Chemistry": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET Eric brefo-mensah via "CHIWANZA-kasanga";
 - o Help in proof reading his Master Thesis LaTeX document before his final submission in "year 2018".
5. Shirley Ddamba, "M.ASc. Civil Engineering": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET SHIRLEY at a bible study at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario.
6. Esther Lambert, "Ph.D., Geography, University of Toronto, 2017": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET ESTHER while she was cashier at ZEHRS–churchill–street.
 - o Help in proof reading her Master thesis for the department of geography;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario;
 - o ESTHER then pursue 1 year internship at ONTARIO green–belt institute; SHE then was admitted at the University of Toronto for "doctoral Ph.D. in GEOGRAPHY".

RESEARCH AND TEACHING ('PROFESSIONAL' TEACHING ASSISTANT – CONTINUED [2] - THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

I. *Professional Computer Engineers living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada":*

1. "A paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon" (<https://www.ank-technologies.com>).

r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou" who at 1st was an illegal migrant worker idiot in GB–great britain, a junior brother of my late father and genitor "Théodore Nounbissi, B.Sc., Electrical & Computer Engineering"; was a student in Information Technology student at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>), and graduated from there with a "Bachelor of Sciences (B.Sc.)".

"Demo" then obtained a position as "PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer" at "Canon LTD.", based in Germany - Osnabrück !

AT least trice (3 times) a month, I will receive a phone call from Germany requesting software programming and / or database technical help from this GUJA.

Each time I could solve his issues until HE stopped calling around August 2014, when I became a CANADIAN citizen, and when himself *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* went for a marital union with *r-"Astride Patibé"*; a nurse from Cameroon – Baham – BAFANG tribe.

r-"CÉLESTIN puene" is another (Food–processing) engineer from Cameroon that came to myself sent by "his natal village Babouantou" friend paternal uncle *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* .

HE came saying he needed help in buying a mechanical truck from the USA for his brother in cameroon who possessed a road construction society in YDE. *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* was first living in Frankfurt–GERMANY, before moving around 3 years after myself, into Canada [WASKAGANISH, qc; and "then Brampton, ON"].

" *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* and *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* are now member of [** +—"ROTARY CLUB INTERNATONAL"—+ **]; *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* was initiated by *r-"MBOUM, MD, Ph.D. (surgeon)"* from OSNABRÜCK–germany. I could say I do not want to be member when *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* asked for this in year 2014".

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[2016 - 2017]

A. "ENGINEER-ENSPY job seeker-gay PAUL:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I started teaching C programming to this young gay electrical engineer from CMCI-communauté missionnaire internationale chrétienne OBILI-obédience (CMCI-obili); While he was looking for employment for almost 6 years after graduating as BSc.-electrical engineer from "École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY"."

HE stopped attending just 2 weeks after starting participating in group meeting with the 2 following scientist-educators.

HE said his financing person wanted him to focus only in applying for positions in industry such as "BRASSERIES DU CAMEROUN", etc.

B. "Scientist-educator-cuon KITIO:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

He could find a position as computer science teacher in a secondary school in west cameroon !

C. "Scientist-educator-cuon CHARLES-eteme; now working at Yaounde GENERAL hospital:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

HIS father could find him soon a position at "Yaounde GENERAL hospital" where he was earning "250 000 Xaf" to start his career as a staff web developer.

TODAY, as I have been living in Cameroon for more than 6 years now full time; I believed he was a "SED"-anti gang; IT means someone hijacking people from west-region so to make them wretched as a political argument for PAUL-biya-idiot-CPDM-president.

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[Jan. 2021 – "January 14, 2026"]

A. "Engineer JEAN-PIERRE kamgain-idiot:"

This not professional computer science & computer engineering graduate, from "THE university of Yaounde 1", and from "IAI Cameroon"; was interested in various web-related tasks for searching employment within Douala.

1.) *plain code source "C" application programming interface development;*

A sample task was a development of a translator from "Qt 5 user interfaces (".ui" files)" onto "HTML5 pages";

2.) *JAVA servlet & apache tomcat server;*

A sample project using *APACHE-maven* (<https://>), for car maintenance & rental was developed both by myself and by JP-kamgain-culprit.

THIS sample exegete of "IAI Cameroon" wasn't capable of clearly write JAVA code as supposed with a "*bachelor of honours in Computer Software Engineering*" from both "IAI Cameroon"; And "University of Yaounde 1 (UY 1)".

3.) *PHP software development.*4.) *Training P.C.T.B-sarl employee on YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum:*

The culprit and school-mate NGADJEU-francis, refused to utilize JP because he went without asking advise from me recruit a so called call-girl-*IUC-cameroon* (<https://myiuc.com>).

5.) *Indicator for destruction of YVES-landry-galax-etoga in person:*

"JEAN-pierre kamgain has been trying to hijack my properties, both physically and emotionally because I COULD notify that HE was trying to spy my activities for "C.P.D.M party as NGADJEU-francis from P.C.T.B.-sarl did"“;

"Also JP-kamgain is the one that went to propose my ERP software system to BONTÉE sarl in AKWA-sud douala.“

6.) *[COPLATEC sarl is a psy-company for hijacking people at home:]*

OUR experience in Africa has been that at least "85% of societies" that are of type "SARL-ndlr-société à responsabilité limitée", 'GmbH (<https://WIKIPEDIAlinkDefinition.ORG>)-in-German-language';

"are companies for gay owned by soldiers FOR hijacking male and/or female consultants like myself that do not participate officially in lesbianism and homosexuality-zoophyte.“

ARLETTE-sibeuf seemed to be also member of SED.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (POSTDOCTORAL RESEARCHER AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
- [VIJAY-ganesh-chenapan, static dataflow taint analysis, dynamic binary program analysis, "INTEL-Pin", LLVM]
- A. Duties completed by Researcher [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noubissi Noundou:
1. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) ["Program Analysis for Web Apps"] "Grade 88%";
 - b.) ["Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)"] "Grade 88%".
 2. **SOLE and INDEPENDENT idea and research of development of static dataflow taint analysis with use of "compiler framework LLVM", for solving following complex software engineering problems:** [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) "Application Programming Interface (API) usage temporal rules";
"QUANTAMP.COM (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) uses for instance part of this research outcome to solve the problem of checking the conformance of BITCOIN-related-software-automated-contracts."
 - b.) "Detecting software security vulnerabilities" that endanger normal workflow, PER user-requirement elicitation, OR per software usability engineering: "BUFFER-OVERFLOW problems"; "SQL-injection problems"; "FORMAT-STRING attacks problems"; "AUTOMATIC test case and test data generation solution classes";
 - c.) "VERY PRECISE AND DETAILED collaboration with Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. VIJAY-ganesh";

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – 2014]

[Vijay-GANESH-from Ph.D.-at-stanford.edu (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>),
RESEARCH outcome plagiarism,
RESEARCH outcome hindrance,
"JAN-peleska-crédible; best-ever-professor of mine",
"student advising-MISSING paper",
static dataflow taint analysis,
LLVM (<https://llvm.org/racist-apple>)]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING.-PH.D.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

[Summary-PAGES]

1. EXPERIMENTATION WITH IFDS-FRAMEWORK FROM "REPS ET AL."

[JAN. 2013 – JUNE 2013]

I discovered the "IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) problems algorithm by THOMAS reps from UNIVERSITY-of-WISCONSIN-MADISON (<https://www.wisc.edu>), and from "Grammatech" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) ;

"I really enjoyed this graph-based software system interdependence algorithm; and accompanying free FOSS IBM-wala library (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>) ".

NEVERTHELESS I tried a personal implementation of the IFDS-framework using SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) & Java-SCALA with no successful binaries; BECAUSE the ideology for using "IBM-wala" was quite strange to my understanding !!!

I then renounced & abandoned to pursue and implement "The KILDALL-style" ("Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)") using C++ and a book-Advanced Compiler Design-from ...IBM author... !:

 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34]

2. [Work on "Dynamic PROGRAM Analysis with FRANK-tip" in course CS846] & [Work on "Software System Security by Software VERIFICATION"]

3. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D.-advisor PATRICK.]

[Sep. 2009 – Mar. 2015]

4. [Previous RESEARCH-development at AGBS—UNIVERSITY-OF-BREMEN.DE] :

"JAN peleska is my 1st best ever professor because I learned the best research skills from him while working in his research group in Germany-bremen-racist (E.g.: Unfortunately for myself; I couldn't get any professional-vocational student software developer position in a commercial company installed in Bremen.). (<https://informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>) "

[FSE-soqua 2006]

"More importantly we had a paper at Foundations OF Software Engineering research conference in 2006 while I was working on my "Diplom-Informatiker degree [Dipl.-Inf.] (Master of Science equivalent)" in his research group at the University-of-bremen.de (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>): "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) — ("VERIFIED.DE" (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>)) !!! "

5. Follow-up on research started by [DIVAM-jain] with following other fellow researchers at ECE:

- o DEREK-rayside
- o PATRICK-lam
- o REID-holmes
- o LIN-tan-idiot-gay-non-sense-girl
- o FELIX-fang
- o etc.

I started collaborating with DIVAM jain because PATRICK-lam sent DIVAM jain to me for learning about static dataflow code analysis using SOOT.

"WHEN divam-jain-racist left, I pursue this same research with FELIX fang, and then with researchers afore-mentioned in office of the director of software engineering program PATRICK-lam; Where we attended to group collaborative meetings."

THEN he was more about the problem itself; IN this occasion, how to automatically generate "JUnit test suites test cases" based on static code dataflow analysis of unit test code of the analyzed projects.

"A benchmark of "at least 100 open source JAVA libraries" was used to test these projects JUnit test code.

From this research came out at least 11 conference peer-reviewed papers and some journal articles, AND i wasn't mentioned as a co-author either:

- 1.) "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2014 – 2018]

["sodomite-peggish-JULIA-rubin-AT-UNIVERSITY-of-british-columbia-CANADIAN-rate-gay-Israelite-ANTI-JESUS-OF-Nazareth",
dynamic binary program analysis,
"INTEL-Pin"]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

4. **DEVELOPMENT of certain features of PHP-JAVA-judo-quebec web application for management of club members:**

[JUNE 2014 – NOV. 2014]

THE research paid-provision was around "1000 \$CAD" a month, which was very insignificant because of all the technologies working together such as: PHP, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), etc.

5. **PATRICK-idiot lam research idea**, and personal sole development of a dynamic binary program analysis for moving "PROGRAM-POINT" during runtime execution based on certain loop-condition; USING "INTEL-Pin" :

[SEP. 2014 – OCT. 2014]

PATRICK-idiot lam didn't allow myself to complete the program under his sole supervision.

I WASN'T really happy because he interrupted my main project on static taint dataflow analysis; HE didn't tell me anything about any outcome, and/or later done publication or whatsoever.

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

6. **!!-sodomite-peggish-woman-attention-patrick-JULIA-rubin-ece-british columbia-faineant-chien-tabaweak-canaoe** said she will continue research with myself at **UBC** (<https://www.ece.ubc.ca/mjulia>) so I WILL GRADUATE as a "PH.D." !

[2018]

" IT was dereak-gayside that said I SHOULD TRY TO apply somewhere else than university-racist-of-waterloo since they-idiot-of-lam could call the police to arrest myself ILLEGALLY on waterloo dirty-racket-pd-cuon-tabaweak-quebec-salaud main campus !!! "

PLEASE FOLK that may think a white-racist Gives you a residence permit to allow yourself to fulfill your peace dreams; IT'S NOT THE CASE.

" THE WHITE-GAY-DAY-nancy-racist is only trying to reduce the speed of perfectionism and development of your country of origin by harassing you there with corrupt-gay authorities so you will try to go outside. "

" All these mansory-free-rotary-club-ETC.; CATHOLIC-gay-church is only a way to hijack your life in anti-christ-of-negger-jesus-of-nazareth like myself I HAVE BEEN experiencing for 7 years in ontarian-CANADA-shit-people-race. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[Algorithms dis-pension,
finite automaton theories,
"Year 2010 report",
"Year 2011 report",
"1st summer school on formal techniques",
[IDIOT-black-afro-descendant Sandy BEIDU from ghanaian land]]

I. Duties completed by Research Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.; MSc)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my advisor-PH.,D. PATRICK].
2. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [SEP. 2009 – DEC 2011]
 - a.) ["First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"] "participated with certificate";
 - b.) ["Computer-Aided Verification-racist-nancy"] "Grade 90%";
 - c.) ["Advanced Compiler Design-cuon-plagiarism-of-jon"] "Grade 86%".

3. I went to **menlo-racist-college** (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) in California, USA, to the 1st summer school on formal techniques from "May 22, 2011" until "May 27, 2011"; under a recommendation-required (from professor doctor **NANCY-idiot-day** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>)).

I was accompanied by the GHANAIAN called SANDY-cuon-beidu supposed to be a very famous computer scientist originating from my home continent AFRICA.

[THIS hideous ignorant fellow, from a very poor material background arrived at the university of waterloo "WatForm-waterloo formal methods" in year 2010 if I have good memories; Saying to the world he is a JESUS-christian;]

This kind of black-afro-descendant is so disgusting that I believed that the racist **JO-atlee-his-research-advisor** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>) went to pick him so to dishonest myself in front of the extremely dominant ["iranian female population in ECE graduate student folks"] !

HE even thought that I RENTED my "ford fusion" to tell them (Sandy-idiot-day, and a lady from long-island-black-prostitute) that I AM A WELL-TO-DO-MAN in front of them.

[I JUST remembered my BUSINESS-trip while I WAS TRAVELING for SIEMENS-medical-solutions-erlangen IN concord-ca-usa; And I KNEW I NEEDED to be mobile; THAT's why I RENTED A luxurious "ford fusion" from my savings account from my HARD-job at SIEMENS.]

[SANDY-idiot-poor-man-in-all-system thought when the other ghanaian idiot-story-teller-Dr-PhD-ERIC-brefomensah brought me to his travesty-basement-slot in WATERLOO, in ontario, 2018; THAT i needed some drink from him !]

[PLEASE folk from basement places in GHANA; Cameroon don't need this kind of down-treatment as CAMEROON is way more advanced as demonstrated ONLY by me !!!!!!!]

4. I have worked on topic "temporal property verification in plugin-based software"; and created a computer-Libreoffice-Impress presentation slides for the **IBM workshop CASCON 2010-CDP-compiler-...** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); [IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

THIS research as "**Master Of Science**" (so called "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.-INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?]") led to my "**Doctoral Thesis / PhD comprehensive examination**" released research technical document : "**Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)

5. I have created sample program static code analyzes using the **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) so to acquire skills in static code program analysis.

A very short introduction: " " (<https://>) to SOOT framework by

6. I HAVE IMPROVED my algorithm design skills by implementing popular algorithms using the Following ALGORITHM POPULAR BOOKS:

- A. **Computer Systems: A PROGRAMMER'S PERSPECTIVE, 2nd edition ("ISBN 13 : 978 - 0 - 13 - 610804 - 7")**; by "**BYANT**"-racist & "**O'HALLARON**"-racist-sexist;
- B. **Introduction to Algorithms-Isbn: " "**; by **THOMAS cormen** (https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crd=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjojMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVFed1BzcV0qunH6HMFdUvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWVHVsmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABi7cszQqi1XxeWBu8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gw1drRqhl2Alh8huCTZ2PeIofPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fio1k8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWazLVBUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1).

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANCE FROM FOLK-IDIDIOT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**"JOHN HOPCROFT"**, **"samaneh navabpour-racist-extreme"**, **"1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"**, **LLVM**, **SOOT**]

I. **People from [the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] whom I got academic help:**

1. "AAKARSH nair, M.ASc., Computer ENGINEERING, 2009"

- "AAKARSH nair was the 1st student of DEAR-idiot PATRICK lam I have ever met.

HE is the 1st one to give me sample code on static dataflow analysis with "JAVA-SOOT framework (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)" à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" "

2. "NANCY day"

- "Professor DAY wrote a very good and tremendous recommendation that was used to admit myself to [**"First Summer School on Formal Techniques"**] (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>), by THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA; in year 2011".

3. "Samaneh Navabpour, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering"

- SAM gave me 1st explanations about LLVM by using her previous work for **a paper-RITHM** (<https://uwaterloo.ca/embedded-software-group/sites/default/files/uploads/documents/main.pdf>) she worked on in SEBASTIAN fischmeister embedded computer research group; She confessed not having exactly applied a static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)";

BUT used only control flow graph related features to perform static dataflow analysis; this is NOT exactly **CLANG** (<https://clang.llvm.org>).

4. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem>)

- NOMAIR was the 1st person apart from Patrick, my doctoral Ph.D. advisor that took so much time to help me understand and proof read my **doctoral Ph.D. Thesis** ([HTTPS://WWW.SEMANTICSCSCHOLAR.ORG/PAPER/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33)) [32];
- NOMAIR helped myself in understanding the intricacies of a context-sensitive static parametric analysis by explaining from his **research paper Interacting objects ...** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem/papers/oops1a08PhD.pdf>).

5. **Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>)

- Professor Lhoták accepted to review my **YERITH-SAINT** algorithm thoroughly.
- Ondřej was very kind to help me with source code of 1 of his 1st **LLVM** dataflow analysis, before I started my own.

6. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. JOHN hopcroft-SEXIST, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.cornell.edu/jeh/>)

- Explanation, at my email request, and very promptly and generously about an algorithm in his compiler book.

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (GRADUATE INTERN AT INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS MACHINERY (IBM))

1. Perform duties assigned by big manager and PATRICK doyle in JAVA-J9 JUST-IN-TIME OPTIMIZATION team (, located in Markham-ONTARIO-canada); (advised by Prof. VIJAY sundaresan, M.Sc. (MCGILL, QC, CANADA) | Patrick Doyle, (M.ASc., UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, Ontario, CANADA))) |
IBM TORONTO-IDIOT SOFTWARE LAB. [01/2012 – 08/2012]

[AS canadian-idiot permanent resident;

Automated Software TESTING with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIFY (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verify>),

Program OPTIMIZATION (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), "Clark-salaud Verbrugge, Ph.D. (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>)";

JVM – JAVA virtual machines, IBM – WEBSPPHERE, Managers are really understandable,

DOCTOR-ENGINEER,

Racism from restaurant in india-bangalore-IBM-gay]

[Summary Of D.ENG. [DR.-ING. in "French language"] (PH.D.) Review Research-PAGES]

I. Comfort excellent for work research at IBM:

1. I was working into a brown cubicle and had so much freedom in work that I WAS SOMETIMES afraid that I AM NOT PERFORMING well.

BUT when I STARTED working closely more with VIJAY I felt so busy that I WAS DREAMING of going home around 03:00PM in evening;

IN total, IBM in MARKHAM offers very good working and research conditions for his employees, *even better than my previous 1st full-time job as JUNIOR-SOFTWARE-DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS in Erlangen, BAVARIA, GERMANY !!!*

SIEMENS MEDical solutions was really good in Erlangen; But i didn't like seeing "BOSS gerhard" watching his arm watch any 2 minutes to make sure we only had 45 minutes lunch-break; "Secretary "gudrun" is also really helpful and smiling ! "

II. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. **Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, MSc. – from Bangalore, INDIA**

THIS daemon of work was so kind that I ONLY FEEL I have satisfy him as much as he wanted and could !!!

HE is very attracted to good and fast male workers; because female workers would only try to hijack his time for a snack !!!

I am very proud of having work with such an amazing scientist at all !!!

ALSO the team managers, including the chinese woman, were very kind to myself as the only male afro-descendant from AFRICA !!!

2. **Patrick idiot Doyle, M.ASc. – from Ireland-CANADA**

THIS ignorant as a teacher and / or mentor couldn't even pick myself at time when I Was waiting for my hiring team for the internship to come at my encounter in the biggest room where we all intern were awaiting 1st day of internship.

III. Duties of Graduate INTERN [Doctor of Engineering] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. **FIX SOFTWARE TESTING FEATURE AUTOMATION USING BASH SCRIPTS**

I felt a lot better at this task because I could feel having a positive impact on the project team lead by manager that I don't remember names and academic titles.

ALSO vijay sundaresan wasn't very disgusting as people working in the restaurant, that always served myself BURNed food, especially pagan-an-food.

Vijay sundaresan is a very talented software lead and developer that I could ever see in my career; I VERY MUCH LIKED THE INTERACTIONS with him compared to PATRICK doyle.

TODAY I FEEL there are 2 factors that helped:

- A. **MCGILL university** (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) graduates in Computing Sciences are very much talented compared to other students from ONTARIO.
B. VIJAY-sundaresan was born also outside of Canada-racist-systemic like my recruiting manager that I forgot about names;

2. **MAINTAIN CERTAIN DAYS BUG DATABASE**

AT all not very difficult, since I WAS USED TO use CHARMNT in my previous full-time job at Siemens Medical Solutions in Erlangen, BAVARIA, germany.

3. **ATTEND TO COURSES AT IBM TORONTO-IDIOT LABORATORY GIVEN BY "pr. prof. dr.-ing. clark-salaud verbrugge" FROM MCGILL.ca** (<https://mcgill.ca>) "on Creating Optimizations for Compilers"

4. **SOLVE AS MANY AS BUGS IN COMPILER OPTIMIZATION CODE SOURCE IN C++**

Coming from a program analysis research team, that performed more static code analysis using framework like S00T, and LLVM; I WAS KIND OF not performing very well at this task at all because of the very applied and complicated data structures; Especially because PATRICK-indigeneous-iranian-irish-from-british-kingdom never even got me to a small talk for explaining me briefly what was the governing ideas leading the development team in MARKHAM.

INSTEAD, i only received so many documents that I had to read and detect understand myself.

Earning as much as 3 000 \$CAD monthly, I FELT SO BAD that I Went to complain to the manager; a very kind person; that allowed then myself to work with the team lead VIJAY sundaresan...

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' (WEB DEVELOPMENT INTERNSHIP AT BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN – HTML, CSS, PHP, JSP – CODE SOURCE FOR a Content Management System – as an EVENT MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE ONLINE racist (advised by MARTIN ...) |

BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST, BREMEN, GERMANY-RACIST-PEGGIST

— March. 2004 —

[[WEB software development with PHP, CSS],

Peggist-racist colleague Martin...,

[JSP, HTML5,]

Samsung CONTACT Server on Redhat LINUX]

I. Duties of Web Development Intern [Vordiplom-B.Sc candidate (In Computer Science)] Xavier Noundou:

1. *Before attending and applying for this position; I attended courses workshops on Web development using MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP during around 1 semester (4 months) at the Department of Computer Science ("FACHBEREICH 3) of the University of Bremen. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)*
2. *Create configuration in Redhat LINUX for the Samsung Contact Server system.*
3. *Create HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP combined code into a Content Management System for managing Event that are to be published on a specific date on the Bremen4u-Gmbh website.*
4. Martin was always having a very bad mouth-breath because of smoking cigarette all day together with drinking black dark coffee with no milk at all.
5. THIS was a very disgusting place to work as a new person living in Germany; also young girls from secondary school as internship workers; With almost no sense on respecting black african race at ALL !

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVISOR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[NOV. 2007 – July 2009]

[C++,
 Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),
 Software Integration Testing [21],
 UNDER german-traveler work-permit;
 ROBOTEK-linac,
 Radiation Therapy Treatment,
 IMRT beam treatment,
 TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

1. Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer) [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. "MARVELOUS TRAVEL to Concord, CALIFORNIA, USA : my greatest and high paid experience of work since I was given birth in 1983 !!! — 5 000 EUROS

THANK you boss gerhard-idiot-SENG !!!!!!! "

2. "Participation in cancer treatment (IMRT) radiation therapy training, and all other software development related training for this position as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER."
3. "C++ coding and defects fixing of DMIP control communication protocol as heart of Software component TXSUPERVISOR: around 110 000 Lines of code (SLOC)."
4. *Conception & Development of an automated software integration test infrastructure:*
 - a. Cygwin bash-scripting
 - b. Microsoft COM component as [CORBA] agent communication used
5. Software Integration testing using "IBM Purify Plus".
 (COMPETITOR FROM "PR. PROF. DR-ING. Xavier noumbissi Noundou":
 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b]);
 git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> ;
6. "DMIP Control Console" device as user control management for simulating radiation therapy linear accelerator "SIEMENS Linac Artiste" in our laboratory in Erlangen ground-base;
7. Focal entry point of all bugs of "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software. INVESTIGATION, and then redistribution, according to defect type, to an appropriate sub-team VIA team-lead "Gehard Seng".
8. Support technical in writing software user manual with software testers.
9. Support technical with software testers in using "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
10. Phone support technical in TROUBLESHOOTING "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
11. Maintenance of communication development support from software developers from Siemens Concord in California, USA.
12. Maintaining using "MS office" of design documents of TXSUPERVISOR and "DMIP control communication protocol"; based on "FSM state machine theory": United States of America's FDA (U.S.A – Federal Drug and Administration), as well as CE (European Community) had to review the digitally signed documents; stored in "SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)".
13. Assisting "DARIO meraviglia" in selection of interns based on their qualification as reported on their CV – resume.
14. Advising of 2 software testing maintenance part-time employees:
 1. 1 from Germany, from The University of Bamberg (Bayern, Germany);
 2. 1 as an intern, from India.
15. "VMWare" (<https://www.vmware.com>) as debugging image creator development tool.
16. "MS Windows 2000", as well as, "MS Windows NT", as software development operating systems platforms.
17. "Visual Studio C++" as IDE;
18. "IBM Rational ClearCase" as Code BASE source management control software used;
19. "IBM CharmNT" as bug management platform used;
20. [LEGAL requirement summary experience with HANDLING of Design Documents Functional Specification for Medical Software according to "CE" ; "FDA".]

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[11/2007 – 07/2009]

[C++,

Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),

Software Integration Testing [21],

UNDER german-traveler work-permit;

ROBOTER-linac,

Radiation Therapy Treatment,

IMRT beam treatment,

TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

I. ISSUES – Problems with some colleagues:

1. Gerhard Seng and Dario Meraviglia told myself I should be promoted to the position of Dario as "technical lead of the software module component TXSUPERVISOR (only 1 developer)" if I could succeed in gaining a full-time permanent contract after an initial successful 6 months period of work under direct leadership of DARIO MERAUVIGLIA.

"AFTER SUCCEEDING the trial period of 6 months, I obtain a change of software developer contract from a full-time limited contract to a full-time permanent contract with "Siemens Medical Solutions"."

"HOWEVER after an additional 15 months of work, I am not anymore promoted to a higher level position of Technical Lead."

"This is why I decide to make the effort to go back to academia and pursue [a doctoral Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering (Computer Software)] at the University of Waterloo, in ONTARIO, CANADA; WITH [Dr.-PhD patrick lam as academic adviser] !! "

2. "Merlin Tonka from Cameroon" is calling me even before my first day at job in Erlangen to tell me he hopes I will be able to perform well and thus keep my job beyond the 1st 6 months period of try: He tells myself HE got my email from boss "Gehrrard Seng";

"From NORTH of GERMANY WHERE I STUDIED AND LIVED for almost 6 years before being recruited and before moving to Fürth-BAVARIA-Germany, this is not "SACK-ARBEIT": I.E. one shall not mixed private life affairs with business matters at all: THIS IS HOW I LEARNED IT in HAMBURG, and BREMEN ! "

3. "Merlin Tonka" one day follows myself in metro and bus so to tell me that HE shall be promoted as a team of a new testing and developers team, And that he shall be my manager.

" I was wondering silently (because very young in year 2008 with only 23.5) years old ("Merlin Tonka was at least 40 years old in front of my age"), that someone less qualified than myself and currently employed as only a software tester, which is a lower level required qualification; Put aside you are PhD-doctor-of-engineering; and that was recruited only 1 week before my personal recruitment, will become my manager by telling it to me only in streets ! "

"THE italian master of science-level engineer Dario Meraviglia is my technical lead, followed by Gerhard Seng, our common teal lead at Syngo-RTT-Therapist-SW-Realize team" !

4. After leaving "Siemens Medical Solutions" legally by resigning with a signed letter 3 months before leaving my IG-METAL-tariff-vertrag employment in year 2009; I sent a letter to thank "MERLIN TONKA" for the positive professional collaboration I had with him as a fellow cameroonian, despite a lot of troubles we had; I sent this letter only around 1 month after starting studying in Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.

"THE answer from "Merlin Tonka" is so negative minded and outspoken that I need to reply to tell him truth about not trying again to tell me he is superior to myself; I.e. Merlin tries in a letter to tell me I could not perform well in software developer job, that's why I resigned !!! "

"Only smelling the same dirty "grey-shirt" MERLIN was wearing almost every day was not comfortable because he was sitting just opposite side of my office-desk ! "

"I today in year 2024 can remark as a citizen living inside CAMEROON that killer from governmental agency [DGRE wear generally grey-shirts !]"

"UDM-université des montagnes (<https://WIKIPEDIA.ORG-racist>) later on in year 2009 invited DGRE-activist MERLIN tonka through THE KILLER OF MY GENITOR théodore noumbissi; So called [HUGUES NTOMANI tiako], which is sleeping with genitor ROSE sangnou so to perform crimes on my person even now in year 2024 ! "

"WHITE-blond supremacist slave-maker; PLEASE stop to hijack black afro-descendants that are talented. TILO. MÜCKE. DARIO. MERAUVIGLIA. MERLIN. TONKA ! "

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING – CONTINUED (1) (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |
SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY [11/2007 – 07/2009]

III Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at Siemens Medical Solutions:

1. **"paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon".**

Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug".

[Help in proof reading his Bachelor–Thesis.]

IV Students living in Canada I helped during vacation time by my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji":

1. Co–roommate of Théodore Wandji at 5850 Rue Souart, #7, H3S 2E8, Quebec, Montreal, CANADA:

"Basser from Syria":

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Master of Applied Sciences (M.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

2. **"Fabrice TCHOUMI from Cameroon":**

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Bachelor of Applied Sciences (B.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

V Software Development Colleagues were:

1. Senior Software Developer "MAMIDI" from INDIA.
2. Senior Software Developer "Detlef Kendelbacker" (Contractor) from Bayern–Germany.
3. Team Lead "Gerhard seng" from Bayern–Germany.
4. Software Architect Balakrishnan; from India.
5. Software–Engineer [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] Xavier Noumbissi NOUNDOU; from Cameroon.
6. Technical Lead DESIREE görisen; from Bayern–Germany.
7. Technical Lead [Dr.] GANESH gopalakrishnan; from India.
8. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Johannes Bauer; from Bayern–Germany.
9. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Martin Maier; from Bayern–Germany.
10. Technical Lead [Ing., Polytechnico Di Milano] Dario Meraviglia; from Italy.

VI Software Testing Colleagues were:

1. Test Manager [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] "TILO mücke"; from Germany.
2. Software Tester "Merlin Tonka, M.Sc. (Computational Engineering, University of Erlangen–Nürnberg, Germany)" from Bagangte, Cameroon–French–Island
3. Software Tester "Suschma" from India
4. Software Tester "Swapnil, Bachelor (Mechanical Engineering)" from India
5. Software Tester "Dhananjay" from India

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (STUDENT SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT GEWETE GMBH)

1. CREATE SQL databases JAVA Servlet programs and C++ communication protocol software programs (advised by SVEN KAMRATH | JENS MÖLLER) | BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH (NOW GEWETE GMBH), GERMANY [03/2005 – 04/2007]

[CE – EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en), UNDER german-traveler student part-time-work-permit, C++, MAKE, "JSWING", Hibernate, JAVA, Servlets, apache ANT, Eclipse IDE, XML (e.g: JAXP library), Qt, SQL, Vending machines, Communication protocol – [debugging at YERITH R&D Now !](#)]

I. APPLICATION FOR A STUDENT DEVELOPER POSITION AT "BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH":

I stumble on this offered position while I WAS LOOKING FOR A NEW DEVELOPER position part-time when I KNEW MY PROJECT with "PROF. DR. RER. POL. KLAUS–racist bönkost" would not be renewed.

THE position was advertised on a website for student jobs of the TUHH (<https://www.tuhh.de>).

II. Duties of Student Software Developer [Vordiplom in Informatik] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project development, and its installer Graphical User Interface (GUI) program developed using "JSWING" ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swing_\(Java\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swing_(Java))) JAVA library technology."
2. "MESO": "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing follower project development."
The novelty in this follower project is that I INTRODUCED, based on my research skills, acquired in BREMEN, an object–relational database object mapper called "**Hibernate**" (<https://www.hibernate.org>); THIS was to be capable of giving newer customers ORACLE 9i functionalities from "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project" !!!
3. "C++ coding of a "Sap-ABAP protocol communication interface" to put "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" vending machines in communication with vending machine of Hamburg public library that used "BIBLIOTHECA software library".
4. "C++ coding of SIPv2 control communication protocol (https://handwiki.org/wiki/Standard_Interchange_Protocol)."
5. Migration from "ORACLE 9i database tables" onto "MySQL database tables" for the MESO project (follower of LaDIVA software project); I used following technologies:
 - a. BASH–scripting
 - b. AWK scripting language.

III. Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "Bergmann Automaten GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg":

1. "**paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon**".
Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>).
"Demo" then obtained by "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" a position as "Bachelor student working on its thesis, project–based":
 - a. I talked to "Mister Sven Kamrath of this request", by "Mister Demo Noundou", of a Bachelor Thesis Project.
 - b. HE ("DEMO") then refused a final offer as full–time "JAVA software developer" because he felt he couldn't perform well in a "JAVA plain object (JPO)" software development environment.
 - c. "[2008] Demo Noundou, B.Sc." then accepted a position at "Canon Ltd. as PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer in Osnabrück; HE can–also wear title Dipl.–Ing. (FH).".
 - d. " [2015] DEMO NOUNDOU is now at his own company in web development & training in HAMBURG. (<https://ank-technologies.com>) "
 - e. " [2024] DEMO is also a consultant in african universities curriculum development based in KENYA, and others. NO ONE CAN BE A PROPHET IN HIS HOME–YAOUNDE. (<https://SAINTEBIBLE.COM/jesusquoteTOCHECK>) "

"DEMO NOUNDOU, B.Sc." also had a "grade of (10.5/20)" which is not a very good grade to enter such position as the one I GOT LATER ON AT siemens medical solutions; A "GRADE OF 14.5/20" is required to apply for any entry level position at ["SIEMENS AG GERMANY–low–payer"].

IV. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. *Herr Sven Kamrath was very angry at myself 1 day during my stay in Rellingen to talk about an ongoing project 'LaDIVA XML Servlet Parser Server' !
"He found a subtle bug that I then fixed the same day."*

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (WEB-HTML-CSS DEVELOPER AT ZENTRUM FÜR MULTIMEDIA IN DER LEHRE (ZMML))

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN websites – www.s-hb.de (<https://www.s-hb.de>) mainly – for KLAUS-racist-extreme BÖNKOST (advised by PROF. DR. RER. POL. criminal Klaus Bönkost) |
 ZMML-UNIVERSITY-RACIST-SEXIST OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY [Feb. 2003 – Feb. 2005]

[UNDER german-traveler student work-permit;
 'dunklefarbige mitarbeiter xavier aus Afrika',
 HTML5,
 CSS,
 "photoshop",
 IMAGE-dateien,
 FADRI,
 SVEN schu]

I. Duties of WERKSTUDENT [candidate vordiplom in INFORMATIK] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "Reception, and implementation, of design documents (e.g.: "photoshop images", etc.) from FADRI-racist."
2. ["Programming of HTML5, CSS web pages."];

[Participated 1-month to a training internship at Bremen4u-GmbH.]

3. "Programming of RAD-server programs with Graphical User Interfaces (GUI); With programming support of Sven-schu-nazi."

"RAD-server programming language (<https://wikipedia.org...>) is a sample VISUAL BASIC dialect domain specific language. "

4. "Participation in weekly meeting on development of websites and test facilities for students in economia."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – UNI-RACIST BREMEN

1. CREATE A MODEL-BASED TESTING FRAMEWORK TO AUTOMATICALLY GENERATE STATECHART MODEL TEST CASES FOR REACTIVE SYSTEM SOFTWARE ([advised by Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. Jan Peleska]) |
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY — "NOT fully described curriculum by myself" [09/2002 – 05/2007]
- a. "Diplom-Informatiker" : "MASTER 2" IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS (DIPLOMARBEIT): "STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (GRADE 18/20)"; as part work for the FSE-SOQUA (2006) Research Conference Proceedings full research paper: "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (VERIFIED.DE), AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [12/2006 – 05/2007]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, reactive system, UML 2.0, HybridUML profile, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), uniformly distributed statistical test case generation, MBT-RT-Tester, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF as of now a doctor (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .]
- Algorithms developed by myself for this 'Master of Science research-based Thesis ("Diplomarbeit" in German)' (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html) [1a], based on 'Prof. Dr. Marie-Claude Gaudelle' research outcome, as a mathematician in France, are used in the RT-Tester tool of the verification and validation research and German society "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) .
- b. C++ CODE GENERATION PLUGIN IMPLEMENTATION WITHIN CASE tool "Borland-Together", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2006 – 02/2007]
- [reactive system, UML 2.0, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), C++ code generation, MBT-RT-Tester]
- Our algorithms are for the "TDIOHS: Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System" (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) state diagram formalism, that could be visualized by [statecharts](#) for instance using a 'Verified Systems International GmbH plug-in' for 'Borland-Together 6' (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Micro_Focus_Together).
- c. "Research Master in Computer Science Software 2-Years PROJECT" : CogAG project : "Robot "Arni" usage in framework of creating mapping recognition algorithms and cartography.", Cognitive Systems Group (CoSy), "Christian Freksa as Project creator and lead", CoSy – University of Bremen, GERMANY [01/2005 – 03/2007]
- [Cognition, Cartography, RFID-tag technology, TEXT-TO-SPEECH (<https://>), Robot control, sensor, actuator, Debian Linux, C++, Qt, systemic racism]
- "My personal contributions were mostly in creating QT user interfaces code for controlling the virtual shop and the roboter "ARNI". I also was very much implicated in Software Engineering round-about code such as blackbox code for keeping a BB-blackboard software architecture between our software components and the MySQL database tables used to share some of the data between components of the software system."
- "I also worked on cognitive cartography algorithms using C/C++, together with "ALINA, Christian, Sasha, and SERDAR". I was moving the robot for scanning RFID sensors stapled onto our real test grocery store, and then trying to find a way for the robot-ARNI based on customer commands on the robot that were at entrance to help them find their way into the real test grocery store. I used text-to-speech technology to talk with robot-ARNI to customers. "
- I was also involved in:
1. HELPING in general project organization for instance:
 - A. Writing project meeting minutes.
 - B. Looking for places in train, buses for project week-end ("PROJEKT WOCHELENDE"). Etc.
 2. Searching for places ("Student sleep places – JUGENDHEBERGE") for project-week-end in groups for fasting our project development;
 3. Writing LaTeX documentation for project reports;
 4. Writing JUnit testing code for GUI code;
 5. Writing BASH-scripts for tackling connection problems between actuators and the Debian Linux Operating System (thanks to Christian).
- "Unfortunately I received a grade of only 2.7 (14/20) because I wasn't interested in cartography and cognition algorithms since this was the specialty of "Christian Freksa" and "CoSy Group of Research" (<https://cosy.informatik.uni-bremen.de>)."
- THIS IS THE REASON our project advisors "FRANK dylla", and "LUTZ frommberger" gave as justification to this baddest grade during my entire curriculum in ACADEMIA at all !
- I also need to mention that I was the only "SCHWARZNEGGER – black from africa" in this research group of mainly white-blond-racists like "MICHA", and "STEPHAN"...
- THESE 4 racists-idiot said some day I may not be very comfortable in group working with white-intellectual. I THINK "frommberger the female-male-gay-BORN-male was at origin of such systemic" sexist discrimination around myself; even during my research time under supervision of male-female-chevalie-boivert-PATRICK-lam !
- d. "A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMA AND TIMED AUTOMATA (Grade 20/20)", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2004 – 12/2004]
- [Vordiplom in informatik – INDEPENDENT STUDY, Bachelor Independent Study, MATHEMATICS for Computer Science, Theoretical Computer Science, timed automata, büchi automata, timed csp, set algebra]
- I developed a set of transformations functions that take as input a büchi automaton and generates a timed automaton. This work was the 1st work under supervision of "Jan Peleska", at our request, because we had interest in working in avionics software development in his company "Verified Systems International GmbH" (<https://www.verified.de>)."
- It is my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji Ngongang" who is the one that gave me this advise at that time of my life where I was around 20 years old in Germany; "Just at my 2nd year of University."
- "Finally a small offer a 200 Euros monthly came after I performed 100 % for this work unpaid [details at link 1b], t hat I used as Independent study. "
- e. "1st & 2nd Semester Software Development PROJECT (Grade 18/20)", ST-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2002 – 09/2003]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, Software Engineering, Project Requirements, "Gant Diagrams", UML 2.0, XML, PHP, MySQL, JAVA]
- "This 1st and 2nd semester project, divided in 2 parts consisted in creating a multi-user dungeon server (MUD-server) where a virtual world existed; 1st year was used to elicit user software program requirements, and establish "Requirement documents using UML 2.0".
 - "telnet (port 23)" protocol was used as client-server communication mechanism."
 - "I involved myself in a project where I contributed around 7 000 lines of plain JAVA code of program development."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN

1. Psychological care | [10/2002 – 07/2007]
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- A. "DIPL.-PSYCH. RALF ERIC STREIBL.", MATHEmatics and Computer Science Department, University of Bremen, Germany [10/2002 – 07/2007]
["Dipl.-Psych. Ralf ERIC Streibl".]
- "As a student of computer science in the "FB3" of the UNIVERSITY OF Bremen, In city Bremen, HANSEATISCHE-CITY, Germany, WE had a psychologist as 1 of our lecturer called "Dipl.-Psych RALF-idiot Eric Streibl". "
- RALF-idiot was kind of very reluctant to discriminative opportunities because I remember having visited courses on web creation based on PHP, and MariaDB, since I WAS having [a student-job (WERKSTUDENT) at "ZMML"].
- Eric RALF-idiot also gave myself a so called course titled "PROPÄDEUTIK" where we students learned on how to effectively, clearly present our projects or work; THIS was done in groups and individually !
- B. "AT-HOME-RACIST-IN-BREMEN PROGRAM", Foreigner office-"Sekretariat für AUSLÄNDISCHE studierende", University of Bremen, Germany [JULY 2005 – AUGUST 2017]
["RAÏNER schulze-smidt".]
- THIS program was exclusively addressed for foreign country students to gain access to german in-born families in order to accustom one to germany as a home country.
- "I joined this program because my maternal uncle "THÉODORE WANDJI" recommended it to myself because He was emigrating to CANADA-montreal, And would have been very far from me. "THÉODORE wandji ngongang" was the one person that welcomed and invited myself to study in BREMEN ! "
- AT this effect, each volunteer foreigner student would be connected to a single volunteering family of BREMEN. IN my specific case, I was assigned to the "ARISTOCRATIC"-bürgerliche family "SCHULZE-SMIDT", originating predominantly from HOLLAND into GERMANIA.
- MISTER "raïner-schulze-smidt", and his 2nd"SPOUSE GABRIELLE schulze-smidt" were really kind and nice to myself.
- "RAINER was "sole investor and proprietor-German-INHABER of an insurance company in Bremen, and in LONDON-great-britain", WHERE he did his apprenticeship as "INSURANCE-business-man". HIS 2nd spouse Gabrielle that I met in person; Was a part-time "physiotherapist" for the football team of Bremen city : "WERDERBREMEN (<https://>)". "
- Through them, I could know more about the origins of the autonomous-HANSE-STADT of Bremen, since "GOVERNOR SMIDT" as upper-upper grandfather of "MR. RAÏNER Schulze-Smidt", was governor of BREMEN for 50-years, and is the one person that acquire land from "HANNOVER-autonomous-STATE", to create a water-port-German-haven; "BREMERHAVEN", as a city and port for the autonomous city-federal-STATE of BREMEN.
- People and places I visit, and met, through organization of RAINER and GABI :
- 1.) HIS cousins from Brazil by talk-only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names;
 - 2.) HIS cousins from JOHANNESBURG by talk-only & pictures (<https://>); that I DONT remember family names, but that are having a wool factory for exportation in the state of BREMEN-recist germania;
 - 3.) VISIT of "evangelic church" on King-JESUS birth day "December 25th";
 - 4.) VISIT of MUSEUM-"Fockemuseum";
 - 5.) VISIT of "musical-theater" in "BREMEN-DOMSHEIDE";
 - 6.) "Bernhadine", "Caspar", "Johann" & "senior sister JULIA" schulze-smidt.
 - 7.) Several friends of them in need of computer technical help in terms of Software installation, and support.
 - 8.) "DOROTHEE" and "her brother Dr. oec. Sebastian Dettmers (<https://>)";
 - 9.) "Kryenhop family" (<https://>) : a leader in industrial transfer And sale of asian food and products into GERMANY :
 - a.) Father "Rolf";
 - b.) Daughter "SVANTSKE";
 - c.) etc.
- "I quit this family relationship at request of "RAÏNER" and "his 2nd spouse GABRIELLE-gabi", because they thought I lied to them that I have got a position as a temporary "SOFTWARE DEVELOPER" employee earning "70 000 Euros" annually at "AMADEUS Germany GmbH", Via THE frankfurter human resource company """. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – YERITH-RD-TEST

2. Psychological care |
 COLLÈGE INTEG –FROM-LAQUINTINIE-HOSPITAL-EYOUM-CHRISTIAN-IDIOT-CRIMINAL,
 DOUALA, CAMEROUN [01/2021 – 06/2021]
- A. "DR. (PH.D.) JEAN MOUBEB", Collège Integ –from-LAQUINTINIE-hospital-EYOUM-christian-idiot-criminal,
 Douala, Cameroun [01/2021 – 06/2021]
 ["DR. (Ph.D.) Jean MOUBEB".]

"ROSE sangnou-chienne-génitrice; a sanguinary mégère that is said to have caused a sudden death of her husband THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot; my biological genitor; ORGANIZES that I am brought by force to a psychiatric institute called Douala-laquintie-hospital because we had a talk at her mother's place where I WAS SAYING that I NEED my documents from my real-estate properties be given back to myself by her."

"AS I am currently writing this small report on NOVEMBER 20th, 2024; ALL my belongings weren't given back to me by VICTOR koliou noundou that detains this official documents that I MUST possess by inheritance right as summoned by a judge just after the death of my father and dear genitor THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot."

"INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni-chandriand, born-geboren Ingrid TCHITCHUI noumbissi is trying to take away all my real-estate properties, together with LAURENT-tchandeu free mason !!! "

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS I

1. **2003 – 2005:** [ZMML – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE ENHANCED LEARNING CAPABILITIES of economics students at the University of Bremen by DEVELOPING WEBSITES AND STUDENT SELF-LEARNING COMPUTER PROGRAMS, together with THE TEAM OF PROFESSOR KLAUS BÖNKOST.
2. **2006:** [FB 3; University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE created a website for the AFRICAN STUDENT ASSOCIATION "Nasgen e.V (New African Student Generation eingetragener Verein)" !
3. **2006:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE pleaded FORMER CAMEROON STUDENT serge achille fopoussi nono TO COME WITH MYSELF CONTRIBUTE at work research group of PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
4. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE completely alone, installed and deployed a networked installation of LaDIVA at a section of "KARLSRUHE city council !", SO TO ALLEVIATE DUTIES OF dear mentor DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH) SVEN KAMRATH !
5. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY pinpoint TU HAMBURG-HARBURG CAMEROON STUDENT david demo noundou TO MR. JENS MÖLLER of GEWETE GmbH ¹, FOR HIM TO HELP MR. DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU with access to FINAL SCHOOL YEAR WORK EXPERIENCE, AND BACHELOR OF SCIENCE THESIS-WORK.
6. **2006:** [University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I could successfully provide "MS WINDOWS SOFTWARE" INSTALLATION, TROUBLESHOOTING, and TRAINING to several GERMAN people because of "DEAR MR. RAINER SCHULZE-SMIDT" and HIS SPOUSE "MS. GABRIELE SCHULZE-SMIDT".
THESE EXPERIENCES WERE VERY POSITIVE FOR my finances !
7. **2005 – 2007:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **2007 – 2009:** [SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Erlangen, Bayern, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY MAINTAIN All Oncology Care Systems HOSPITALS customers, throughout the whole planet, ON FRONT-LINE OF problem/defect RESOLUTION WHENEVER technicians on CRITICAL problem phone resolution lines 1, 2, and 3 COULDN'T SOLVE SOFTWARE TECHNICAL ISSUES of linac.
9. **2009 – 2011:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE socially, WITH COMPUTING TECHNOLOGY, helped following afro-descendants from CAMEROON:
 1. CÉLESTIN puene: helped him search on the internet, and call, because of his poor English language knowledge, U.S.A businesses for inquiring on buying trucks for his brother in Cameroon.
 2. FABRICE Kouam Kamdem: maintained and improved an on-line website for FREE for his cameroon oriented professional association.
 3. ALBERT HERVAIS Ngagom Piewe: taught Debian-Linux basic shell command usage, Java and C++ programming on phone and internet.
 4. I HAVE presented orally and given personal written material ON SOFTWARE SECURITY AND SAFETY to CAMEROON ASSOCIATION of migrants in KITCHENER-WATERLOO: "ROWAC".
10. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE INTRODUCED skilled migrant cameroon worker, as ACTUARY in TORONTO, "AUDREY Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc (Université de Laval, Québec, CANADA)" to use and exploitation of FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE (FOSS) "Debian Linux".
11. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE advised, counseled, and even developed an on-line website for fellow CAMEROON expatriate YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (ÉCOLE SUPÉRIEURE DE GESTION, Paris) ON HIS ABANDONED PROJECT (WITH DAUGHTER OF FORMER ENERGY MINISTER of cameroon) FOR SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCTION in cameroon.

I WAS INTRODUCED to "YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (E.S.G, Paris)" BY MY AUNT-HUSBAND pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.
12. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY buy and implement foundations of "IMMEUBLE YERITH_{r&d}" which WILL STEM as a "PREMIER COMPUTING RESEARCH AND "Software Testing & Validation"" center in CENTRAL AFRICA (yaounde, center region, cameroon) !

I BOUGHT THIS PLOT OF LAND FROM hon. THÉODORE DATOUO; vice-president of parliament in YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION IN CAMEROON !

Land title CERTIFICATE nr.: 560 792, in SIMBOK, mfoundi vi (6), vol. 265 !
13. **2014:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE searched information, on how to WELCOME and ACCOMMODATE CAMEROON AMBASSADOR IN OTTAWA, for "ROWAC", a cameroonian ASSOCIATION of high skilled migrants (MOSTLY PROVENING FROM GERMANY) in KITCHENER-WATERLOO.

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS II

14. **2021:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE built a partnership with Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe and his societal NGO so to provide his NGO with VERY CHEAP AND APPROPRIATE software solutions for a NGO financed foodstore.
15. **2022:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY trained Mr. NESTOR Kenfack in ONLY 3 days at basic usage of our ERP software system YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for hardware shop selling. Mr. NESTOR Kenfack IS ONLY holder of a "B.E.P.C".

USUALLY in Yaounde, a holder of a "B.E.P.C" couldn't be trained to use COMMONLY present ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEMS (e.g.: 'Sage Gescom i7', 'SAP Business One', etc.), BECAUSE THEY ARE MEANT for highly qualified users.

Mr. NESTOR Kenfack HAD NEVER GOT exposure to an ERP system in the past.
16. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have given software cyberspace security counsels to Santa Lucia AHALA by talking to a computer technician employee because I could see vulnerabilities at cashier while paying for my goods.
17. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have counseled a business owner to start a bigger grocery shop and gave him ideas and ways on how to realize this using YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM, and, also, my unfinished two-storey building.
18. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have started YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), so to improve computing skills of fellow citizen, and also, of any other person that conforms to Cameroon laws !
20. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I try to have SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA AS 1 OF MY CLIENT THESE COMING YEARS so to have YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM there working instead of 'Odo'.
So they (SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA) will contribute in improving quality by thorough usage of this new platinum-platform.
21. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I am now working with ALT PLUS in YDE-AHALA so to have a working Supermarket in one, Instead "of a hardware-shop + a food-store separately, BUT JOINED physically".

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS I

1. **YEAR-2005:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the JAVA servlet XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA", AND ITS GUI (JAVA-SWING) configuration and installer program; for GEWETE GmbH !
2. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF "MESO"; the IMPROVED and revised version of the XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA" for GEWETE GmbH !
3. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the library computer systems communication protocol SIPv2 for GEWETE GmbH vending machines !
4. **YEAR-2005:** INVENTION OF A PROCEDURE TO systematically transform A BÜCHI AUTOMATON into A TIMED AUTOMATON ! TASK COORDINATED BY SHAREHOLDER PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
5. **YEAR-2006:** CREATION OF (with higher study part team CogAg of the University of Bremen [Cognitive Systems Group led by DEAR LATE PROFESSOR CHRISTIAN FREKSA]) ROBOT "arnie"; AND PROCEDURES TO automatically map a supermarket both geographically AND store item-wise with RFID technology by HELP OF A ROLLING ROBOT "arnie" !
6. **YEAR-2007** [FB 3! AGBS: Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)]: IMPLEMENTATION OF statistical uniformly distributed test cases generation for HAREL-statecharts ! COMMERCIALIZED BY VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
7. **YEAR-2007:** [FB 3! AGBS: University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **YEAR-2008:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the communication and control protocol DIGITAL MEVATRON INTERFACE PROTOCOL (DMIP) version 13 for THE LINEAR ACCELERATOR "linac" of SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Oncology Care Systems (OCS) !
9. **YEAR-2009:** Stopping my career; AFTER 21 MONTHS; as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS (Oncology Care Systems) in ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY; with 0 defects / faults returning FROM CUSTOMERS because OF non achievement protocol repair ! Award saying from BOSS GERHARD SENG; MY TEAM LEAD !
10. **YEAR-2011** [ECE! Ph.D. in Computer Science]: I HAVE INVENTED AND INTRODUCED A PRACTICAL AND SIMPLE STATIC ANALYSIS BY ITERATIVE DATAFLOW ANALYSIS, to check temporal safety properties, expressed with tracematches, of JAVA programs !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* Similarly, but as a dynamic analysis technique) MASC thesis (2011; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR JON Eyolfson of the UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, ON, CANADA !
EVEN THOUGH JON Eyolfson MASC (COMPUTER ENGINEERING) SUBMISSION WAS EARLIER THAN MY Ph.D. in SOFTWARE ENGINEERING THESIS DEFENSE, because of finding an examiner (reporting) within ECE DEPARTMENT, I AM THE ONE THAT GAVE A PROTOTYPE DESIGN AND PROTOTYPE DOCUMENT FOR HIS SUBMISSION !
11. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY DEVELOP manual and automatic BASH (Bourne Again SHell) programs (scripts), THAT LEAD TO A 0.5% improvement of WEBSPHERE computing performance !
12. **YEAR-2013:** CREATION OF A RUNTIME dynamic taint analysis for the QUERCUS PHP INTERPRETER !
13. **YEAR-2015:** FIRST WORLD-WIDE OPEN-SOURCE (foss) RELEASE OF AN LLVM-BASED ON INTERMEDIATE REPRESENTATION (IR) static iterative KILDALL (gary kildall) DATAFLOW ANALYSIS named 'YERITH-SAINT' !
'YERITH-SAINT': <https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint> !
14. **YEAR-2015:** CREATION OF A CONTEXT-SENSITIVE FLOW-SENSITIVE tainted paths generation algorithm by iterative dataflow analysis !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* EXACT same technique) PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at VIRGINIA TECH, VA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR SAZZADUR Ahaman AT University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ, U.S.A !
 2. PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, SANTA BARBARA, CA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ARAVIND Machiry AT Purdue University, IN, U.S.A !
15. **YEAR-2020:** FIRST OFFICIAL RETESTED RELEASE OF THE full featured OPEN SOURCE enterprise resource planing software "YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE"; FIRST OFFICIAL RELEASE OF THE OPEN SOURCE AUTOMATED BACKUP-SYSTEM AND ALERT ("yerith-erp-3.0"-system-daemon": <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>) !

"YERITH-ERP-PGI-standalone, server, academic, client" ARE THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THIS FOSS-ERP-PGI-FRENCH !

SERVER AND CLIENT are mainly meant for a supermarket having several cashiers offices, AND A SERVER directing MYSQL-commercial options in common for different client-cashier-OFFICES !

ACADEMIC is meant for use WITH an IN-MEMORY DATABASE like "SQLite" !
16. **YEAR-2021:** First stable release of YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE at PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE MAKËPÈ !

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS II

17. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST DELIVERY OF a compendium OF DOCUMENTS concerning OUR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE !
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>
18. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE state transition diagram LIBRARY FOR RUNTIME DATAFLOW VERIFICATION (YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))
20. **YEAR-2022:** MODIFICATION OF A Free Open Source Software (FOSS) "QVGE" (<https://showroom.qt.io/qvge-qt-visual-graph-editor>) TO DESIGN state diagram TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES ! "YR_QVGE" ! YR_QVGE is a commercial tool of mine priced at 3 000 EUROS a single executable copy.
21. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE FRAMEWORK for runtime dataflow analysis (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF | YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif) | 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))!
22. **YEAR-2022:** I have added a runtime check verification view within FOSS-ERP ("YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER": 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)) IN ORDER TO VIEW LOG MESSAGES SENT TO YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !
23. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION of a systematic method, AND / OR PROCEDURE TO TEST AND / OR verify dataflow of thick-client (or web application), AGAINST A SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY SPECIFICATION expressed as a STATE DIAGRAM (modified mealy machine) !
24. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST OFFICIAL REPORT in FRENCH LANGUAGE OF ACTIVITIES of YERITH R&D SINCE RELEASE OF FIRST STABLE VERSION OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum!
"REPORT in french: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/> !
25. **YEAR-2023:** creation of a domain-specific language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG) to describe *state diagram mealy machines* (📄 [SDMM](#)).
26. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION with flex and bison OF A DOMAIN-SPECIFIC LANGUAGE COMPILER to create source C++ code files for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
27. **YEAR-2023:** SUBMISSION OF A FULL TECHNICAL PAPER ("YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF: A FRAMEWORK FOR VERIFYING SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTIES OF GUI SOFTWARE AT RUNTIME") TO SPLASH-ICTSS 2023 CONFERENCE in May 2023.
28. **YEAR-2023:** Implementation of more than 2-states *state diagram mealy machine* (📄 [SDMM](#)) in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)), and YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)).
29. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION of guarded condition expression specification within YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)), and automated code generation of guarded condition expression in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
30. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
31. **YEAR-2023:** First release of our CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) drawing design tool "📄 [YRI_QVGE](#) " official commercial document.
32. **YEAR-2023:** online ENGLISH INTO FRENCH, and vice versa LANGUAGE TRANSLATION within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
33. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION of a viewing graphical user interface application for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF in JUNE.
34. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF FIRST RELEASE OF automatic EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP SALARY CALCULATION. Cumulated pay groups for a single employee salary calculation is included.
35. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION OF a user's guide for YERITH_QVGE.
36. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED IMPLEMENTATION OF a user sample project AUTOMATIC binary executable generation in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
37. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE programs under analysis (PUA) monitoring within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
38. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE runtime monitors WITHIN A SINGLE EXECUTABLE for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
39. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED journal article (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8381187>) for STTT official journal release.
40. **YEAR-2023:** started a predicate logic for deriving SOFTWARE RECOVERY ACTIONS for sdmm ("state diagram mealy machine").
41. **YEAR-2023:** started writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10515549>).
42. **YEAR-2024:** finished writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report*: THIS REPORT specifically says that CPDM ruling party has tried to destroy my life using *CHRISTIAN eyoum* (<https://scholar.google.fr/citations?user=eHvsI1UAAAAJ&hl=fr>).
43. **YEAR-2024:** started writing courses curricula and content for several courses of [YECEFOIQ](https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm) (<https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm>).
44. **YEAR-2024:** started creation of a web site application for teaching computer science center YECEFOIQ.
45. **YEAR-2024:** I have implemented case insensitive search for financial expenses list within YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
46. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paused new features in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (I.E.: Human resource management, and Financial Accounting management) due to advancements required for their quality assurance, WITH 📄 [YRI_QVGE!](#)

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS III

47. **YEAR-March 2024:** I could finally find 1 company commercial that rented my 1st 3-bedrooms apartment in DLA for "90 000 Xaf" monthly !
48. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paid "50 000 Xaf" as starting advance funds for incorporating YERITH R&D SARL.
49. **YEAR-March 2024:** I am recruiting 1 commercial financial-entrepreneur for ~~YECEFOHQ~~ (LOOKING for investment funds).
50. **YEAR-JUNE 25, 2024:** Returning client N.K hardware shop for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 !
51. **YEAR-2024:** Refining automatic stock CSV data entry.
52. **YEAR-JULY 29, 2024:** Still training "Christelle Akamba" for just 1 000 Francs an hour.
THERE is no money outside in Yaounde; and my rental apartments are still not having renters due to LAURENT TCHANDEU that I know has been trying to disrupt my activities in the open source software (OSS) era.
53. **YEAR-September 08, 2024:** *I AM working on ground to perfection building YERITH.*
THERE is lack of funding even though I could have my judicial affair against CHRISTIAN-EYOUM and others to get sent back to NDOKOTI prosecutor.
UNFORTUNATELY attorney SYNCLAIRE-NJEUTCHA-TCHANA has been trying to disrupt my activities with some money-bribery he received from genitor-organizer of assassination of mine !!!
I now try to get ATTORNEY-tchonang-albertine on my side these days. C.P.D.M wolfgang owona idiot political party has been trying to take down all my activities so to destroy a non-gay citizen.
54. **YEAR-2024:** Incorporating unit of measure like gram, etc. for inventory stock entry creation and pricing.
55. **YEAR-2024:** Started incorporating Financial debt entries creation in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
I am also specifying YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME for a new idea as good-physical stock exchange start-up marketplace idea.
56. **YEAR-NOVEMBER 2024:** I have re-introduced new color schemes for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME, AND also started a document for SPECIFYING and DESCRIBING the already existing and ALREADY IMPLEMENTED: C++ runtime monitoring verification library SDMM (STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE) :
1. YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF : [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif) ;
 2. ITS usage as algorithmic trading stock exchange library and runtime monitoring engine with help of a FOSS *"STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE"* (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) monitoring container for real-timing.
57. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *I have incorporated "FR", "EN", USA-american flag and FRANCE-flag onto YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM so to hint users on Translation from English into FRENCH; And vice versa.*
58. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *We are trying to render incorporating of sdmm[1d] as plug-gable dynamic libraries into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.*
59. **YEAR-FebRUARY 2025:** *[I am also trying to check conformant thread calls from runtime QT-QTimer instances whenever a user tries to cancel his modification / insertion work; FOR instance a special case is whenever 'INSERT/UPDATE' button is pressed and then there is intermingling with the checking mechanism introduced for verifying whether a user cancels his work on the window frame or not !]*
60. **YEAR-March 2025:** *I am struggling with INGRID-own-sister that digest all time my genitor because of 6 children with less than 2 years separation birth time between them !*
61. **YEAR-April 2025:** *Currently doing major research & inspection work for a web shop by using partly our; At YERITH R&D, new invention WYSIWYG-Tool for web HTML pages (YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL) !*
62. **YEAR-April 2025:** *NO body originating from West Cameroon seems to be living peacefully in CMR with bulu tribe since event a ["**president bulu of the republic**"] is embezzling young researcher in science and / or engineering like myself so to perpetuate going to IMF-fucking-idiot to pertain African in under poverty world for ever-devilish !*
63. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[JUDGE yager] seems to think of taking my complaint more seriously these days since I was advised to meet another justice attorney working a kind of on my file; Directly this coming 20th week of year 2025 (May-12 up to May-16) !*
64. **YEAR-May 2025:** *Eyoum Christian sends even people as kind fo rental management agent into my house to act so to hijack myself again : "Soumbil" living here at Cité-des-Palmiers.*
65. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[I am also these days trying to incorporate a dynamic taint analysis within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum as an instance incarnation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF and / or "SDMM" specification & accompanying source code.]*
66. **YEAR-May 2025:** *We are working on our 1st prototype complete product that automatically generates a webshop from QT-trolltech user-interface files again this month; We plan a travel abroad !*
67. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[Soumbil, a molester of myself via a so called paternal uncle-gay-hijacker seems to not understand that as a mature researcher professional, And born-again Christian; There is no need for myself to talk with non sense village-babouantou-born people like KOLIOU-gay-idiot VICTOR-noundou !]*
68. **YEAR-JUNE 5, 2025:** Currently refactoring YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum !
69. **YEAR-JUN.-NOV., 2025:** *I am solely working on all projects so to try having YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum in the software program market starting JAN. 2026 !*

20.20 'VALKYRIE' upgrade to DEBIAN BULLSEYE (11.0); QT-5

VALGRIND USER INTERFACE: *valkyrie* (<https://www.valgrind.org/downloads/guis.html>)

July 2023

- Free open source code:
https://www.github.com/yerothd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL

'VALKYRIE' is a dynamic analysis CASE tool for verifying memory errors, and using VALGRIND as backend program server for analysis.

21.21 CONTEXT SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ("YERITH-SAINT")

October 2009 – March 2015

- Free open source code:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>

'YERITH-SAINT' is a static taint analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs and that doesn't require any program annotations. 'YERITH-SAINT' is built upon the iterative dataflow framework and has been implemented using the LLVM compiler infrastructure. 'YERITH-SAINT' is interprocedural, flow-sensitive, and developers can choose to run it either with context-sensitivity or without. THE HEARTBLEED bug (april 2014; security breach in open ssl 1.0.1f) IS A POTENTIAL FINDING OF yerith-saint.

22.22 YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE !

23.23 YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON': AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DB-BACKUP SYSTEM FOR 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DATABASE BACKUP SYSTEM FOR FOSS-ERP YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE !

24.24 YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF': C++ Library FOR RUNTIME MONITORING (Safety Temporal Properties) FOR State Diagram MONITORING !

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) C++ library, THAT ENABLES TO IMPLEMENT STATE DIAGRAM SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY RUNTIME CHECKING (and/or VERIFICATION).

25.25 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF': RUNTIME VERIFICATION OF TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES IN 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE'

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
- YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM:
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE), AND REUSABLE DYNAMIC RUNTIME ANALYSIS AND TESTING INFRASTRUCTURE created for FOSS ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' !

26.26 [YRI_QVGE](#)

'YRI_QVGE': Design and Creation of Runtime SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTIES FOR State diagram MONITORING C++ Library
'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' !

2,500 Euros a single executable copy FOR DEBIAN-LINUX
June 2022 - Currently

27.27 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE](#): an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE: an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software'

PRICE DEPENDS ON installations ! (STARTS AT 200,000 XAF per node-computer; ONLY AVAILABLE FOR DEBIAN-LINUX)
Mars 2015 - Currently

(GRADUATE) STUDENTS ADVISING / COUNSELING

- 1.) ["AMIRHOSSEIN VAKILI"], Ph.D. (www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 2.) ["DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU"], BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF HAMBURG-HARBURG, HAMBURG, GERMANY
- 3.) ["DIVAM JAIN"], M.MATH (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/7943>) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2013
- 4.) [Dr "ERIC BREFO-MENSAH"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/13341>) (CHEMISTRY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2018
- 5.) [Dr "ESTHER ELIZABETH LAMBERT"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://ca.linkedin.com/in/esther-lambert-5b869414>) (GEOGRAPHY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2009
- 6.) ["Basser (from Syria)"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING, ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2008
- 7.) ["FABRICE tchoumi"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING (AVIONICS), ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2007 – 2008
- 8.) ["FELIX FANG"], MAsc (<https://www.patricklam.ca/papers/15.pppj.af-analysis.pdf>) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2014
- 9.) Dr. rer. nat. "HASHIM CHUNPIR" (<https://www.igi-global.com/affiliate/hashim-chunpir/324991>) (MSC, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2005 – 2006
- 10.) DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. "SERGE ACHILLE FOPOUSSI NONO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 11.) "DERRICK FIEDLER (born YAPI YAPO)", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 12.) "INES NGAKOU TEMOU", (BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 13.) "DAVID KAMGA ADAMO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 14.) C++ MATRIX programming : "Dr. MOHAMED RIDHA MAHFOUDHI", MBA, PhD (Financial Engineering, University of Laval, QC, Canada). 08 / 2009
- 15.) www.assiw.com; "MARCELLIN TAALY" (<https://www.tally-tech.com>), (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY)
- 16.) "MATTHIAS (from Germany)", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH); INFORMATIK-INGENIEUR, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 17.) "Virginie kamche" (<https://www.virginie-kamche.de>), DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 18.) "MAÏMOUNA BAMBA" (https://www.linkedin.com/authwall?trk=gf&trkInfo=AQFQXYFtwV7oPgAAAZpFVPT4EKXGTEW7GH101CD4u_8N1S0xGKwMs5KN2sOZJwAIdn182N7jf-ZVEP0M88eq9AJpMymzhwyCmFnDfOVkLrgeYIiR8GwDj91RrPXUtYQsjgqcSZI=&original_referer=https://www.google.com/&sessionRedirect=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.linkedin.com%2Fpub%2Fdir%2FBamba%2FMaimouna) (from COTE-D'IVOIRE), DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 19.) ["Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D."] (Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 20.) ["JON EYOLFSON", Ph.D.] (M.Asc. / Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/6206>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 21.) "THÉOPHILE TCHIENCHO", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH), INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES, BREMEN, GERMANY

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - I

1. SHANDA family as a destructive life for BOTH noumbissi, and NGONGANG and whereabouts families

"SHANDA Ndjatie Dorothee, and her spouse official TONME-shanda-JEAN-claude" are the 1st persons that started destruction of my life by coming into my family with so called psychiatrist, via WOLFGANG-owona.

"OWONA wolfgang" seemed to getting married with ANGELA which is a cousin maternal of mine because HE WANTS to sell my soul to AMERICAN USA societies in the sense that HE put myself into troubles via GOVERNMENTS AGENCIES, all of them Are linked to secret services to which he belongs, as I HAVE HEARD from ANGELA myself.

Frequently, HE idiot wife says he traveled to USA, so he would talk to people that want my OPEN SOURCE entrepreneurial adventures to be stopped; GET money from them, Then organize hijacking with following agencies:

- 1.) Social Services; so I AM NO MORE independent in the state of biya-regime;
- 2.) HOSPITAL like "laquintinie", etc.

Dr.-wolfgang, which is born from MINISTER owona-joseph-deceased, And mother as daughter of MINISTER owona-Gregoire has tried to put Rosicrucian organization AMORC into my life via Angela who proposed to me to join a so called "lectorium-rosicrucae" based at external relations ministry Where WOLFGANG attends with her.

2. WAAH (anne), spouse Kemmegni, is a subject of BIYA SPOUSE !!!

This 'megere' of my grand mother mother's side; Tchuitchui-ELIZABETH;

Is obviously a devilish demon that possesses super-natural powers in dark kingdoms; Based of 3 sacred objects I have last seen in her house in Byemassi-YDE.

1. "Buffle" horns as a representation of Money-laundry-BAPHOMET-satan
2. 2 turtles carapaces in the back of the "Buffle" horns.
3. 2 portraits of girls invoking and respectively crying;

3. "SANGO, spouse Bernadette Noundou" IS SOMEWHAT a suspect at origin of this family tragedy !!!

This pseudo-suspect seems to want to acquire my place at KING.

Laurent tchandeu ministry plenipotentiary is a subject of itself at Batchieu-Babouantou kings places.

Obviously, every member of GRAND-FATHER noundou nuclear family is a subject to this GUJA.

4. "Victor Koliou NOUNDOU" IS A NOBODY into my life;

THIS idiot, junior brother of my deceased late father "Théodore Noubissi" is contacting people INCLUDING "derek rayside (drayside@uwaterloo.ca)" (Already talking with other ignorant paternal unwanted uncle "Jules NTETA noundou (julesnteta@gmail.com; julesnteta@yahoo.fr)" from Cameroon external research criminal agency (DGRE));

The idiot Victor presents itself as a chief of a family where I am supposed to belong with some faked official documents from uncle politician LAURENT tchandeu-IDIOT.

OFFICIAL registered document that "Victor KOLIOU NOUNDOU" refused to give a copy to myself when I asked him about, since I am the only, according to documents written by my late grand-father Michel NOUNDOU, Legitimate SUPERVISOR OF HIS left over to children and descendants, WEALTH AND MATERIAL POSSESSIONS !

"Afriland first-bank" and "Intelligentsia employee "Jean-PAUL-yamtche"; And CEO currently as of April 2024", A person that I really don't really know whereabouts in his genealogy or affiliation to my late grand-father; "Jean-PAUL-yamtche" owns a big storey house just opposite face of our main common house entrance in Babouantou idiot village !

"Afriland first-bank" and Intelligentsia MAIN CREATOR AND INSPIRATORY person; "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne", was, according to sayings of my genitor Rose Sangnou, 1 of an intimate friend of my late father and genitor "Théodore NOUMBISSI" !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" went to a place of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)", according to "Rose Sangnou" told myself in person when I reached age 32; That they ("LAURENT Tchandeu my paternal uncle" and "Rose SANGNOU" my genitor) gave money (BRIBED) to an employee of "CCEI-BANK" where "late Théodore NOUMBISSI" owed "4 000 000 XAF" at his death so that *MORTGAGE ("hypothèque" in French) on his property-land in BONABERI-DLA (700 m²)* would be erased everywhere in computers and documents of former 'CCEI-bank' !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" also told me, after I had an employment interview with "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne"; that my later genitor and father "Théodore NOUMBISSI" is the one, together with "HUGUES NTOMANI TIAKO", his business partner and soul-mate at that former ancient time, THAT computerized totally all enterprises businesses of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)" !

I remember seeing my late father only 1 time in a day, around 19 : 00 at diner time; this is before we moved to Yaounde in year 1990; After he quits "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-DLA" to open and manage solely "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-YDE" !

5. "LAURENT tchandeu (ltchandeu@yahoo.fr)" ASSASSINATES in an hospital "THEODORE noumbissi"; late father of mine on January 1992;

AS an orphan at age of 7.5 years old, I remember uncle paternal Laurent came into our biggest house in YDE-Essos to settle in the secondary apartment at the back of our house.

6. "LAURENT tchandeu" Tries with "Hugues Ntomani Tiako" "VIA judith ngaleu in Etobicoke (Toronto, Ontario, Canada)" to crash "my Toyota Corolla LE-2003" in December 2013

This sorcerer freemason ("Hugues Ntomani Tiako"), and Christian-so-called-ORTHODOX-catholic of Roma, acknowledges that IT SHALLN'T be that I gain cause in the court of justice process THAT I have against "LAQUINTINIE and SED", that sent 9 people, including "Christian Eyoum, MD, PsyD"; in February 2021 at night around 23 : 30, to hijack and attempts to kill myself.

SED sent myself 1 time in a CABANON Because they receive 15,000 FCFA from "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou and my genitor ROSE Sangnou", IN douala 2018.

"Galax Yves Landry Etoga" is personally, as a CPDM political party member, AND not as a SED authority implicated in trying to kill myself through psychiatry and / or any other means !

"Laurent Tchandeu (assassin of Ingrid's father and his elder brother in Babouantou-village)" is the one that connected "Ingrid TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI", born (geboren in German) TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI; my uterine sister, to marry officially "THE IDIOT AND PSY-CHILD since age 12 *CHANDRIAND TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI*".

7. "LAURENT tchandeu" Deems and Dares OR-DONATES to squeeze my financial money income VIA genitor of mine "Rose SANGNOU" Since September 2023 until TODAY.

8. "***JULES NTETA NOUNDOU extremely dangerous person" is a consanguine brother (same father; another, still living mother, in same marriage) of "LAURENT tchandeu"; And his helper in almost everything dirty and / or clean here in CMR!

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - III

9. ("Derek Rayside drayside@uwaterloo.ca") pays money to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that an equivalence to my "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering degree from UWATERLOO", will be turned from PhD into the non-academic degree ABD; just 2 weeks after talking with "JULES NTETA NOUNDOU" at his dirty-office in "YDE-élig-essono"
10. "David demo noundou" tries to connect me to Laurent external security research agent "Jean-Daniel-tujilo-tchokote"; "VIA his natal village idiot babouantou friend Célestin puene (cpuene@cscmonavenir.ca)".
11. "David demo noundou" has written documents in Germany that I was mentally ill while staying 3 days in his rental apartment in September 2018.
12. "David demo noundou" is A student of myself at the TUHH; benjamin brother of my late father "THEODORE noumbissi"; since I could help him get an bachelor internship At "GEWETE GmbH", Where I was working while a student at Bremen University state.
13. "LAURENT tchandeu" was a "Minister Plenipotentiary of Cameroon Embassies in France, Belgium, etc. for around 30 years outside of Cameroon". Especially promoted sent outside Cameroon 1 year after assassinating his elder brother "THEODORE noumbissi".
14. "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" tries to physically arrest and violates myself in front of at least 7 other people in his private residence of Bankepche-Bangou with no apparent reason other than humiliate myself.

"Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" vows a personal and individual cult to 'Shanda Owona Biya', especially as an appointed, not applied CPDM (RDPC) political party, vice-president in Bankepche-Bangou; with "Honorable Datouo Theodore" as his president.

15. "**RODRIGUE alain sienchié ngongang** (sienchie@gmail.com)", Ancient psychiatric patient in Düsseldorf-Germany Sends messages everywhere So I could again be hijacked into a Cabanon-cell FOR mad-ill-people; "Xavier Noumbissi Noundou" paid in total amount 2,000 Euros to help him get back "to his paternal family NGONGANG" in Deido-Dla-CMR !
16. "**Théodore Wandji Ngongang, And Aurélie Kamdoum Yano his spouse** (takouengongang@yahoo.ca; ngongangtietie@yahoo.ca)", ows myself around "1 500 EUROS" since year 2005 as he fled out from Germany to emigrates into "Montréal-Côtes-des-neiges" !
17. "**Idiot Angéla Tchamou Shanda Wolfgang Owona** (krauserminrex@gmail.com)", a maternal cousin of mine, tries to hijack myself in buses because She deems being a very important personality ("VIP") in front of myself.

"HER spouse Dr Wolfgang Junior Fernand Owona" was making her ("Angéla Tchamou Shanda Owona") come to myself and harassed me with: "Wolfgang wants to be president of the republic" !

This idiot of Wolfgang is the grandson mother side of "Grégoire Owona", who was implicated in the sudden death of his former colleague "Theodore Noumbissi (Late father of mine)".

"Grégoire Owona" is today inviting "my remaining genitor Rose SANGNOU" to his village houses in "Gomedzap-Center-Region-CMR"; so to think her How to destroy my life as a black and renowned scientist universally from the University of Waterloo; THIS in conjunction with former uni colleagues such as "Dr. PATRICK lam"; etc. "Grégoire Owona" -

For 2 days now (January 14, 2026.); my profile is down at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project; And at same time I felt several people trying to hijack my person here in Cameroon because a certain "#PASTOR-landry ENTERS MY PERSONAL HOME WITH A WEAPON."

In cameroon, as I have heard from people in background, CRIMINAL-ASSASSIN FROM yves-galax-landry Wear name PASTOR.

Derek Rayside has put back a vietnamese idiot on my file at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that I cannot be upwell in Cameroon.

My official university of waterloo graduate transcripts says:

"Program: Engineering Doctoral;

"PhD" Comprehensive Examination.

Status: Completed

Date Completed: 12/20/2011

In good english: "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering ("PhD" in Electrical & Computer Engineering)".

In french language: Docteur-Ingénieur (Dr.-Ing.).

IT means I must also have *Ph.D.* exactly as My former room colleague Jon Eyolfson that is since 2022 an Assistant Professor in Teaching only at the University of Toronto, ON.

18. **"S2TBED main proprietor-ally A SO-called gangster-Simplice-KAMENI was seen 2 days ago here in a luxurious car by myself.**

"IMMEDIATELY, today, *"/Friday-Sep.-27th, & Saturday-Sep.-28th/*, both days in year 2024, I and neighborhood start again to experience energy supply disruption for more than 4 hours."

SIMPLICE KAMENI seems to be a cocaine dealer that works on laundering money through usage of wood processing & wood sale activities via intermediary White-racist-extremist—italian so-called "MARCO".

ALSO, I could experience certain "neggers" working there from far-north cameroun coming along my foot way to dance kind of like I am their aid.

KAMENI simplice is also implicated in financing together with my cousin culprit-theodore-MOISE-tebiwo-yamkam my properties entirely in Cameroon; Starting year 2013 when TEBIWO-yamkam-moise traveled to Canada.

BOTH moise-yamkam-tebiwo, and SIMPLICE-kameni-ebacka; are sleeping in so-called orgy-sexist-FRANCK-biya gay personal property estate here in YAOUNDE.

19. **"HONORÉ WUCHE, a genitor of mine Spouse; ", EVENTHOUGH her cousin uterin, as hijacker into my life.**

"THIS honore-wouche has been calling me on my phone cell while I was a doctor of Engineering working on my doctoral Ph.D. degree in year 2013; GIVEN TO HIM BY ROSE sangnou."

HONORÉ WUCHE has lost already at least two wives he got kids with them as a guja.

HIS uterine cousin "Rodrigue Alain NGONGANG SIENCHIE", that tried to break my neck last August 2024 while I was attending home for 4 weeks and visiting faked "church Chapelle De la GLOIRE-DE-CHRIST by FAKED-devilish-racist-bassa pastor-so-called MARK-DJENG-DJENG";

Said to myself in front of honore-wouche that: 'SEND "xavier-noundou-ph.d." Again to MAD-person cell at "laquintinie" AS you did twice at least; I didn't even knew who was this gay-honore-wouche with black tattooed wrist-arm-bracelet for gangster and riders.

IT seems this cousin of my mother-genitor; together with another man-lady-cousin-uterine so called NANA; are working on molesting myself in life here in Cameroon; HE-honore-wouche told me laughing that 1 of his daughter was working in south-cameroon in farming for PAUL-biya-family.

20. **"Bulu-Sud-East-Akan tribe AS stealer in CMR"**

- Year 1983 was changed into year 1985-(*ingrid-teuntchou-noumbissi birth year*) so to allow later on a hijack of my property via a marriage to a uterine sister; Called "INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni", Born-geboren "Ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi";

[TEUNTCHOU-isaac & JOSUE-nkwouano; & RICHARD-mfeugwang agreed on a dinner time of my passing away with all means via a psychiatric injection treatment by LAQUINTINIE-hospital;]

[LAURENT-tchandeu could then secure a prosperous career after the killing & hijacking of money of his blood-brother Théodore-noumbissi-rosicrucian-rotarian !]

- "BULU-biya" tribe in CMR-c.p.d.m-r.d.pc are trying to hijack any wealth of Well-to-do rich cameroonian so to secure presidential leadership for ever.
- Bulu notary-justice attorney [*"MENYE-Ondo Xavier-FRANCOIS"*] & *"LIMA-rose (at time in 2012, 2013 years)"* change effectively & voluntarily year of birth of mine in my [LAND-title certificate of MFOUNDI-VI.]

- GENOCIDE of West originating people started in CMR

"MARIE-commissary-of-DEA-05ème-arrondissement-od-City-DOUALA, in Littoral region, sent 8 burglars on street to arrest myself while I was relating to CMRnian that BIYA regime has tried to spoliolate all my belonging via TEUNTCHOU-isaac."

"INGRID-teuntchou couldn't say no to this fake-marriage only to destroy my life as a super engineer and scientist originating from WEST-cmr."

"[TEUNTCHOU-isaac] used since she was aged 15 years old while I went outside of CMR to study in GERMANY-racist-culprit; NGATCHOU-henri-bertrand, a maternal uncle of myself & Ingrid to beat her & accustomate her to perform only what was told to her via JOSUE-nkwouano, senior brother of NGATCHOU-henri ! "

- 2025, AVRIL --18--*"DLA-ndokoti-palace seems to be for now out of service due to atrocities that I have related internationally via web-site "zenodo.org" ! "* (<https://www.zenodo.org>)

"ATANGA NJI idiot minister; Cannot prepare elections without asserting NON-Sence propaganda to Cameroon people."

- Laurent-fainéant TCHANDEU, a paternal vernacular uncle of mine seems to be an ally of people in Zürich working in Avionics !

TCHANDEU, TCHINGWA, KOLIYOU, and HAKOUA seems to be working for whittle racist supremacists in other to destroy any afrique-intelligentsia out of a psychiatric cyclops and / or poverty; So no black intelligent person wouldn't gain his money out of independent intellectual work; & intellectual property.

TCHANDEU, the lead, a so called diplomat, Hires only personal people from his own blood family against scientists & engineers here in Cameroon in particular.

[Koliou, TEUNTCHOU have been associated together in their rosicrucian association de destroy my financial life as I COULD observed since February 2021 when TEUNTCHOU tried to kill me.]

21. ***"EKONDY-PONDY tries to humiliate myself publicly by arresting me without any paper from a judge and / or prosecutor, so called in french procureur-de-la-république !!!***

- ***THE president of the republic PAUL-biya has tried to assassinate myself several times.***

THIS is why I JUST reply by describing what happens on the internet media so 1-day, christian will see what is happening in life of a christian-JESUS-of-nazareth life here in CMR.

- Myself I only repeat like anyone that wants his life saved here that I support him for 2025 presidential elections !
- YOU just see a police man that has no police uniform come to your home and tries to open gate as you were a gangster. THIS time it was ekony-pondy, a commissary with 4 stars on his shoulder that came in person because my sister thought I must go again for a psychiatric treatment, because she belongs to people habilitated to decide so !!!
- 1 day I believe she will notice that she can do sp because BIYA wants to use her to destroy my brilliant career that doesn't accept homosexuality call marriage.

A country where the eldest girl-child of PAUL-biya says she is a lesbian without any fear of jurisdictions-justice because she is the girl of PAUL-biya !!!

JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven, please do your will in my life !!!

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (1.)

28.28 HIJACK OF MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY BY laquintinie on FEBRUARY 2021

[r-DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM – tALKING AT *BBC-british-broadcast-corporation* (<https://>), AND *+--rotarian--+* club member in douala-sawa-tribe, chief of psy staff of LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL IN DOUALA (LITTORAL REGION, CAMEROON)], has sent in FEB. 2021, without any official document, 7 people to break into my privately owned (closed with a steel gate) house in DOUALA, so to hijack myself and terrorize me. THIS HAPPENED AT NIGHT AROUND 11:00 PM, with BERTRAND, breaking my gate seals with a weapon of some sort (BERTRAND, was the lead thief of DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM).

THIS HIJACK OR ATTACK on my person happened just 1 day after I denounced to PRC.CM and SHANDY-SHANDY-CABINET.COM (biological father of my mother's side cousin ANGELA) a fake "BACCALAUÉAT"-DEGREE from 'ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA', because her sister-cousin CYNTHIA NKWOUANO told me about this: "ANGELA WENT TO CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC and received her diploma in a hotel".

I ALSO BECAME AN AGENT OF CAMEROONIAN DEFENSE AND SECURITY FORCES ON FEBRUARY 14, 2021.

DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM after this kidnapping, held me at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL for poisoning me 2 weeks, AND THEN RELEASED AN OFFICIAL DOCUMENT TO MY RELATIVE ROSE SANGNOU.

ROSE SANGNOU has since been using the fake document to go meet my clients to say that I AM A PSY PATIENT AND THAT THEY SHALL NOT DEAL ANYTHING WITH MYSELF. ROSE SANGNOU also went to meet all my privately-owned real estate properties' neighbors TO DO THE SAME.

I HAVE COMPLAINT BEFORE DOUALA-NDOKOTI JURISDICTIONAL TRIBUNAL in front of JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SINCE FEB. 2021:

- 3 convocations have been sent by now to DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM; he hasn't come to respond to prosecutors.
- I am now awaiting for a "MANDAT D'EMMENER" AGAINST DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM, a form of order from judge that will bring DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM in front of prosecutors by police force.

29.29 Kidnapping on FEB. 2023 WHILE WALKING BACK IN MY YAOUNDÉ REAL ESTATE PROPERTY

1. DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI accepts to send 2 thugs-burglars on the road to kidnap myself, while I was walking on street to get back into my house, and to bring me in a cab at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ; this is requested by DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA, spouse pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI is chief of psychiatry staff at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI IS VERY WELL KNOWN IN YAOUNDÉ to say disturbing voices against BAMILEKE-TRIBE, an ethnic group of the west cameroon to which, I by birth, and not by spirit [I AM A BORN AGAIN CHRISTIAN], belong.

2. AFTER 2 WEEKS OF POISONING AND TRYING TO DESTROY MY BODY WITH DRUGS AND PILLS, a yellow clothed (level of BACHELOR OF SCIENCE) gate guard OF "HÔPITAL JAMOT" that I don't remember the name, tries to SNEAK INTO my private life by calling me on my private cell phone number [(+237) 6 52 39 69 50] every other day.

I SAID TO HIM THAT I DON'T ENTERTAIN RELATIONSHIPS WITH PEOPLE LIKE HIM.

PS: THIS GATE GUARD, yellow-clothed with an uniform, is of BETI-TRIBE like DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI!

3. S2TBED, a so-called forestry society here in Yaoundé seems to be a secret agency against black-owned societies here in Cameroon.

30.30 Attempt to give me a psy consultation by ROSE SANGNOU's sister DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM

AFTER RELEASED FROM 'JAMOT', i stop taking the drugs that i was forced to intake by drink.

Knowing that this is judicial information time, I accept to talk to DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, which is DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA and ROSE SANGNOU sister, by my own request.

My goal is at time to collect as much information as possible.

She (DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM) tries to convince me that i should intake psy drugs in order to be more sociable !

31.31 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JUNE 2023

In June 2023, in its 25th week, a relative, ROSE SANGNOU, living and based in Douala for more than 60 years, comes into Yaoundé, and settle for 1 week at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA's house, at her (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) invite.

ROSE SANGNOU, whom was told, no more to persecute myself, during her interrogation time at prosecutors' office in Douala-Ndokoti, starts calling me increasingly and says she is in Yaoundé because her sister (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) son, PATRICE SHANDA SANOU CABRAL, is very ill and hospitalized at Yaoundé general hospital.

ROSE SANGNOU insists that we shall meet because she is my mother. I then accept, but refused to meet up her at my private owned property in Yaoundé-Ahala-Nsimbock. We then meet up first at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA house, then at supermarket 'supermarché carrefour EKIE' in YAOUNDÉ-ÉKIE.

THIS PERIOD IS judicial information investigation time, that is mostly why I accepted to meet up with her.

I NOTICE with an impression THAT my mother ROSE SANGNOU COULD HAVE BEEN BRUTALIZED ON HER LEFT KNEE. SHE SAID SHE FELT DOWN IN THE BACK OF HER SISTER'S HOUSE (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) because the maid woman SPILLED water with amidon on the floor.

AFTER FINISHING our lunch, my mother ROSE SANGNOU says I SHOULD START AGAIN TO TAKE psychiatric drugs: I IMMEDIATELY STAND UP FROM LUNCH TABLE AND RETURNS TO MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY, 'immeuble yerith'.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (2.)

32.32 MY SUSPICIONS about real activities of pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude and his wife

SEVERAL TIMES, pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude invited myself to hotel PARFAIT GARDEN in yaoundé so that I COULD SEE HIM ACTING as managing director of expatriate US CITIZEN ELECTRICAL ENERGY COMPANY.

so i suspect pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude receives money from some big giants NORTH-AMERICAN COMPANIES, so to disrupt my activities in the free open source software (FOSS) AREA.

33.33 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Victor Koliou Noundou IN JULY 2023

PREVIOUSLY. HÔPITAL ADLUCÉM, a hospital in Douala-BONAMOISSADI, that I went with paternal uncle Victor Koliou Noundou to threat a hyperglycemia, established with him (uncle Victor Koliou Noundou) THAT I SHOULD BE BROUGHT USING AN AMBULANCE to 'LAQUINITIE-CABANON' because Dr. MVONDO felt that I am not well behaving !

Victor Koliou Noundou, a brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi ASKED MYSELF, relentlessly, if I still take the psychiatric drugs.

I need to note here that, WITHOUT ANY APPARENT REASON, another brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi, Laurent Tchandeu, former minister plenipotentiary, sent A TRUCK WITH 6 firefighters to take me by force from my privately rented apartment in yaoundé, in the year 2015, SO TO BRING ME TO A PSYCHIATRIST OF 'JAMOT': Dr. Kamga.

IN FRONT OF ME, Dr. Kamga SAYS TO Laurent Tchandeu AND ROSE SANGNOU THAT HE CAN'T KEEP ME THERE AT 'JAMOT' BECAUSE I AM NOT A PSYCHIATRIC DISEASED PERSON.

Dr. Kamga ALSO MENTIONS THAT IF I GO TO COURT AGAINST HIM, HE WOULD PUT ALL TROUBLES on ROSE SANGNOU since WHAT SHE SAID TO HIM SO THAT HE SENT A FIREFIGHTER TRUCK to take myself by force from my privately rented apartment is wrong.

Laurent Tchandeu IS TRYING SINCE Théodore Noumbissi, my deceased (JANUARY 9, 1992) father (and chief of the NOUNDOU family), passed away, to sack my POSITION AS CHIEF OF THE FAMILY NOUNDOU:

- IN MAY 2023, politician GRÉGOIRE OWONA, grand-father of MY COUSIN MOTHER SIDE "ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA", comes with Laurent Tchandeu (and spouse DR. HENRIETTE POLA) in my village BABOUANTOU to open a primary school as gift from political party R.D.P.C (C.P.D.M).

34.34 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Laurent Tchandeu ON AUGUST 3rd, 2023

DR. Laurent Tchandeu, a paternal uncle of mine, tries to harass myself with taking psychiatric drugs.

HE DID THIS USING TELEPHONY APPLICATION "whatsapp".

35.35 WAITING FOR judge JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA

JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SEEMS TO WANT TO destroy evidences against state hospital laquintinie since He (JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA) hasn't call by police force DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM to come answer allegations against him about TRYING TO KILL ME with psychiatric drugs at night after HIJACKING MY PRIVATE PROPERTY IN DOUALA-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS !

36.36 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU harasses ROSE sangnou my mother

ROSE SANGNOU, my mother, complained to myself that KÉMAJOU is calling her very frequently to tell her I (PROF. DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU) is not mentally sane since HE is doing a lot of christian cross-sign while walking on Yaoundé streets.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (3.)

37.37 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU destroying my life as a neighbor

A FORMER SED (SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT À LA GENDARMERIE) retired colonel of cameroon gendarmerie, who has spying devices AT HOME TO HEAR PHONE, OR WHATSAPP conversations; MAKES CURRENT ELECTRICITY cut-off whenever I RECEIVE MONEY so I cannot cook and refrigerate my food properly.

THIS VERY POOR PERSON, both in spirit and financially; whose wife makes money out of cooking food for street workers, COULD SUCCESSFULLY intimidate people not to come attend work or anything else into my real estate properties.

COLONEL (retired) of Army Gendarmerie KÉMAJOU couldn't lie and convince people that I DON'T POSSESS A Ph.D in Computer Engineering; since his son "Jonas Kémajou" who he also in gendarmerie told me once: "Myself I also POSSESS A Ph.D QUALIFICATION WITH NO DEGREE AT HOME" !

I am wondering in Cameroon why army intermediates in civilian life and affairs; THIS DOESN'T HAPPEN usually in rich and developed countries like Germany.

This day of **Saturday November 18, 2023**; while I was talking to a computer technician neighbor named Gabriel Takoumbe, KÉMAJOU came along walking with an indigo "Garde Présidentielle (special unit of cameroon forces attached only for the President of The Republic.)" T-shirt.

COLONEL kemajou tells me HE WANTS MY PERSON NOT TO WRITE anymore on his forfeitures against myself; in front of at least 7 young men and women, saying He didn't call my genitor mother any day before.

COLONEL kemajou sect named JÉRUSALEM APOSTOLAT, sacks every public entry road to my real estate 2-storey building (unfinished yet).

Yves Landry Galax ETOGA, chief of secret services of Cameroon seems to like to try harassing competent professors of science and technology like myself. May be He works against CAMEROONIAN SKILLED ORPHANS like my humble person in JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven !

PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA and DR. PATRICK LAM have never said anything against what is happening to myself since 3 years ago; ALSO, Patrick is a member of Rotarian organization ROSICRUCIARY !

"29" November 2023: **I HAVE RENOUNCED TO AN ATTORNEY since TCHANA NJEUTCHA Synclaire is clearly going against my personal interests !**

"03" December 2023: **KEMAJOU and its troops that call themselves Christians ARE HARASSING PEOPLE COMING HOME.**

"04" December 2023: **I cannot recognized Cameroon where someone high qualified by myself is permanently harassed physically by illegal neighbors like KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel Criminal.**

KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel tries on the street to talk to myself while I am coming back from a hardware shop.

It seems to myself that illegal neighbors religious sect "Jerusalem Apostolat" is trying to make confusion about my humble person wherever I go in my life; Kemajou gendarmerie colonel has tried around my neighborhood, with help of SECTARIAN OF JERUSALEM APOSTOLAT; to make noise that XAVIER noumbissi noundou IS A PSYCHIATRIC PATIENT that doesn't want to take pills !

38.38 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JANUARY 2024

ROSE SANGNOU, despite that JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA gave her prohibition to come to my home in Yaounde during year 2023, came by force with someone that I don't know whereabouts To my neighbor "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" To incriminate her about chairs she owns by now;

I destroyed chairs that were not in good shape last year from my humble home by throwing them away outside. It seems "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" put them in her personal home without asking myself since I just threw them away; which is normal since They don't belonged to me anymore !

"30" January 2024: It seems my genitor mother ROSE SANGNOU went to talk to gendarmerie people so they could harass myself to go for an illegal psychiatric treatment; because while I was talking to Justice "ME. ANDRÉ Mbet" today, I saw 1 gendarmerie man came into his personal office where he also, with his wife, Owns a financial transaction center.

I immediately told Justice "ME. ANDRE Mbet" about this attitude of gendarmerie people coming inside where I perform businesses to make some kind of visual and gesture signs to owners of businesses, So they wouldn't deal with myself anymore !

"24, 25" April 2024: 1 man wearing a talkie-walkie came across my personal road in Simbock YDE.

I went to talk to him since I was looking for a technician that didn't finish a work in my humble house. For 6 days now, this technician wasn't in my house anymore despite myself telling him to finish his work on my steel door.

I suspect again *justice ("huissier") SHANDA-DJATIE and her spouse Pr. JEAN-CLAUDE shanda-tonme* to harass my genitor and mother Rose SANGNOU to try to bring myself by force to a psychiatric destructive mind place.

JERUSALEM-APOSTOLAT rosicrucian sect tried to follow myself these last 2 days using the brigand 'Moise BATOMEN', and another person male, THAT i don't know whereabouts but that live behind "Carine Lele Njougep Tchana" house for at least 6 months from now backwards in time !

Just 1 month before, I was stopped from walking by to our main official road by a sectarian female of Jerusalem-APOSTOLAT. I now see that it was meant to bring myself to other roads were they don't have their own people on it, so they could hijack myself properly to bring by force to a psychiatric hospital so to try to deteriorate my physical and psy body.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (4.)

39.39 SHANDA SANOU patrice cabral idiot son of Dorothée Shanda Owona passes away at age 33 (March 18, 2024)

"Dorothée Shanda Owona" who had tried to make myself sodomized "by Bertrand of Laquintinie" in Feb. 2021, illegally by police force.

SHE leaves now her son out of life after 3.5 years trying to destroy my life; Probably because she got some laundry money for this dirty task against A BORN-AGAIN-CHRISTIAN !

NONE of the people I have heard from coming back "from some kind of obituary ceremony" could even see any corpse of ATTORNEY OF LAW, deceased, Patrick Cabral SHANDA SANOU !

40.40 Dr. Annie Metiam, Spouse Eric-POKAM-WAM tries to say something illegally about my mental health publicly (May 23, 2024)

A sister of my mother and genitor ROSE SANGNOU, DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, sends a RECORDED AUDIO MESSAGE via whatsapp-phone-android-application, without any request from "Rose Sangnou" and / or my person about a supposed mental health abilities report that She as GASTROENTEROLOGIST has wrote based on our investigation whatsapp call that was done in year 2023 during around the month of JUNE.

This retarded personage that was initially at "Alfred Saker School" oriented to perform Commerce AND Accounting, WITH A grade of 10.00/20 is an idiot; Not just because *she doesn't even have a "degree of Doctor of Medicine (Dr. med.)"*.

This happens unsolicited as I am having a talk together with "Rose Sangnou"; AND "PASTOR marco OF Pentecostal Christian CHURCH" ' 'chapelle de la gloire de christ" in DLA.

I AM SUSPICIOUS of this corrupt C.P.D.M aunt that has german citizenship to be from Central Intelligence Agency (CIA); hired specially to try to kill me by any means; even using sorcery.

41.41 YAGER MABOMA is an idiot of justice judge here in CMR

Since 2021, February that I have complaint for a group of harassers that came into my compound to brutalize myself in front of a so called judge of instruction from sawa tribal tribe, I STILL RECEIVE PEOPLE TRYING TO AGGRESS and Harass myself.

42.42 I-xavier-went on roads to shout That I required JUSTICE for my saved life by SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA

- **Wednesday 28th of JUNE 2024:** "Proverbs 1 : 18 – 21 (in Holy bible of JEOVAH-NISSI in Heaven)"

Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA was sodomized both physically and mentally to release myself as a client, So I will go in front of a judge without the initial attorney I have chosen myself.

I went to road "in AHALA-simbock" to shout at populace that I MUST HAVE JUSTICE DONE against people who broke my gate in the night of FEBRUARY 2023 to kill me with psy-drugs involuntarily.

Politics is going on thoroughly because the year 2025 must released a president of the republic of cameroon !

43.43 YAGER MABOMA has sent my documents to Attorney-prosecutor

- **SATURDAY 31th of AUGUST 2024:**

I hope I can finish this matter without a judge that has been sodomized by "BIYA-clique".

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" said to myself on my cell phone that I sent to him at least 2 other attorneys of law so to replace him; Which is FALSE.

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" has received money from PAUL-biya.

"Tchonang albertine" is now the person I asked for, for assistance."

"I received this name and contact from my friend and customer "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL SARL" based in Akwa-douala ! "

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (5.)

44.44 Police of AHALA – 19ème arrondissement harassing myself because of SHANDA-tonmeo **Friday 6th of September 2024:**

"NESTOR kenfack tries to talk to my genitor and adversary ROSE-Sangnou without asking anything to myself."

"ROSE-idiot sangnou went to give certain objects to "NESTOR and VALÉRIE kenfack" that are supposed to be my sole customers and friends; Without any intermingled relationship with ROSE-sangnou since I told both of them THAT I am not interested into talking with someone who has tried to kill myself."

"I KNOW that it is C.P.D.M that went to give money to these burglars ("NESTOR" & "VALÉRIE") so they will try to intervene against my interests when court justice comes AS this has been the case with my personal attorney of law the culprit "SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA"."

45.45 CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Saturday 10th of November 2024:**

"A culprit called CLOVIS kemmegne, an intelligence secret service agent of GENDARMERIE NATIONALE of CAMEROON is tring to put troubles into my life via false divulged information around my new business relationships with a new tenant that I could gained via a so called "RENTAL PROPERTY MANAGER"-EMMANUEL-idiot."

"NOW that i have been staying in douala for more than 4-days in a row since my last hijack-attempt, in a so-called inherited property of noumbissi-vilain-idiot-THÉODORE; I can see that clovis kemmgne changed the colours GREEN-Yellow-gendarmerie of his GAY-young-porn-female-clairvoyant-boy-jackdaniels; INTO a BLUE-presidential-GRAY-porn-DGRE colors."

"INSTEAD of doing is openly called business of electronics computer technician, and also, "GAY-handler-bar-JACKS.", THIS guja-gay is hiding himself behind my sister and my mother-side family to plan a so-called "CONSTAT-de-FAIT" for the idiot of justice judge HUGUES-alain-yager maboma-faineant."

"THE other gay-called napoa-maxime-eteme; a viagra-gay that seems to be a burglar to myself since BAMKOUI said to me he didn't worked at all for SEMIL; BUT is working for CMR-navy in DOUALA; came openly salute myself, together with another idiot called KAMGAIN jean-pierre;"

"i hope only "jean-loïc siewe and belvianne" that seemed to be young fellow cameroonian entrepreneurs are not intermeddle here."

"i can already see that siewe's mother is from the idiot-village-Babouantou !."

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (VI (6).)

CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Wednesday 13th of November 2024:**

"SIEWE and BELVIANNE his collaborator of my new rental property seem to be not able to accommodate well due to destructive actions in water plumbery that seemed to be have done by a previous renter called; AND from R.D.P.C-C.P.D.M-south-bulu-tribe: GERMAIN Blaise ndzie and his wife called Geneviève Ndzie."

"~~Dr. —NOMO siméon-replacement~~ by C.P.D.M.-eyoump-psy; A so-called MAXIME-napoa-eteme called someone I am not sure "Docteur" while I was crossing a street at DLA-cité-des-palmiers yesterday evening; THIS gay-female-psy-hijackist; THAT seemed to be an organizer of my killing via the hijack of my private property in DLA-FEBRURAY-2024 is the one that talked to my 1st before a same day at night I was hijacked. "

"~~MAXIME-napoa-eteme~~ the gay-female-idiot is also from BETI-ekang-amougou-beling-TRAIBAL-tribe as a previous renter called NDZIE geneviève. "

o **SUNDAY 17th of November 2024:**

"IT seems there are no repression against criminals that come officially against my personal and / or familiar interests in CMR. "

"FOR INSTANCE, a family from "BATIÉ-ouest-cmr" that bake "beignets" and that used to transport "Pouse-Pousse" has built a 'bidon-ville-taudis' directly closed to my compound, Where my late father dear THEODORE-idiot noumbissi built a ground foundation, Without any rejection from SOUS-Préfecture that I contacted using my Attorney at law Mr. JUSTICE (Maître Synclaire NJEUTCHA tchana)."

"Some folk around this place in Béedi told me that:

1. "A beauty-gay hair-cut society wearing black and /or rosa T-SHIRTS, based on the opposite side of road to CLOVIS-telecom-Alias-kemmegne-gendarmerie-nationale-CMR";

"Sent a hijacker wearing finger-female-paint to say to people around where I was sitting reading my Bible-holy; That I AM SAID to be a mad-person; "

"BEFORE this physical attack even though I WASN'T talking to that gendarme that seems to act as a gay-female-hair treater; I COULD see a woman from CHRISTIAN-eyoum-tribal-tribe called Assassin. "

2. "Clovis telecom Alias clovis kemmegne" has repeatedly summon several people to harass me with no fear since he is well connected with ETOO-fils, a burglar called in CMR Soccer-player-female-male-born-again-gay-hijackist-Christian-eyoum "
3. "Maxime NAPOA-eteme is the one who told this very strange family since they don't do anything apparently to survive in Douala other than sneaking other people properties; WHERE enforced by "NAPOA ETEME, MAXIME" to Hijack myself even physically because I AM A NOBODY IN THIS COUNTRY called CAMEROON. "
4. "i suspect the current president of the republic of CMR called PAUL-biya to be behind this multi-attempt to destroy my life; Since for all my legal complaints nothing could be done for at least more than 12 years. "
5. "paul-biya-junior is mad; a culprit from mvomekaa. "

o **WEDNESDAY 27th of November 2024:**

"This new renter of mine a so-called-CALLPRIT jean-loïc siewe, And BELVIANNE meleu nossi seem not to even welcome very nicely their clients because they left so dirty the entrance step-feet of their rented apartment for 138 EUROS monthly. "

"ALSO this belvianne aged of 25th years old seem not to understand that I AM NOT CONFIDENT of renewing their rental agreement because of all inconsistencies I COULD notice since they entered this apartment inherited of mine:"

1. Her national identity card says she is "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala".

THERE was a so-called "gendarme-etoga-idiot" call Jonas-Kemajou-fainénat that scammed myself around 3 000 EUROS, And that was wearing a gendarme-green-attire, And that also has this "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala" instead of something professional-criminal-armed-robber-south-west-CMR.

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 1

- 1.) *STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS, MASTER'S DEGREE THESIS DEFENSE TALK, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE (FB 3), UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY* |★| *MAY "2007"*
- 2.) *STATICALLY VERIFYING API USAGE RULES USING TRACEMATCHES, 9th Workshop on Compiler-Driven Performance, CASCON 2010, Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham Conference Centre, MARKHAM, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)* |★| *NOVEMBER "2010"*
- 3.) *TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-based SOFTWARE, PH.D. THESIS EXAMINATION COMPREHENSIVE !, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)* |★| *DECEMBER "2011"*
- 4.) *Course project small talk-presentation in front of PATRICK-lam-idiot & course ECE 750 students, 1 EIT room I don't remember code room number digits, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA* *Spring "2013"*
- 5.) *(prepared based on result outcome of talk given during Spring 2013 for course project.); CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, ECE GRAD TALK, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA* *April "2014"*
- 6.) *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES SEMINAR, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA* *JANUARY "2015"*
- 7.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; sns cameroon ltd (Mr. DIVINE Njobati); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2016"*
- 8.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; best car care & services (Mr. HENRI ngatchou); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2016"*
- 9.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; snob bazar outlet stores (Mr. LAVOISIER); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *MAY "2016"*
- 10.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; expert3dev s.a.r.l (Mr. Momo); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JUNE "2016"*
- 11.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bilingual entente bookshop (Mr. JACQUES); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2017"*
- 12.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; BLACK & WHITE snack bars (Mr. TOM & Mr. AURÉLIEN iloga iloga (ecobank poste centrale yaoundé)); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JUNE "2017"*
- 13.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for COMPUTER INFORMATICS ENGINEERING TRAINING; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; IUC [Institut Universitaire de la Côte] (Mr. HYPOLITHE Tekeu); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON* *SEPTEMBER "2017"*
- 14.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS TALKS; Dr. SANDY beidu; Dr. ERIC brefo-mensah; WATERLOO; ON; CANADA* *JUNE "2018"*
- 15.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for CROWD FUNDING REQUEST PROPOSAL; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION (for "MS WINDOWS"); BAFIASOFT (Mr. CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong); WATERLOO; ON; CANADA* *SEPTEMBER "2018"*
- 16.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; coplatec s.a.r.l (Mr. CONSTANT Kemmogne); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON* *MAY "2020"*
- 17.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and drugstore selling; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pharmacy fiango lycée MAKÉPÉ (Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2021"*
- 20.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and INDUSTRIAL logistics; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bontée s.a.r.l (Ms. ARLETTE [Sibeufo-mpay-army-general-spouse-in-official]); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *FEBRUARY "2021"*
- 21.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and PRODUCTION planing; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; CROQUE-MATIN (Mr. MOUSSA Saliou); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *MARCH "2021"*
- 22.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL ("MS WINDOWS 2000"); elektro maképé (Mr. ARMSTRONG); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *JUNE "2021"*
- 23.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; établissement kenfack (Mr. KENFACK); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *JULY "2021"*
- 24.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; clinique de l'espérance (Mr. YVES Mogo); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *SEPTEMBER "2021"*
- 25.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *OCTOBER "2021"*
- 26.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie la confiance (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON* *NOVEMBER "2021"*

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 2

- 27.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie n.k. (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **NOVEMBER "2021"**
- 28.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mr. FABRICE Siemeni); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 29.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 30.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND networked installations; quincaillerie aimée (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **JUNE "2022"**
- 31.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND commercial financial accounting; poissonnerie plus (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **SEPTEMBER "2022"**
- 32.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0 BRIEF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PRESENTATION; ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE YAOUNDÉ - ENSPY (PROF. DR.-ENG. THOMAS NDIÉ DJOTIO); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON* **May "2023"**
- 33.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER TRAINING; happiness potential sarl (DIPL.-ING. (FH) DR. FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI, M.Sc); Douala; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **August "2023"**
- 34.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER financial accounting SHORT PRESENTATION VIEW DEMONSTRATION; quincaillerie aimée sarl (Ms. CHRISTELLE spouse NAMEKONG, B.SC.); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **December "2023"**
- 35.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 VERY SHORT INFORMATION SESSION; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mrs. Hecna Ngayam) ; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 36.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-FOSS SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Hilaire Yimdjo, B.Sc. in Computer Science (entrepreneur in car care and management); Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 37.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in hardware shop and grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 12, "2024"**
- 38.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 Installation hardware checks; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 13, "2024"**
- 39.) Aborted installation & training of family association "MA-sangnou-idiot-bangou"; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON. **March "2025"**
- 40.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur-woman-lady from Douala-sawa tribe; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **March, "2025"**
Based on our remarks to this lady of very low class revenue, we could find that we may add an option for "automatically recalculating cost-price of acquisition."
WE see here an opportunity to examine how to improve quality & revenue of this low-class entrepreneurial adventure !
THIS kind of entrepreneurial organization is very pro-eminent in Douala-sawa tribe as customers come into living-house to buy. !
- 41.) **YERITH-ERP-9.0 design introspective view talk accompanied with Q&A (Questions & Answers) by management consultant IRIS mbieukop; [M. Iris-mbieukop] is an expert using MS-excel & PowerBI (BUSINESS intelligence).** **April, "2025"**
VERY impressive questions that could make our start-up "YERITH R&D" [improve YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum in terms of Ergonomics (color management)], and / or functionality; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON
 ► **June 11, 2025 :**
[This guja seems to be an EYOUM because he was looking quite strange while I just great him yesterday night while entering DLA.] Kind-of son of a guja call PAUL-fokamn-kemmogne—idiot.
- 42.) **[YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum short introduction]; MBA-Claude BISSEG (bisseg@yahoo.fr); Very interesting introspective towards reconfiguring pricing options !**
Very similar to Microsoft Dynamics & Sales Forces software. MBA-Claude BISSEG seems to want trying this as a rental software monthly around "20, 000 Francs CFA monthly". **May 12, "2025"**
HIS father, M. BISSEG is a very well respected member of Lions-Club Douala, TOGETHER for instance with Dr.-criminal GWET-bell !
Attorney of JUSTICE-congolaise-brazzaville Vicent GOMEX & President-Congolaise Sassou are also members of Lions-Club-INTERNATIONL-criminal !
- 43.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur named ROSTAND-moungam. Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **June 2, "2025"**
ROSTAND is a startuper that uses Programming language "DART" and also website builder application "flutter flow" to give maximal power to its clients that are in need of a webshop !"
ROSTAND is at time skeptical in trying YERITH R&D product YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum because it seems to him not very simple to implement according to his web presence requirements !"

List of Figures

1	A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME	17
2	A screenshot of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL error event log running on YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.	17
3	A sample YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET in action.	17
4	YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 generates legacy web files from Qt 5 interface files (".ui" files).	21
5	A Stack Stapled Architecture Overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0.	21
6	Webbrowser-based software architecture : at least 4 layers logical software architecture (Image modified from online pdf paper "FlashCache: A NAND Flash Memory File Cache for Low Power Web Servers" [https://doi.org/10.1145/1176760.1176774] by Trevor et al.). YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runtime monitors communication layers.	22
7	A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine file.	23
8	A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine.	23
9	YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL : A SCREENSHOT of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 generator within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.	26
10	A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart; Example created and / or inspired from QT-trolltech sample; in Documentation present; Statechart found in some place I don't remember yet.. . . .	27
11	A sample ping-pong parallel process depicted in Figure 10.	27
12	A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) file.	28
13	A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A SQL-database based only in a disk-file with not much roundabout code could also be used instead of a full-featured database management system such as MariaDB (https://www.mariadb.com). Q0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name) ; Q1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.dept_name).	28
14	A David-harel statechart modeling of a temporal property expressed as a finite state diagram machine of mealy-GEORGES in fig. 13.	28
15	A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart.	28
16	Software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: it is also a runtime monitor container for software verification.	29
17	YRI_QVGE software stack dependencies.	29
18	"Program verification (including model checking)" is a subset (⊂) of "SOFTWARE VERIFICATION". (See also research goal 13.)	30
19	Embedded program verifier notifier within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a background process service.	30
20	Runtime Verification Monitoring with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.	33
21	YERITH SDMM based runtime monitoring verification analysis.	33
22	A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.	33
23	A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS.	34
24	A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL ERROR EVENT LOG.	34
25	A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.	34
26	BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	35
27	Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	35
28	BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	36
29	Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	36
30	Manager Main Window in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum	37
31	Generic Schema of Trading Realtime with YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (French language)	38
32	YERITH-SAINT (LGPL license) : Accessing JAVA code with "Polyglot LLVM frontend" A Mealy Machine State Diagram (SDMM) Specified Using	39
33	YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF Specification Language for NO-WRITE-AFTER-CLOSE memory check API file usage rule.	39
34	YERITH-SAINT (LGPL license) Algorithms Architecture. "poolalloc" pointer-alias analysis tool from "Chris Lattner" at "APPLE Ltd." is re-used.	51
35	A sample API rule violation as tainted path "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i)) L4-L7-L9-L10-L11" (orange colored lines of code); on LLVM THREE-ADDRESS-CODE.	51
36	"Portrait of YERITH-NISSI. now 42 years old."	110

List of Tables

1	Software LICENsEs summary table.	14
2	Design Documents for the CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool YERITH_QVGE.	15
3	Design Documents for the Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF].	15
4	Design Documents for the Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]	15
5	Tools used for Qualification and / Or Certification at YERITH R&D.	16
6	A SOFTWARE architecture overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 ("An SDMM usage scenario by IBM-websphere".)	21
7	YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL keywords and meaning (An excerpt).	22
8	Jeeves Programming Language Versus (Vs.) The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	31
9	COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++, Python, AND JAVA. JAVA has an (interpretative and / or JIT-compiled) virtual machines that are in FACT reactive systems (E.g. : A "GUI software" is as well a reactive system) ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)	32
10	Comparison between 'YERITH-ERP-9.0' and 3 top tier-1 ERP systems	36
11	Visited Courses at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot	40
12	Visited Courses as post-doctoral researcher professor at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot	41
13	Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D]	110
14	Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D] — Continued.	111

"XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU [PR. PROF. DR.-ING.]"

R&D — RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT — SUMMARY

— RESEARCHING GOALS IN "DISTRIBUTED & OPERATING COMPUTING SYSTEM" (CONSTRUCTION & ANALYSIS & VERIFICATION & VALIDATION) —

- Create technology for easing life in Africa • Make human-being life easier and cheaper •

Research KEYwords : Yerith-Xavier-NOUNDOU ✓ ([2025]-(YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0); [2022]-SDMM; YRI_QVGE; YERITH-SAINT; [2006]-(Peleska. Yerith et al.); [2022]-KLAUS HAVELUND (LogSCOPE); [2017]-Frank-TIP-Koushik-SEN (EVENTRACECOMMANDER); [2007]-"Hendren, et al". (tracematches, S00T); THOMAS-reps (IFDS; IDE); [1977]-Gary-KILDALL ✓ (static code lattice-based "dataflow analysis"-seminal); [1977]-Patrick & Radia-COUSOT (Abstract INTERPRETATION);.

Figure 36: "Portrait of YERITH-NISSI. now 42 years old."

DOCTOR-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING. / PH.D.) in Electrical & Computer Engineering; UNiversity of waterloo-mutilative; '12/20/2011' !

★ — ★ DOCTOR-PH.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING. [21]) ★ — ★

Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree ("B.Sc & M.Sc." / Dipl.-Inf.); UNiversity-racist of BREMEN.; '05/25/2007'.
— Diplom-INFORMATIKER (Dipl.-Inf. [?]) —

■ UNIVERSITY publications | [Tranng](#) | [TALKS](#) | [Latest](#) | [Figures](#) | [Tables](#)

■ PUBLICATIONS at ["Start-Up YERITH R&D"]

- Resrching goals.
- Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise.
- PUBLICATIONS in FRENCH.
- PUBLICATIONS in English.
- Summary of PRO-eminant Contributions.
- Contacts with ACADEMIA—other than myself !

— Scholarships & Awards

- "Post- & Doctoral Research and Studies" at the UNiversity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 30 + 27 = 57-months" —.
- "GRADUATE [students] : Dr. ridha | Basser | Divam jain | Zheng FELIX fang".
- "Teaching for the UNiversity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 24-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "Graduate INTERN" at International Business Machinery (IBM), MARKHAM, Toronto, CANADA-idiot (<https://www.ibm.com/ca-en>) — " ≈ 8-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for AGBS - Arbeitsgruppe Betriebssysteme (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>), UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 6-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH) (<https://www.gewete.com>), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY — " ≈ 24-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "JUNIOR Software Developer" for SIEMENS-racist Medical Solutions (now SIEMENS-healthineers) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>) — " ≈ 21-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "(Part-Time) WEB AND 'RAD' APPLICATION DEVELOPER" at ZMML-racist, UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-angeber (<https://www.uni-bremen.de/en/zmml>) — " ≈ 25-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "Research Curriculum" at the UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 54-months" —.

46.46 Professor-professional Computing Scientific Association Memberships

■ Current: "~~aem: The Association for Computing Machinery~~"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

47.47 Hardware Products

■ ★ "Portable Computer for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring" : YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>).

48.48 Software (System) Products ("Progiiciels en langue Française")

■ ★ "WYSIWYG Web Designer Generated Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)[?].

■ "Runtime MONITORING tester verifier" : YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b].

■ "Computer-Aided Software Engineering (CASE) Design Tool for creating SDMM" : YRI_QVGE (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d].

49.49 Research Impact.

Table 13: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D]

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
1.	ERP – PGI introduction because of creation & proof-tested YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2025	Insertion of a placebo ERP-PGI software system by R.D.P.C-C.PDM-biya-in-year-2025	N.A
2.	★ Secured Web-browser architecture only 2-tiers layers .	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2025	1 st 2 layers web-browser based software architecture with security proof code backed and secure via model-checking runtime verification monitoring !	N.A
3.	★ Hardware YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2024	1 st open-sourced runtime verification on-the-fly; Also as Hot plug-in device embedded	CE
4.	★ Software YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL Software YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2024	"1.) WYSIWYG-Tool for HTML pages." 2.) HIGH-level view imperative Programming language for HTML pages dynamic; 3.) Automatic generation of safe & secure web sources files	N.A
5.	Software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2015	1 st Simpler to use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing). Starting age 12 years old.	N.A and / or O.H.A.D.A (not required at all)
6.	Program YERITH-SAINT	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2013	1 st temporal property verification by (staged-alias analysis) static taint analysis framework-algorithm in LLVM.	N.A

RESEARCH IMPACT — CONTINUED

Table 14: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D] — Continued.

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
7.	A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine).	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2022	1.) 1 st fully compliant to "David-harel statechart"—"mealy machine" STATE DIAGRAM formalization for runtime monitoring verification & automatic model-based statechart-code-generation; 2.) Checks for forbidden trace specification across software system with no additional runtime overhead as demonstrated by concurrent event stream analysis technique	N/A
8.	Software YRI_QVGE	CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool	YEAR-2022	1 st CASE-Tool for designing by drawing state diagram mealy machine (SDMM); 2.) 1 st model checker at runtime that encompasses Mealy-machine as opposed And not KRIPKE-structure !	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
9.	Software YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2022	1 st open code sourced Runtime MONITOR container (generator) software for "SDMM"	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
10.	Algorithms not published in any journal And / Or conference due to missing financial funding.	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2015	Various algorithms for creating working User-QT software easily	N/A
11.	[UWATERLOO-SE 465-ECE 453] — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL".	Unit Testing	YEAR-2009	Pragmatic Junit 4 Tutorial aided with "Cobertura Test Coverage Analyzer"	N/A
12.	Software "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (N.A).	Static Program Code Analysis Checking	YEAR-2013	Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints.	N/A
13.	Software YERITH-XRESIN-SOFTWARE.	Web Apps Program Analysis	YEAR-2013	A dynamic taint analysis software for Security for PHP in a JAVA PHP Interpreter.	N/A
14.	Taxonomy of Program-Software Verification & Analysis.	Software Verification	YEAR-2023	Unique positioning and specification of PROGRAM-software Verification & Analysis.	N/A
15.	MASTER thesis – Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems (N.A).	Test Cases / Test Data — Generation	YEAR-2007	Statistical uniform distribution generation of test cases for statechart diagrams.	N.A and / or A.R.I.N.C
16.	Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata (N.A).	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2004	A set of transformations from Büchi automata to Timed Automata.	N/A

- Our commitment to create software tools & programs for insuring a better and safe software system quality as both open-sourced and priced products, Enables now young immature software developers and engineers in under-developed Africa to have better products and quality at a low cost price : ["Software Products at YERITH R&D"]. TABLE 13, TABLE 14 illustrate sample products, both potential-in-preparation hardware, and already available (accompanying) software.

THIS statement previously made is also available for medium sized companies in west developed countries where even not far as for in year 2000, and also years before; CRASHES of aircraft "Ariane 5 occurred and other airplanes from Airbus and BOEING, causing lost of several human being lives.

- YOUNG adults aged around \approx 12 years old can now start learning using a full-featured ERP-trading stock exchange software that uses a very simplified everyday language as testified by our previous report of "Start-Up YERITH R&D" for years 2022 – 2023 : "REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023) (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>)".

This couldn't be possible years before starting 2015 when I started creating YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM; Our previous assertion is corroborated by deployment of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum at at least 5 locations in Yaounde & Douala, in main cities of Cameroun, which is the leader of central africa economic zone C.E.M.A.C (<https://www.cemac.int>).

50.50 Tools & Programming Language Expertise

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming and Compiler Frameworks (including IDE):** DIFF, Patch, Txl, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

51.51 Teaching for the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada–racist.

Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].

52.52 Summary of Professional Training in USA, Canada, & Germany

- "Professional international workshops and conferences". 2001 – 2015

53.53 Teaching / summary of competencies Acquired at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA–RACIST.

- "Formal training at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during post–doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2012 – 2015

54.54 Teaching ONLINE on the World Wide Web UNIVERSITY–level (graduate) Students.

I currently live in Africa, Cameroon where I cannot have a position at my level of knowledge and experience in a formal Cameroonian UNIVERSITY.

 "POUR les usagers de la langue FRANÇAISE : "Enseignant d'université"; ET NON Enseignant–employé d'université (d'État); EST 1 des définitions du mot professeur."

 Enseignant d'université signifie divulguer des enseignements académiques de rang doctoral et post–doctoraux aux apprenants des universités du monde. "LE titre et grade académique de *Ph.D. et / ou Docteur-de-3^{ème} cycle universitaire*" en est l'approbation universellement reconnue en ma connaissance.

Nonetheless I still teach via WWW books & tools, & programs that I deem at University level graduate courses level; Based on my "doctoral & post–doctoral Ph.D. studies In Computer Software Engineering" & work at the University–racist of Waterloo.

I am developing course material for online worldwide university level (graduate) students as depicted online on "zenodo.org" (<https://www.zenodo.org>) :

I.) Topic : SOFTWARE SYSTEM

- 1.) **FORMAL METHODS** using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) for runtime monitoring and verification (via model checking) :
 - YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>)
 - A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine) – Book Preprint (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
 - User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
- 2.) World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH–WEB–DSL–9.0" : book in preparation, together with accompanying CDROM–USB-key dongle. (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)
- 3.) **SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE** : SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH–ERP–3.0[?]: (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf);
- 4.) **SOFTWARE VERIFICATION AND ANALYSIS** : " Temporal Property Verification in Plugin–based Software by Program Analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10990602>)".

II.) Topic : ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE & TOOLS

55.55 Research Expertise (PR. PROF. DR.-ING.)■ **Business Informatics** ⇒ **illustrative figure of business workflow of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.**○ **Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery**

- 1.) **ERP Software: "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"?**; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0> C++; Qt 5; [03/2015 -]

■ **Software Engineering**○ **Web Apps Program Analysis**

- 2.) 3 **A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus**; <https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis> JAVA; Firebug; [01/2013 - 04/2013]

○ **Web Apps Automatic Generation** ⇒ **illustrative table of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 (Section 27.27.5).**

- 3.) **YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL[27.27]**; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9> flex, bison; [06/2024 -]

○ **Debugging Tool**

- 4.) 20.20 **Open Source Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"**; https://github.com/yerithrd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; [07/2023 -]

○ **CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool**

- 5.) 1 **"MBT-RT-TESTER PLUGIN" FOR "Borland-Together"**[1b] C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "www.verified.de" [09/2006 - 02/2007]
6.) **YRI_QVGE[1]** C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Compiler Technology**

- 7.) 34 **Ph.D. dissertation: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM**; <https://github.com/AmesianX/saint> LLVM; — 03/2015 —
8.) 1d **A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language**; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; [04/2023 -]

■ **Software Engineering** ► **Software Verification** ⇒ **figure illustrating components of it (Section 13.13.1).**○ **Static Program Code Analysis Checking à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945)".**

- 9.) 1(1)4 **Conference Article : Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints** JUnit; SOOT; JAVA; — 2013 —
10.) 32 **Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software** SOOT; JAVA; — 12/2011 —

○ **Dynamic Program Binary Runtime Analysis Verification**

- 11.) 1 **YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime**;
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-DBus; [06/2022 -]
12.) 1f **A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library**; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Unit Testing**

- 13.) II **Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL"** JAVA; JUnit; "COBERTURA coverage analyzer" — 10/2009 —

○ **Test Cases / Test Data — Generation**

- 14.) 1a **Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems** C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "RT-Tester" — 05/2007 —

■ **Theoretical Computer Science**○ **Concurrent Systems, AUTOMATA theory**

- 15.) 1d **Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata** Set-Algebra; — 12/2004 —

56.56 Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise

- A.) **C++**; & **JAVA**; & **SQL – DBMS (Database Management System) MariaDB** with **DEBIAN LINUX & SVN** (E.g. : *(Part-Time) Student Software Developer Position* (<https://www.gewete.com>))
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER — Team Lead of myself at that time* 2005 – 2007
 b.) *Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH — Technical Lead of myself at that time* 2005 – 2007
- B.) **C++** with **MS Windows (XP, 98,2000,7,10,11)** & **FSM (Finite State Machines)** & **Rational ClearCase** (E.g. : *Junior Software Developer position*) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG — Team Lead of myself at that time* 2007 – 2009
 b.) *Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAUIGLIA — Technical Lead of myself at that time* 2007 – 2009
- C.) **ERP System YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : *Inventor & Developer*)
 SUCCESSFULLY Used & Re-Tested.
 a.) *Annual reports : REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>) 2021 – 2023
 b.) *[Document local link !]*
- D.) **Software Testing (UNIT, Integration)** with **UML 2.0-HybridUML (Statechart by David-HAREL)** & **C++** (E.g. : *Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN-racist-idiot, BREMEN-germany, Germany-racist*)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska — MSc-advisor of myself at that time, Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH.* 2004 – 2007
 b.) *Prof. Dr. Rolf Drechsler — MSc-advisor of myself at that time* 2004 – 2007
 c.) *Diplomarbeit Kolloquium MASTER-thesis defence* May 25, "2007"
- E.) **JAVA** with **JUnit** (E.g. : *SE 465-ECE 453 — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL"*)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — Course Instructor.* SPRING term (Jan. – Apr.) – 2010
- F.) **Web Apps Automatic Generation** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : *"WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0"*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/17466696>)
 a.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OWOLABI Legunsen, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA-*
 b.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Christian RIKONG Ngueyong, AS-degree in Computer Science, Santa monica-california, USA-*
 c.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Djotio Ndie-*
 d.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Patrick-LAM-*
- G.) **Web Apps Program Analysis** with **Quercus & JAVA** (E.g. : *A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus, CS846 at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Frank Tip, Ph.D. – COURSE instructor* APRIL 30, "2013"
- H.) **Program Code Binary Analysis** with **SDMM & YERITH_QVGE** (E.g. : *Software Testing of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum & Runtime Monitoring Verification.*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>)
 a.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OWOLABI Legunsen, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA* December 20, "2025"
 b.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska — Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH.* October 7, "2025"
 c.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of KLAUS HAVELUND, Researcher at N.A.S.A., U.S.A.* July 11, "2025"
- I.) **Program Code Static Analysis** with **apache ANT, SOOT & JAVA** (E.g. : *Doctoral TheSis at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — PH.D.-advisor of myself at that time* December 20, "2011"
 b.) *Prof. Dr. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — at my request before my PhD Comprehensive Examination* December "2011"
 c.) *PhD Comprehensive Examination – ECE-University of waterloo* December 20, "2011"
- J.) **Software Vulnerability Analysis** using **LLVM & C++** (E.g. : *Doctoral Dissertation in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. — at my request before my ECE graduate research seminar talk* "2014"
 b.) *ECE Graduate Seminar Talk Series at THE university of waterlloo-racist, ontario, canada* April, 16 "2014"
 c.) *PhD Dissertation Defence – CS-University of waterloo* January "2015"

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)

- 1.) A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMATA AND TIMED AUTOMATA, INDEPENDENT STUDY, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA. JANUARY 2005
- 2.) STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html), MASTER'S DEGREE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, AND PROF. DR. PHIL. NAT. ROLF DRECHSLER. MAY 25, 2007
- 3.) RESEARCH MASTER PROJECT REPORT cognitive agents, [Research Project Report Robotic-Cognition-Cartography], UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY DR.-ING. LUTZ Frommberger, DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. Frank DYLLA, PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. Christian FRESKA. July 2006

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.uwaterloo.ca>)

- 1.) JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>), UNDERGRADUATE COURSE LECTURES NOTES 'SOFTWARE TESTING, QUALITY ASSURANCE AND MAINTENANCE', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. OCTOBER 31, 2009
- 2.) TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-BASED SOFTWARE (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>), PHILOSOPHY DOCTOR (PH.D.) DISSERTATION, (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. DECEMBER 20, 2011
- 3.) DYNAMIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR PHP IN QUERCUS (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) (◆[git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis); ◆[git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)), PH.D. GRADUATE COURSE PROJECT 'program analysis of web apps', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY FULL PROFESSOR FRANK TIP. APRIL 30, 2013

**JAVA application server "Quercus" — JAVA-PHP-interpreter
PROGRAM analysis of web apps
SOFTWARE cyber-security**

- "[THIS course CS846 project led by Professor doctor Frank TIP], was about creating a security taint analysis program code in JAVA for the "Quercus JAVA PHP Interpreter", which is a web application server, COMPARABLE to Apache-Tomcat (<https://www.tomcat.org>); And that enables PHP developers to use existing JAVA libraries within their PHP code as well. "
- "I have implemented and tested a dynamic taint analysis using Firebug, and FirePHP. THIS taint analysis enables to warn developers about data and values that originate from outside the webserver, and / or also about values that emerge as results from operations that involve "tainted values"; MEANING values that are considered not safe because they originate from the outside world of the Quercus web application server. "
- "Taking particular care of unsafe outside world data and values (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) allows developers to avoid web cyber-software security vulnerabilities attacks such as SQL injection, BUFFER-OVERFLOW attacks, format string vulnerabilities, etc.."

► YEAR-2024

IN our project YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0, we will need to instrument binaries of a running JAVA virtual machine; Most probably "Debian-Linux OpenJDK Runtime Environment" (<https://docs.oracle.com>).

THIS binary instrumentation technology from INTEL-pin (<https://www.intel.com/missingfornow>) has an advantage over reinstrumenting and recompiling code sources each time any Qt-DBus message has been introduced and / or modified in tool YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

- 4.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK, (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. MARCH 10, 2015

**Heartbleed BUG security breach SSL-1.0.1-f (<https://heartbleed.com>)
Static PROGRAM code analysis of C programs
LLVM code; SOFTWARE cyber-security**
- 5.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM TOOL USER'S GUIDE (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051299>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK artifact, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. [OCTOBER 2015]

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (in English language) (II)

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

57.57 YERITH R&D – Algorithms Excerpt not published in conference papers due to resources.

1. [Created Algorithms Link].

58.58 YERITH R&D – Reports

2. *REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, November 23, 2025. November 23, 2025.
3. *REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023)* (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, October 1, 2023. October 1, 2023.

59.59 Business Informatics Management Knowledge

5. *YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum SOFTWARE SYSTEM PRODUCT SHEET* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17661983>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
6. *ADVANTAGES OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum COMPARED TO OTHER TOP ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEMS* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662017>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
7. *INFORMATION BROCHURE OF ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662117>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
8. *INSTALLATION GUIDE FOR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum* (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060182/>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021.

60.60 Associated Computer Devices

9. *YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum RECOMMENDED POINT-OF-SALE HARDWARE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17661831>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.

61.61 Advanced Software Technology

10. *"WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0"* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>),
BOOK, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, March 2025. March 2025.
11. *Concepts around real-time trading for physical and / or virtual stocks with software system: YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME* (<https://zenodo.org/records/14505133>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, DECEMBER 17, 2024. DECEMBER 17, 2024.
12. *A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
Book in preparation, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2025. 2025.
13. *User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2023. 2023.
14. *YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>),
DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MAY 2022. MAY 2022.
15. *Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>),
Journal article in preparation, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, August 2023. August 2023.
16. *Compendium of Documents About the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, June 2023. June 2023.
17. *SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/uploads/17662181>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
10. *YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051303>),
CONFERENCE article in submission, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, February 2023. February 2023.

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (en langue française) (III)

[LIEN interne à ce document sur mes Spécialités en recherche académique et / ou Professionnelle.]

62.62 YERITH R&D – Algorithmes scientifiques (En Anglais) – Non publiés dans 1 journal pour causes de ressources financières entre autres.

1. [Lien sur des algorithmes repertoriés et Créés par moi !]

63.63 YERITH R&D – Rapports

2. *RAPPORTS DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
3. *RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0 (années 2015–2022)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, OCTOBRE 2022. OCTOBRE 2022.

64.64 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Connaissances Marketing

4. *BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680727>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025

65.65 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Management des données

5. *GUIDE DE L'UTILISATEUR 'MANAGER', PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/record/8058259/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, JUIN 2018. JUIN 2018
6. *YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: ESSAI DE PRODUCTIVITÉ ENTREPRENEURIALE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071437>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021. MARS 2021
7. *GUIDE PRATIQUE DU LOGICIEL DE GESTION COMMERCIALE ET FINANCIÈRE YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680818>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
8. *DOCUMENT COMBINANT LES PRÉSENTATIONS DE YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680860>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
9. *FICHE DE DONNÉES DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680904>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
10. *BROCHURE D'INFORMATION DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680949>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
11. *AVANTAGES DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 COMPARATIVEMENT À SAGE GESCOM I7, ET À SAP BUSINESS ONE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680986>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
12. *AVANTAGES D'UTILISATION DE L'INFORMATIQUE POUR LA GESTION DE STOCKS* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681077>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
13. *BRÈVE PRÉSENTATION DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI) YERITH-PGI-3.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681095>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
14. *GUIDE D'INSTALLATION POUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060217>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021. MARS 2021
15. *YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 : Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681136>), Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES), YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025

66.66 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — COMPTABILITÉ analytique

17. *YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: NOTIONS DE COMPTABILITÉ ET DE SYSTÈME O.H.A.D.A* (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071458>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021. MARS 2021

67.67 INFORMATIQUE de gestion-PGI-Erp — Accessoires Recommandés

18. *MATÉRIEL INFORMATIQUE RECOMMANDÉ POUR LE POINT-DE-VENTE YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681167>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025

68.68

Ingénierie du Proiciel TRès Avancée

19. **YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAT / PH.D. COMPENDIUM** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>),
DOCTORAT COMPENDIUM, **YERITH R&D**, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MAI 2022.

MAI 2022